

Graduate School for Cellular and Biomedical Sciences
University of Bern

Large Language Model Methods for Protein Engineering and Antibody Discovery

PhD Thesis submitted by

Chiara Rodella

for the degree of

PhD in Computational Biology

Supervisor

Prof. Dr. Thomas Lemmin
Institute of Biochemistry and Molecular Medicine
Faculty of Medicine of the University of Bern

Co-advisor

Prof. Dr. Matteo Dal Peraro
Laboratory for Biomolecular Modeling
EPFL - Swiss Federal Technology Institute of Lausanne

Accepted by the Faculty of Medicine, the Faculty of Science and the Vetsuisse Faculty of the University of Bern at the request of the Graduate School for Cellular and Biomedical Sciences

Bern, Dean of the Faculty of Medicine

Bern, Dean of the Faculty of Science

Bern, Dean of the Vetsuisse Faculty Bern

*Alla mia Noni, per renderla ancora più orgogliosa di me.
Al mio Eddi, senza il quale questa tesi probabilmente non sarebbe neanche stata compilata.*

Abstract

Proteins are fundamental to nearly all biological processes, acting as enzymes, structural components, signaling molecules, and therapeutic agents. Understanding how proteins function and how their functional properties arise from their **amino acid sequences**, has long been a central challenge in molecular biology and biomedical research. The ability to decode and design proteins with specific properties has become increasingly critical for both basic science and **therapeutic development**.

Over the past decades, technological breakthroughs in genomics, proteomics, and structural biology have revolutionized our view of proteins. While the genome offers a relatively stable blueprint, the **proteome**, the complete set of proteins expressed by a cell, tissue, or organism, is dynamic, context-dependent, and influenced by factors such as developmental stage, environment, and disease. Proteins can exist in multiple isoforms, undergo post-translational modifications, and interact in intricate networks. This complexity has driven an explosion of scientific interest and highlighted the need for tools capable of **interpreting and manipulating proteins** at scale.

However, studying proteins remains a formidable challenge. **Traditional approaches** for understanding protein structure and function, are often **time-consuming, costly, and difficult to scale**. These limitations have motivated the search for computational approaches capable of predicting protein behavior directly from sequence information. In this context, the advent of **deep learning**, and particularly **large language models (LLMs)** adapted from natural language processing, has opened transformative new possibilities. By treating protein sequences as a **“language” shaped by evolution**, these models are able to learn rich, contextual representations that capture biochemical, structural, and functional properties from large-scale sequence data alone.

This thesis explores how large language models can be applied to address key challenges in **protein engineering** and **antibody discovery**, two fields at the cutting edge of therapeutic development. By leveraging the representational power of **protein language models**, we aim to facilitate the analysis, design, and generation of functional proteins. We develop TemBERTure, a model that predicts **protein thermostability** from sequence alone, a feature influencing therapeutic efficacy and developability. We then concentrate on the **identification of antibodies** with neutralizing activity against challenging targets such as HIV-1, showcasing how LLMs can accelerate biologic discovery. By focusing on sequence-level data—particularly the CDRH3 region—the developed model H3BERTa enhances **interpretability** and guides the rational design of next-generation protein therapeutics. We also present a framework for modeling **antibody heavy and light chain pairing**, and for generating plausible light chains conditioned on a given heavy chain, offering new capabilities for antibody repertoire reconstruction and design.

Keywords: Protein engineering, computational biology, deep learning, large language models, protein stability, antibody discovery, HIV-1, sequence analysis, Next Generation Sequencing (NGS), therapeutic design.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my supervisor, Professor Thomas Lemmin. His guidance and mentorship have been very important from my earliest research time through the completion of this PhD thesis. His support, profound expertise, and thoughtful insights have shaped not only the work presented here but also my development as an independent researcher. I am especially thankful for his kindness and understanding over the years, and for fostering a stimulating, encouraging environment that has sustained my curiosity and will continue to guide my future work.

I would also like to thank Edoardo G. Filippi-Mazzola for our spirited exchanges of ideas and for supporting me through moments of overwhelming stress. You are my comforting shoulder when I needed it.

I also wish to honor my grandmother, who witnessed the beginning of this journey but, sadly, did not see its completion. Words cannot capture how grateful I am for her love and belief in me, but I know she is proud of this achievement wherever she may be.

I owe special thanks to Symela Lazaridi for the laughter, the loud, unforgettable memories, and the anecdotes that I will always cherish. I am also deeply grateful to Giulia Peteani, who started as a colleague and blossomed into a dear friend with whom I have shared countless snack breaks and conversations. To Axel and Calvin, thank you for the moments we have shared, the funny spirit that enriched my journey, and above all, the laughter.

Finally, I extend my sincere appreciation to everyone who has contributed indirectly to this project. In particular, I am grateful to the members of my dissertation committee for dedicating their time and expertise to reviewing my work and offering such insightful feedback.

Contents

Abstract	iii
Acknowledgements	iv
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background and general context	1
1.1.1 Foundations of protein biology	1
1.1.2 Protein engineering in biomedicine	5
1.1.3 Emergence of large language models in protein engineering	6
1.2 Motivation and objectives	9
1.3 Structure of the dissertation and main contributions	11
2 Chapter 2 - TemBERTure: advancing protein thermostability prediction with deep learning and attention mechanisms	18
2.1 Introduction	18
2.2 Methods	20
2.2.1 Database creation	20
2.2.2 TemBERTure _{CLS}	21
2.2.3 TemBERTure _{Tm}	22
2.2.4 Training	22
2.2.5 Analysis	23
2.3 Results	23
2.3.1 TemBERTure _{DB}	23
2.3.2 TemBERTure _{CLS}	23
2.3.3 TemBERTure _{Tm}	25
2.3.4 Interpretability	27
2.4 Discussion	29
3 Chapter 3 - Discriminating HIV-1 broadly neutralizing antibodies via CDR-H3 language model embeddings and perplexity	36
3.1 Introduction	36
3.2 Results	37
3.2.1 H3BERTa	38
3.2.2 Classifier	44
3.3 Discussion	47
3.4 Materials and Methods	49
3.4.1 H3BERTa	49
3.4.2 Classifier	50
3.4.3 Analysis	52

4 Chapter 4 - Bridging the Chains: A Deep Learning Framework for Heavy-to-Light Antibody Sequence Translation and B Cell Classification	57
4.1 Introduction	57
4.2 Results	58
4.3 Discussion	67
4.4 Methods	69
4.4.1 Models	69
4.4.2 Data preparation	70
4.4.3 Pre-training datasets for HeavyBERTa and LightGPT	70
4.4.4 Fine-tuning dataset for Heavy2Light	70
4.4.5 Fine-tuning dataset for naive/memory B cell classification	70
4.4.6 Pre-training and fine-tuning	71
4.4.7 Evaluation	72
4.4.8 Pairing compatibility assessment using ImmunoMatch	72
4.4.9 Heavy-light chain V gene coherence	72
4.4.10 Hardware and software	72
5 Conclusions and Future Directions	76
A Supplementary materials for Chapter 2: "TemBERTure: advancing protein thermostability prediction with deep learning and attention mechanisms"	78
A.0.1 Ensemble evaluation for melting temperature prediction	78
B Supplementary materials for Chapter 3: "Discriminating HIV-1 broadly neutralizing antibodies via CDR-H3 language model embeddings and perplexity"	92
C Supplementary materials for Chapter 4: "Bridging the Chains: A Deep Learning Framework for Heavy-to-Light Antibody Sequence Translation and B Cell Classification"	103
Curriculum vitae	115
List of publications	118
Declaration of Originality	119

List of Figures

1.1	Structure and modular organization of an antibody and its antigen-binding site . . .	3
1.2	Schematic representation of the four levels of protein structure	6
2.1	TemBERTure database and model architecture	21
2.2	TemBERTure _{CLS} with state-of-the-art models	24
2.3	TemBERTure database creation and model architecture	26
2.4	Predicted melting temperatures	27
2.5	Frequency of high attention score by amino acid	28
2.6	Representative structural analysis of attention score	29
3.1	Schematic overview of the proposed deep learning framework	38
3.2	AntiBERTa and H3BERTa encode complementary germline–gene features in healthy–donor heavy–chain repertoires	40
3.3	Perplexity landscape of antibody repertoires quantified with H3BERTa	42
3.4	Decision boundary of a linear SVM trained on H3BERTa embeddings projected onto the first two PCA components	46
4.1	Data processing and training strategy	60
4.2	Dimensionality reduction of learned embeddings	61
4.3	Characterization of unconditionally generated light chain sequences	63
4.4	Comparison of conditionally generated light chains with their true paired counterparts reveals distinct pairing patterns and preserved structural integrity across similarity ranges	64
4.5	Characterization of conditionally generated light chain sequences	66
A.1	Effect of fine-tuning on amino acid High Attention Score (HAS) frequency	87
A.2	Amino acid frequency and HAS frequency	87
A.3	Comparison of TemBERTure _{CLS} attention scores on pairs of protein homologs	88
A.4	Mapping of TemBERTure _{CLS} attention score on protein structures	89
A.5	Comparison of TemBERTure _{CLS} attention scores and entropy per residue on protein structures	90
B.1	Comparison of perplexity values	93
B.2	UMAP visualization of H3BERTa-derived embeddings	94
B.3	Latent space representations of CDR-H3 sequences stratified by donor group and J gene usage	95
B.4	Latent space representations of CDR-H3 sequences stratified by donor group and V gene usage	96
B.5	Wasserstein distances analysis	97
B.6	Perplexity distributions of CDR-H3 sequences	98
B.7	CDR-H3 length and amino acid composition across perplexity-defined groups in Healthy and bnAb repertoires	98

B.8	Length distribution of CDR-H3 sequences across perplexity-defined groups	99
B.9	Biochemical properties of CDR-H3 sequences across perplexity-defined groups . . .	100
B.10	Length distribution of CDR-H3 loops in bnAb and nnAb repertoires	101
B.11	Distribution of V gene identity across antibody repertoires with varying neutraliza- tion capacity	102
C.1	Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of learned embeddings	104
C.2	Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) of learned embeddings	105
C.3	Distribution of percent identity across light chain V gene families	108
C.4	V gene family distribution across generated and reference antibody light chain se- quences	108
C.5	Distribution of pairing compatibility scores for Heavy2Light generated sequences .	109
C.6	Distribution of germline identity and region lengths for light chain sequences across dataset splits	110

List of Tables

A.1	Summary of the data-processing pipeline for TemBERTure _{DB}	79
A.2	Summary of the data-processing pipeline for BacDive _{DB}	80
A.3	Summary of the data-processing pipeline for Meltome _{DB}	81
A.4	TemBERTure _{CLS} model hyperparameter tuning for different datasets	82
A.5	TemBERTure _{T_m} hyperparameter tuning	83
A.6	Number of sequences in the TemBERTure _{DB} classifier and regression datasets	83
A.7	Comparison between TemBERTure _{CLS} model and other state-of-the-art models	84
A.8	TemBERTure _{CLS} generalization ability	85
A.9	Ensemble performance on the regression validation set	86
C.1	Dataset composition and data split allocation	103
C.2	Language modeling performance across model configurations	103
C.3	Classification performance	106
C.4	Coherence percentages of V gene usage	106
C.5	Germline similarity	106
C.6	Similarity generated light chain sequences to their corresponding true light sequence	107
C.7	Germline identity and region lengths of light chain sequences	107
C.8	Hyper-parameters and performance of the Encoder–Decoder model	111
C.9	HeavyBERTa model training parameters and performances	112
C.10	LightGPT language-model pre-training hyper-parameters and performance	113
C.11	Training parameters for naive/memory B cell classification models	114

Introduction

1.1 Background and general context

Proteins are among the most essential and versatile macromolecules in all forms of life. The scientific study of proteins began in the early 19th century, with Gerardus Johannes Mulder coining the term "protein" in 1838. It was in the late 19th and early 20th centuries that Emil Fischer, through his groundbreaking work on peptide bonds, identified proteins as polymers of amino acids. Proteins have since been recognized as the molecular workhorses of biology. Present in every living cell, they are responsible for carrying out the vast majority of biological functions: catalyzing metabolic reactions, transmitting signals, enabling cellular motion, ensuring structural integrity, and defending against pathogens. Their ubiquity and functional richness make proteins central not only to the basic understanding of life at the molecular level but also to a wide range of applications in medicine, biotechnology, and synthetic biology.

1.1.1 Foundations of protein biology

Proteins are essential macromolecules composed of amino acids linked by peptide bonds into linear chains called polypeptides. This sequence of amino acids, referred to as the primary structure, is determined by the genetic code and built from a set of twenty standard amino acids. Each amino acid possesses a unique side chain (R group) that confers specific physicochemical properties. The precise arrangement and complementary interactions among these side chains govern the protein's folding pathway and stabilize its native three-dimensional conformation, which is critical for its biological activity.

As the polypeptide chain emerges from the ribosome, it begins to adopt higher-order structures. Segments of the chain often fold into secondary structure motifs, most commonly α -helices and β -sheets, stabilized by regular patterns of hydrogen bonding. These elements then assemble into a protein's tertiary structure, its three-dimensional conformation that determines its biochemical function. In many cases, multiple polypeptide chains (or subunits) interact to form a quaternary structure, resulting in multimeric protein complexes. A classic example is the antibody, which consists of two identical heavy chains and two identical light chains assembled into a Y-shaped tetramer. This quaternary structure is essential for antigen recognition and immune function, as it enables the formation of two antigen-binding sites and the proper orientation of effector domains.

Protein folding is governed by both the intrinsic properties of the amino acid sequence and the surrounding cellular environment. A major driving force is the hydrophobic effect, which causes nonpolar side chains to cluster in the protein's interior, minimizing exposure to the aqueous environment. Folding is further stabilized by a combination of non-covalent interactions, hydrogen bonds, ionic interactions, van der Waals forces, and, in some proteins, covalent disulfide bridges. The resulting native conformation is typically a compact, energetically favorable structure that is

optimized for function. Misfolding, on the other hand, can lead to dysfunction and disease, underscoring the critical importance of proper folding pathways.

The functional repertoire of proteins is remarkably diverse. Proteins can act as enzymes, catalyzing biochemical reactions with exceptional specificity and efficiency; as structural components, forming the cytoskeleton (e.g., actin, tubulin) that maintains cell shape and organization; as transporters, shuttling molecules like oxygen (e.g., hemoglobin) or ions across membranes; as signaling molecules and receptors, mediating inter- and intracellular communication; as molecular motors, driving movement within and between cells; as regulators of gene expression, modulating transcriptional and translational programs; and as components of the immune system, such as antibodies, which recognize and neutralize foreign pathogens with high specificity. In short, proteins are indispensable to nearly every biological process and are central to the maintenance of life.

This immense functional and structural diversity arises from the combinatorial possibilities of amino acid sequences and their context-dependent folding behavior. Even a single point mutation in the primary sequence can have profound effects on a protein's structure and function, leading to altered activity or disease. Therefore, understanding protein biology, spanning primary sequence, folding mechanisms, structural organization, and molecular function, is a cornerstone of molecular and cellular biology, with far-reaching implications in fields such as drug design, synthetic biology, and systems immunology. In particular, the versatility of **antibodies** make them indispensable tools both as natural defenders against pathogens and as engineered therapeutics in cancer, autoimmune diseases, and beyond, and it is on these remarkable molecules that we will focus our attention.

Antibodies

Antibodies, or immunoglobulins (Igs), are highly specialized Y-shaped glycoproteins produced by terminally differentiated B cells (plasma cells) and represent a cornerstone of the adaptive immune response. Their primary function is to recognize and bind with high specificity to antigens, molecular structures associated with pathogens or altered self-cells, enabling their neutralization or elimination. Structurally, each antibody consists of two identical heavy (H) chains and two identical light (L) chains (either K or λ), which assemble into a heterotetrameric complex stabilized by both covalent (disulfide) and non-covalent interactions (Schroeder and Cavacini, 2010; Thermo Fisher Scientific, 2025).

Each chain is divided into variable (V) and constant (C) domains, as shown in Fig. 1.1. The amino-terminal variable domains of the heavy and light chains (VH and VL) pair to form the antigen-binding fragment (Fab), while the carboxy-terminal domains of the heavy chains (CH2 and CH3) dimerize to form the crystallizable fragment (Fc), which interacts with Fc receptors (FcRs) and complement proteins to mediate downstream immune effector functions. A flexible hinge region connects Fab and Fc, enabling conformational adaptability during antigen binding.

The antigen recognition capacity of an antibody is largely determined by the six hypervariable loops, or Complementarity Determining Regions (CDRs), three contributed by each chain (CDR1–3). Among them, CDR-H3, which spans the V–D–J junction of the heavy chain, exhibits the highest degree of sequence and structural variability and plays a dominant role in defining antigen specificity and paratope geometry (Xu and Davis, 2000). The framework regions (FRs), which flank the CDRs, provide a structurally conserved scaffold that ensures correct folding and presentation of the antigen-binding site.

FIGURE 1.1: **Structure and modular organization of an antibody and its antigen-binding site.** Left: Schematic representation of an IgG antibody, highlighting the variable (V) and constant (C) domains of the heavy (H) and light (L) chains. The antigen-binding site is formed by the variable regions of both chains (V_H and V_L), located at the N-termini. Center: Structural zoom-in of the variable domain interface, showing the six complementarity-determining regions (CDRs), three from the heavy chain (CDR-H1, H2, H3) and three from the light chain (CDR-L1, L2, L3), in red, which form the antigen-binding interface. Bottom: Linear representation of the V_H and V_L regions, illustrating the alternating framework regions (FRs) and CDRs that together shape the antibody's specificity and structural scaffold. Image from (Rapid Novor Inc., 2025).

The antibody class, also known as isotype, is defined by the constant region (CH) of the heavy chain, which plays a key role in mediating the antibody's effector functions (Stavnezer et al., 2008). There are five main antibody isotypes in humans – IgA, IgD, IgE, IgG, and IgM – each with distinct roles in the immune response. These isotypes differ in their distribution, structure, and ability to activate immune mechanisms such as complement activation or interaction with Fc receptors.

Antibody diversity arises through multiple molecular processes during B cell development and activation (Tonegawa, 1983). Initially, in the bone marrow, developing B cells generate diversity through a process called V(D)J recombination (ScienceDirect Topics, 2025; Tonegawa, 1983; Dudley et al., 2005). This involves the random selection and joining of Variable (V), Diversity (D, for heavy chains only), and Joining (J) gene segments to form the variable region of the antibody. For light chains, only V and J segments are recombined. This combinatorial process creates a vast number of possible sequences, even before the cell encounters any antigen.

Further diversity is introduced at the junctions where these gene segments are joined. During this step, enzymes can delete a few nucleotides or add extra ones not encoded in the genome, particularly non-templated (N) and palindromic (P) nucleotides, through the activity of enzymes like terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase (TdT). These modifications, especially concentrated in the CDR-H3 region, greatly expand the variability of the antibody repertoire (ScienceDirect Topics, 2025).

Once B cells encounter an antigen, they undergo somatic hypermutation, a process that introduces point mutations in the antibody genes (ScienceDirect Topics, 2025). This allows the immune system to fine-tune antibody affinity, selecting B cells that produce better-binding antibodies in a process known as affinity maturation.

Finally, B cells can switch the antibody class they produce (for example, from IgM to IgG), adapting their function to the needs of the immune response, while maintaining the same antigen specificity (Dudley et al., 2005).

Antibodies protect the body through several key mechanisms. One is direct neutralization, where they bind to viruses or toxins and block them from attaching to or entering host cells. They also mediate opsonization, coating pathogens to make them easier for immune cells like macrophages to recognize and engulf via Fc gamma receptors (Fc γ Rs). Through complement activation, antibodies trigger a cascade of proteins that can destroy pathogens directly or tag them with molecules like C3b to promote phagocytosis. Finally, in antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity (ADCC), NK cells recognize antibody-coated targets via Fc γ RIII (CD16) and kill them by releasing cytotoxic molecules.

Beyond their natural role, antibodies have become indispensable tools in biotechnology and medicine (Suzuki et al., 2015). Monoclonal antibodies (mAbs), identical antibody molecules derived from a single B cell clone, form the basis of numerous approved therapeutics across oncology, autoimmunity, and infectious disease (Ebrahimi and Samanta, 2023; Kumar et al., 2000).

Advancements in high-throughput B cell receptor sequencing (Setliff et al., 2019) (Rep-Seq), structural proteomics (e.g., cryo-EM, X-ray crystallography), and protein language models have enabled detailed characterization of antibody repertoires at the population and individual levels. These tools facilitate the identification of convergent ("public") clonotypes, elucidate immune response dynamics, and inform the rational design of next-generation vaccines and therapeutics. In this context, the antibody molecule is not only a biological effector but also a rich substrate for

computational modeling and machine learning, bridging immunology, bioinformatics, and structural biology.

1.1.2 Protein engineering in biomedicine

Protein engineering is the design, modification, and synthesis of proteins to improve or alter their properties for specific applications. It is a foundational discipline in modern biotechnology, with widespread implications in medicine, industrial catalysis, diagnostics, and synthetic biology. The field emerged in the late 20th century following advances in recombinant DNA technology, which enabled the first systematic manipulations of protein-coding sequences. Since then, protein engineering has evolved into a sophisticated discipline that integrates structural biology, computational modeling, and increasingly, machine learning.

Two main strategies dominate traditional protein engineering: rational design and directed evolution. Rational design (Sellés Vidal et al., 2023) involves modifying protein sequences based on structural or mechanistic knowledge to enhance properties such as stability, affinity, or activity. This approach benefits from atomic-resolution structural data and computational tools that predict the effects of specific mutations. However, it is limited by our incomplete understanding of sequence–structure–function relationships. Directed evolution (Sellés Vidal et al., 2023), by contrast, mimics natural selection in the laboratory: large libraries of protein variants are generated (typically by random mutagenesis or recombination), expressed, and screened for desired traits. While powerful, this method is resource-intensive and constrained by experimental throughput.

In recent years, the emergence of data-driven and AI-based approaches has begun to reshape the landscape of protein engineering (Guo et al., 2023).

For example, Rosetta (Leman et al., 2020; Rosetta Commons, 2025) is a powerful and long-standing software suite at the core of modern computational biology. It supports a wide range of applications, from designing entirely new proteins and enzymes to predicting protein structures and modeling complex biomolecular interactions. Its flexibility and accuracy have made it a key tool in fields like drug discovery, antibody engineering, and vaccine design.

Advances in deep learning have further accelerated this transformation. A key example is AlphaFold (Abramson et al., 2024; Jumper et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2023), which predicts protein structures with remarkable accuracy directly from amino acid sequences, solving a decades-old challenge in structural biology. Though not a design tool itself, AlphaFold has become foundational for protein engineering by making reliable structural models widely accessible.

It is used across a range of tasks: modeling protein structures, analyzing mutation effects, identifying binding sites, and locating functionally relevant regions. By reducing dependence on experimental techniques like X-ray crystallography and NMR, it has sped up the design and development of new proteins and therapeutics (Jumper et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2023).

As seen in AlphaFold, the advent of protein language models (pLMs) offers a new paradigm for understanding and designing proteins. These models, inspired by natural language processing, treat amino acid sequences as linguistic entities and learn contextual representations from large-scale sequence data (Guo et al., 2023; Ofer et al., 2021). This opens the door to computationally guided protein engineering, in which sequence design is informed by learned representations derived from millions of natural proteins.

Several successful tools illustrate the potential of these approaches. ProteinMPNN (Dauparas et al., 2022), for example, generates highly stable sequences for designed backbones. When applied to native backbones, it produces sequences that are predicted to fold into the intended structures with higher confidence than their native counterparts. RFdiffusion (Watson et al., 2023) utilizes diffusion models to generate protein structures de novo or conditioned on constraints such as symmetry or binding interfaces. While Chroma (Ingraham et al., 2023) has integrated generative modeling with geometric reasoning to design novel proteins across diverse folds and functions, illustrating how deep generative models can navigate the vast space of functional proteins.

Together, these tools exemplify how AI is transforming protein engineering, from rational design to generative discovery, enabling the design of proteins with unprecedented speed, diversity, and precision.

FIGURE 1.2: **Schematic representation of the four levels of protein structure, through an analogy with language.** The primary structure corresponds to the linear sequence of amino acids, analogous to letters in an alphabet. The secondary structure involves local conformations such as α -helices and β -sheets stabilized by backbone hydrogen bonds, resembling unordered words. The tertiary structure represents the three-dimensional folding of a single polypeptide chain, comparable to a syntactically correct sentence. The quaternary structure is the assembly of multiple polypeptide subunits into a functional complex, analogous to the formation of a coherent paragraph. This analogy emphasizes how structure at each hierarchical level contributes to the overall function, both in proteins and in language.

1.1.3 Emergence of large language models in protein engineering

The rise of large language models (LLMs) in computational biology has opened new avenues for protein engineering and antibody discovery. LLMs, deep learning models originally developed for natural language processing, have demonstrated a remarkable ability to learn complex patterns and semantics from massive text corpora. Recognizing a powerful analogy between human language and biological sequences, where amino acids act as “letters” forming a protein “sentence”, researchers began applying language modeling techniques to proteins. This gave rise to protein language models (pLMs), which treat amino acid sequences as a form of language and learn from them in an unsupervised fashion.

The four hierarchical levels of protein structure, primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary structure, describe the progressively complex organization of protein architecture. Fig. 1.2 illustrates these structural levels alongside their analogy with human language, providing a visual summary of how proteins are organized from linear amino acid sequences to fully assembled functional complexes. The figure highlights the conceptual parallels between protein folding and the

multi-layered structure of natural language: the primary structure (sequence of amino acids) resembles letters forming words; secondary structures (α -helices and β -sheets) can be compared to grammatical phrases; tertiary structure (the three-dimensional folding of a single polypeptide) parallels sentence-level meaning; and quaternary structure (assembly of multiple polypeptides) reflects discourse-level organization.

This analogy highlights a key motivation behind protein language modeling: just as natural language models learn syntax and semantics from sequences of words, protein language models aim to learn biochemical and structural rules from sequences of amino acids, ultimately enabling the direct extraction of functional insights from sequence data (Ofer et al., 2021).

Crucially, protein sequences encode a rich reservoir of biochemical, structural, and evolutionary information. The linear sequence of amino acids alone contains implicit instructions for folding, stability, interaction, and function. pLMs leverage this latent information by learning to represent sequences as dense numerical embeddings that reflect their underlying biophysical properties. Unlike traditional sequence analysis methods, which often rely on explicit alignments or hand-crafted features, these models capture subtle and context-dependent signals directly from raw sequence data, revealing relationships that might otherwise remain hidden.

Early efforts using recurrent neural networks hinted at the promise of this approach (Alley et al., 2019), but the advent of transformer-based architectures rapidly accelerated progress. In recent years, LLMs trained on evolutionary-scale protein databases, such as ESM-1b (Rives et al., 2021), UniRep (Alley et al., 2019), AlphaFold (Jumper et al., 2021), and MSA Transformer (Rao et al., 2021), have achieved notable breakthroughs. These models can distill information from millions of sequences into learned representations that encode features such as secondary structure, tertiary contacts, and evolutionary conservation, even without explicit structural supervision. In effect, they make the information encoded in the sequence computationally accessible.

This capability has far-reaching implications: it means that a model trained solely on unlabelled protein sequences can infer functional and structural characteristics, predict the effects of mutations, and guide rational protein design. As a result, pLMs have quickly become powerful tools in computational biology, enabling tasks such as protein function prediction, mutation effect analysis, and de novo protein design. Notably, generative protein language models can even invent new protein sequences: by sampling from the learned “language” of proteins, they can propose novel variants or entirely synthetic proteins with desired characteristics (Ferruz et al., 2022). Such innovations are poised to accelerate protein engineering by reducing the need for exhaustive trial-and-error in the wet lab.

Transformer-based language models

First introduced by Vaswani et al., 2017 in the paper “Attention Is All You Need”, transformers are deep learning architectures designed to process sequential data. Since their introduction, transformer-based models have become a cornerstone of modern neural network design in natural language processing and has been increasingly adopted across a wide range of domains, including computer vision, speech processing, and computational biology.

Unlike earlier models that relied on recurrence or convolution, this kind of architecture uses self-attention mechanisms to capture dependencies between elements in a sequence. This enables it to model both local and global context without being constrained by the sequential order of the input. The original architecture is composed of two main components: an encoder block and a decoder block. Self-attention operates within each block to learn contextual relationships, while

an additional attention mechanism connects the encoder and decoder, enabling the decoder to attend to the encoder's outputs.

At the core of the transformer architecture there is the scaled dot-product self-attention mechanism. This mechanism operates on three learned projections of the input embeddings: queries (Q), keys (K), and values (V). Each of them is derived from the input matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$, where n is the sequence length and d the embedding dimension. Attention weights are computed as:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (1.1)$$

where d_k is the dimensionality of the keys. This operation allows each token to attend to all other tokens in the sequence, with the softmax ensuring that attention weights form a valid probability distribution. Multi-head attention extends this idea by learning multiple sets of projections in parallel, enabling the model to attend to different subspaces of the representation simultaneously.

In practice, it is built as a stack of identical layers. Each layer consists of a multi-head self-attention sublayer followed by a position-wise fully connected feed-forward network. To promote stable gradient flow and faster convergence, each sublayer is wrapped in residual connections and followed by layer normalization. Unlike RNNs, which process sequences step by step, Transformers operate on entire sequences in parallel, significantly improving training efficiency, especially on large datasets and in high-performance computing settings.

Because self-attention itself is permutation-invariant, positional information is injected into the model through positional encodings added to the input embeddings. These encodings can be fixed (e.g., sinusoidal functions) or learned during training. Depending on the task, the final encoder representations can be used directly (such as in BERT-style models) or passed to a decoder module, as in encoder-decoder architectures like T5 or BART.

Training transformer-based models typically begins with a self-supervised pretraining phase, in which the model learns contextual representations from large unlabeled datasets. In masked language modeling (MLM), a subset of input tokens is randomly masked, and the model is trained to reconstruct them using bidirectional context. Alternatively, autoregressive models like GPT employ a causal language modeling (CLM) objective, predicting the next token in a unidirectional manner. Optimization is usually performed using the Adam or AdamW optimizer, often with learning rate scheduling strategies such as warm-up followed by linear decay to ensure stable convergence.

Once pretrained, transformer models can be fine-tuned on a variety of downstream tasks like classification, sequence generation, and span prediction. In addition, this transfer learning paradigm has enabled Transformers-based models to achieve state-of-the-art results not only in NLP but also in fields such as computational biology, cheminformatics, and protein engineering, underscoring the flexibility and expressive power of attention-based architectures.

Protein language models

Several landmark protein language models illustrate the rapid progress in the protein engineering field. For example, models such as ESM-1b (Rives et al., 2021), UniRep (Alley et al., 2019), ProGen2 (Nijkamp et al., 2022) and MSA Transformer (Rao et al., 2021) have demonstrated the ability to capture evolutionary and structural constraints implicitly by training on large-scale protein sequence datasets. These models have been successfully applied to diverse tasks, including mutation effect prediction (Meier et al., 2021), functional annotation (Bepler and Berger, 2019),

and de novo protein generation, reducing the need for extensive experimental screening.

The ESM (Evolutionary Scale Modeling) family was developed by Meta AI. ESM-1b (Rives et al., 2021), with 650 million parameters, was trained on UniRef50 and set a new benchmark in secondary structure and contact prediction. Its successor, ESM-2 (Lin et al., 2023), scaled up to 15 billion parameters, demonstrates direct inference of full atomic-level protein structure from primary sequence, culminating in ESMFold (Lin et al., 2023), a powerful tool for in silico structure modeling, complementary to AlphaFold (Jumper et al., 2021).

Another influential model is ProtBERT (Elnaggar et al., 2022), part of the ProtTrans project, trained on hundreds of millions of protein sequences from UniRef100 and BFD. With ~420 million parameters, ProtBERT has been effectively utilized in various downstream tasks through fine-tuning.

Antibody language models

Importantly, the LLM paradigm has also been extended to the antibody domain, where extreme sequence variability and immune-specific mechanisms demand specialized modeling. Antibodies rely on hypervariable regions, particularly the CDR-H3 loop, for antigen binding. To capture the language of immune repertoires, models like AntiBERTa (Choi, 2022) were developed. AntiBERTa is a transformer-based model trained on vast B-cell receptor datasets, learning patterns shaped by recombination, somatic hypermutation, and clonal selection. Its embeddings have been shown to reflect key functional features, such as germline origin, mutation load, and even contact residues within folded antibodies (Leem et al., 2022).

Such models have enabled new capabilities in computational antibody discovery: in-silico screening of antibody libraries, prediction of paratope regions, and support for affinity maturation and humanization. Following AntiBERTa, other antibody-focused models, such as AbLang (Olsen et al., 2022), IgLM (Shuai et al., 2023), have further pushed this frontier.

In summary, large protein language models have transformed both general protein engineering and the specialized field of antibody discovery. By learning from natural sequence diversity, these models capture structure–function relationships that can be leveraged to design antibodies with tailored properties. General-purpose LLMs like ESM and ProtBERT offer foundational capabilities, while antibody-specific models unlock in-depth insights into immune repertoires. These advances lay the groundwork for this dissertation, which builds upon these approaches to explore new strategies for designing functional proteins and therapeutic antibodies.

1.2 Motivation and objectives

Protein engineering and antibody discovery play a central role in the development of next-generation therapeutics. Proteins are the workhorses of biology, carrying out catalysis, signaling, structural support, and immune defense (Ebrahimi and Samanta, 2023). By engineering therapeutic proteins, including monoclonal antibodies (identical immunoglobulins produced by a single clone of B cells, each binding the same specific epitope on an antigen), researchers can harness this intrinsic versatility to design drugs that perform highly specific and complex biological tasks, often beyond the reach of traditional small molecules. Engineered antibodies, for example, can specifically target cancer cells or neutralize pathogens while sparing healthy tissue, reducing side effects, and improving treatment outcomes (Justiz-Vaillant et al., 2025; Aggarwal et al., 2023). Indeed, monoclonal antibodies now constitute a large share of new drug approvals, by some estimates, around 70% of biologics approved by the FDA, and roughly one-fifth of all new drugs are mAb-based

(Torre and Albericio, 2024). This trend is propelled by the success of antibody therapeutics like trastuzumab and pembrolizumab (Sava, 2025), which have become standard of care in oncology, as well as by advances in antibody humanization and affinity maturation techniques. At the same time, other classes of protein therapeutics (Aggarwal et al., 2023), such as insulin analogues (Hirsch, 2005), recombinant enzymes, and cytokines, have transformed the treatment landscape for diseases like diabetes, lysosomal storage disorders, and autoimmune conditions.

The ability to design and optimize antibodies provides a powerful means of responding to emerging health threats, including rapidly mutating viruses and resistant cancer phenotypes. Tailored interventions can range from enhancing an enzyme’s stability to function as a long-lasting drug to re-engineering an antibody’s binding sites for improved efficacy against viral variants. In particular, modifying the complementarity-determining regions (CDRs) of antibodies can significantly increase binding affinity to specific antigens or enable cross-reactivity across multiple viral strains (Ebrahimi and Samanta, 2023).

As personalized and precision medicine advance, combining computational tools, high-throughput screening, and protein language models will help speed up therapeutic discovery. Protein engineering and antibody development continue to play key roles in creating safer, more effective, and tailored treatments.

This dissertation contributes to this evolving landscape by leveraging LLMs to address key challenges in protein engineering and antibody discovery. A unifying theme throughout the work is the use of protein language models, augmented through task-specific training, to extract functional insights directly from protein sequence data.

Chapter 2 of the dissertation focuses on **protein thermostability**, a property closely linked to protein folding, solubility, and therapeutic viability. Among the many properties targeted in protein engineering, thermostability plays a crucial role, especially for therapeutic and industrial applications. Proteins with enhanced thermostability are generally more resistant to denaturation, aggregation, and proteolytic degradation, traits that can significantly improve their shelf-life, bioavailability, and performance under challenging conditions. Rational design strategies often involve introducing stabilizing mutations informed by structural models or computational predictors of thermodynamic stability, such as FoldX (Schymkowitz et al., 2005) and Rosetta ΔG (Kellogg et al., 2011), while AI-based approaches (Ahmed et al., 2022; Charoenkwan et al., 2022; Rodella et al., 2024) can learn patterns associated with thermostability directly from sequence data. This dissertation highlights how studying thermal stability as an explicit objective in machine learning-guided workflows has the potential to generate robust protein variants that maintain function across diverse physiological or environmental conditions. We fine-tune a general-purpose protein language model to create TemBerture, a task-specific predictor of thermostability from full-length protein sequences. This approach demonstrates how transfer learning can adapt large-scale, general representations to practical biophysical prediction tasks.

Protein engineering has found particular success also in the development of therapeutic proteins, including enzymes, cytokines, and monoclonal antibodies (Ebrahimi and Samanta, 2023; Kumar et al., 2000). Engineering efforts may focus on improving pharmacokinetics, reducing immunogenicity, or enhancing specificity and potency. Antibodies, in particular, have become central targets due to their modular structure and therapeutic versatility. Modifications to the complementarity-determining regions (CDRs), especially CDR-H3, can profoundly affect antigen binding, making this region a frequent focus of engineering efforts. Chapter 3 of this dissertation explores how deep learning and protein language models (Choi, 2022; Olsen et al., 2022; Mason et al., 2021) can be applied to antibody sequences to enable data-driven discovery of functional antibodies,

including those with broad neutralizing capacity against highly variable pathogens such as HIV-1. Within this context, we focus on the targeted identification of **broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAbs) against HIV-1** by narrowing the input space to the **CDR-H3 loop**. Our results demonstrate that focusing exclusively on CDR-H3 sequences is sufficient to recapitulate repertoire-level distinctions, highlighting the power of region-focused models in repertoire analysis where interpretability and sequence resolution are very important. This approach underscores how protein language models can be harnessed for antibody discovery tasks.

Chapter 4 addresses a complementary challenge: the design and modeling of paired antibody chains, a critical step in both antibody repertoire reconstruction and therapeutic antibody engineering. In this setting, we train a **sequence-to-sequence model** from scratch on **paired heavy-light chain** data, enabling the conditional generation of plausible light chains given a heavy chain. This framework leverages the **full sequence** information of both heavy and light chains and showcases how generative models can drive antibody design. It also provides tools for analyzing gene usage, maturation pathways, and chain pairing, offering a robust approach to dissect antibody diversity and inform the development of therapeutic antibodies.

Together, these projects highlight how protein language models can be customized and applied across scales, from global sequence-function relationships to fine-grained immune repertoire analysis, with applications spanning prediction, design, and therapeutic discovery.

1.3 Structure of the dissertation and main contributions

This dissertation is organized into five chapters, following a progression from general background to increasingly specialized applications of protein language models in protein engineering and therapeutic development.

Chapter 1 – Introduction

Provides background on protein biology, protein engineering, antibody discovery and development, and the emergence of large language models in the biomedicine field. It outlines the motivation and objectives of the dissertation and presents its structure and main contributions.

Chapter 2 – TemBERTure: advancing Protein Thermostability prediction with Deep Learning and Attention Mechanisms

This chapter presents TemBERTure, a deep learning model fine-tuned from a pretrained protein language model to predict both the thermostability class and melting temperature of proteins directly from their amino acid sequences. By training on a diverse set of sequences spanning multiple organisms, TemBERTure achieves improved robustness and generalization compared to traditional approaches.

A distinguishing feature of the model is its use of attention mechanisms, which not only enhance predictive performance but also provide interpretability. Analysis of attention scores in relation to known 3D protein structures reveals meaningful patterns, such as the enrichment of specific amino acid residues and correlations with secondary structure elements, offering insights into the determinants of protein stability.

TemBERTure addresses several limitations of existing thermostability predictors, particularly regarding scalability, interpretability, and generalization. The model's design, which includes the use of adapters, enables fine-tuning without modifying the entire pretrained model, making it more efficient and easier to deploy in practice. Overall, this work illustrates the potential of transfer learning and attention-based models to advance protein developability and guide protein engineering efforts.

Chapter 3 – Discriminating HIV-1 broadly neutralizing antibodies via CDR-H3 language model embeddings and perplexity

This work introduces H3BERTa, a transformer-based language model pretrained on CDR-H3 sequences, designed to capture the complex antibody repertoire signals. By leveraging the expressive power of self-attention mechanisms, H3BERTa learns contextual representations that reflect not only germline-encoded features, but also more subtle biophysical and evolutionary signals associated with affinity maturation and immune history. These properties make it a valuable tool for the in-depth characterization of immune repertoires across different physiological and pathological conditions.

To showcase the utility of these embeddings in a real-world application, we developed an adversarial classifier trained on H3BERTa-derived representations to identify HIV-1 broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAbs) from immune repertoire data. Focusing on the CDR-H3 region, a key determinant of antigen specificity and binding affinity, the classifier successfully discriminates bnAbs across different affinity classes, highlighting the ability of pretrained language models to extract functionally relevant patterns from sequence data alone.

Together, H3BERTa and the bnabs classifier provide the grounds for a powerful framework for accelerating bnAb discovery by reducing reliance on costly experimental screens and enabling the rapid prioritization of candidate sequences. More broadly, these models demonstrate how language modeling can be harnessed to extract biologically meaningful information from large-scale B cell receptor (BCR) datasets.

Chapter 4 – Bridging the Chains: A Deep Learning Framework for Heavy-to-Light Antibody Sequence Translation and B Cell Classification

This chapter introduces a deep learning framework based on transformer models for modeling antibody heavy–light chain pairing. By pretraining two transformer-based models on large-scale unpaired sequences and fine-tuning them on paired antibody datasets, the model enables the conditional generation of light chains given a heavy chain. This two-stage approach enables the reconstruction of antibody repertoires and supports the rational design of complete antibody candidates.

The framework captures biologically meaningful patterns from sequence data alone, such as B cell developmental states and V gene usage. The generative model (Heavy2Light) produces light chains with sequence identity similar to native pairs, with nearly half exceeding a threshold for plausible pairing. Conditioning on the heavy chain improves germline similarity, structural completeness, and foldability of the generated sequences.

These findings highlight the potential of language models not only to interpret antibody repertoires but to generate biologically grounded sequences, paving the way for data-driven antibody engineering.

Chapter 5 – Conclusions and Future Directions

This chapter summarizes the main findings, highlights the limitations of the current work, and outlines potential directions for future research, including enhancing interpretability, incorporating structural information, and expanding the application of antibody-specific language models to immunotherapy and vaccine development.

References

- Abramson, J., J. Jumper, S. Jain, et al. (2024). "Accurate Structure Prediction of Biomolecular Interactions with AlphaFold 3". In: *Nature* 630.8016, pp. 493–500. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-024-07487-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07487-w).
- Aggarwal, D. et al. (2023). "Antibody-Drug Conjugates: The Paradigm Shifts in the Targeted Cancer Therapy". In: *Frontiers in Immunology* 14, p. 1203073. DOI: [10.3389/fimmu.2023.1203073](https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2023.1203073).
- Ahmed, Z., H. Zulfiqar, and A. A. Khan (2022). "iThermo: a sequence-based model for identifying thermophilic proteins using a multi-feature fusion strategy". In: *Frontiers in Microbiology* 13, p. 790063. DOI: [10.3389/fmicb.2022.790063](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.790063).
- Alley, E. C. et al. (2019). "Unified Rational Protein Engineering with Sequence-Based Deep Representation Learning". In: *Nature Methods* 16.12, pp. 1315–1322. DOI: [10.1038/s41592-019-0598-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0598-1).
- Bepler, T. and B. Berger (2019). "Learning Protein Sequence Embeddings Using Information from Structure". In: *International Conference on Learning Representations*. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.1902.08661](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1902.08661). eprint: [1902.08661](https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.08661).
- Charoenkwan, P., N. Schaduangrat, and M. A.-U.-A. Moni (2022). "SAPPHIRE: a stacking-based ensemble learning framework for accurate prediction of thermophilic proteins". In: *Computers in Biology and Medicine* 146, p. 105704. DOI: [10.1016/j.combiomed.2022.105704](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2022.105704).
- Choi, Y. (2022). "Artificial Intelligence for Antibody Reading Comprehension: AntiBERTa". In: *Patterns* 3.7, p. 100535. DOI: [10.1016/j.patter.2022.100535](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2022.100535).
- Dauparas, J., I. Anishchenko, N. Bennett, et al. (2022). "Robust Deep Learning–Based Protein Sequence Design Using ProteinMPNN". In: *Science* 378.6615, pp. 49–56. DOI: [10.1126/science.add2187](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.add2187).
- Dudley, D. D. et al. (2005). "Mechanism and Control of V(D)J Recombination versus Class Switch Recombination: Similarities and Differences". In: *Advances in Immunology*. Ed. by F. W. Alt. Vol. 86. Elsevier, pp. 43–112. DOI: [10.1016/S0065-2776\(04\)86002-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2776(04)86002-4).
- Ebrahimi, S. B. and D. Samanta (2023). "Engineering Protein-Based Therapeutics through Structural and Chemical Design". In: *Nature Communications* 14.1, p. 2411. DOI: [10.1038/s41467-023-38039-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-38039-x).
- Elnaggar, A., M. Heinzinger, and C. Dallago (2022). "ProtTrans: toward understanding the language of life through self-supervised learning". In: *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 44, pp. 7112–7127. DOI: [10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3095381](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3095381).
- Ferruz, N., S. Schmidt, and B. Höcker (2022). "ProtGPT2 Is a Deep Unsupervised Language Model for Protein Design". In: *Nature Communications* 13.1, p. 4348. DOI: [10.1038/s41467-022-32007-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-32007-7).
- Guo, Z. et al. (2023). "Diffusion Models in Bioinformatics and Computational Biology". In: *Nature Reviews Bioengineering* 2.2, pp. 136–154. DOI: [10.1038/s44222-023-00114-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s44222-023-00114-9).

- Hirsch, I. B. (2005). "Insulin Analogues". In: *The New England Journal of Medicine* 352.2, pp. 174–183. DOI: [10.1056/NEJMr040832](https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMr040832).
- Ingraham, J. B., M. A. Hassan, A. Lee, et al. (2023). "Illuminating Protein Space with a Programmable Generative Model". In: *Nature* 623.7989, pp. 1070–1078. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-023-06728-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06728-8).
- Jumper, J., R. Evans, A. Pritzel, et al. (2021). "Highly Accurate Protein Structure Prediction with AlphaFold". In: *Nature* 596.7873, pp. 583–589. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-021-03819-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03819-2).
- Justiz-Vaillant, A. et al. (2025). "A Comprehensive Review about the Use of Monoclonal Antibodies in Cancer Therapy". In: *Antibodies* 14.2, p. 35. DOI: [10.3390/antib14020035](https://doi.org/10.3390/antib14020035).
- Kellogg, E. H., A. Leaver-Fay, and D. Baker (2011). "Role of Conformational Sampling in Computing Mutation-Induced Changes in Protein Structure and Stability". In: *Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics* 79.3, pp. 830–838. DOI: [10.1002/prot.22921](https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.22921).
- Kumar, S., C.-J. Tsai, and R. Nussinov (2000). "Factors enhancing protein thermostability". In: *Protein Engineering* 13, pp. 179–191. DOI: [10.1093/protein/13.3.179](https://doi.org/10.1093/protein/13.3.179).
- Leem, J. et al. (2022). "Deciphering the Language of Antibodies Using Self-Supervised Learning". In: *Patterns* 3.7, p. 100513. DOI: [10.1016/j.patter.2022.100513](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2022.100513).
- Leman, J. K. et al. (2020). "Macromolecular Modeling and Design in Rosetta: Recent Methods and Frameworks". In: *Nature Methods* 17.7, pp. 665–680. DOI: [10.1038/s41592-020-0848-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-020-0848-2).
- Lin, Z. et al. (2023). "Evolutionary-Scale Prediction of Atomic-Level Protein Structure with a Language Model". In: *Science* 379.6637, pp. 1123–1130. DOI: [10.1126/science.ade2574](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.ade2574).
- Mason, D. M. et al. (2021). "Optimization of Therapeutic Antibodies by Predicting Antigen Specificity from Antibody Sequence via Deep Learning". In: *Nature Biomedical Engineering* 5.6, pp. 600–612. DOI: [10.1038/s41551-021-00699-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-021-00699-9).
- Meier, J. et al. (2021). "Language Models Enable Zero-Shot Prediction of the Effects of Mutations on Protein Function". In: *bioRxiv*, p. 2021.07.09.450648. DOI: [10.1101/2021.07.09.450648](https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.09.450648).
- Nijkamp, E. et al. (2022). "ProGen2: Exploring the Boundaries of Protein Language Models". In: *arXiv*. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2206.13517](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2206.13517). eprint: [2206.13517](https://arxiv.org/abs/2206.13517).
- Ofer, D., N. Brandes, and M. Linial (2021). "The Language of Proteins: NLP, Machine Learning & Protein Sequences". In: *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal* 19, pp. 1750–1758. DOI: [10.1016/j.csbj.2021.03.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2021.03.022).
- Olsen, T. H., I. H. Moal, and C. M. Deane (2022). "AbLang: An Antibody Language Model for Completing Antibody Sequences". In: *Bioinformatics Advances* 2.1, vbac046. DOI: [10.1093/bioadv/vbac046](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioadv/vbac046).
- Rao, R. et al. (2021). "MSA Transformer". In: *bioRxiv*, p. 2021.02.12.430858. DOI: [10.1101/2021.02.12.430858](https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.02.12.430858).
- Rapid Novor Inc. (2025). *Structure and Function of Antibodies*. Corporate white paper. URL: <https://www.rapidnovor.com/structure-and-function-of-antibodies/>.

- Rives, A., J. Meier, T. Sercu, et al. (2021). “Biological Structure and Function Emerge from Scaling Unsupervised Learning to 250 Million Protein Sequences”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 118.15, e2016239118. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.2016239118](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2016239118).
- Rodella, C., S. Lazaridi, and T. Lemmin (2024). “TemBERTure: Advancing Protein Thermostability Prediction with Deep Learning and Attention Mechanisms”. In: *Bioinformatics Advances* 4.1, vbae103. DOI: [10.1093/bioadv/vbae103](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioadv/vbae103).
- Rosetta Commons (2025). *The Hub for Rosetta Modeling Software*. Project web portal. URL: <https://rosettacommons.org/>.
- Sava, J. (2025). *FDA Grants Standard Approval to Pembrolizumab Plus Trastuzumab/Chemo for HER2+, PD-L1+ Gastric Cancer*. Targeted Oncology news article. URL: <https://www.targetedonc.com/view/fda-grants-standard-approval-to-pembrolizumab-plus-trastuzumab-chemo-for-her2-pd-l1-gastric-cancer>.
- Schroeder, H. W. J. and L. Cavacini (2010). “Structure and Function of Immunoglobulins”. In: *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 125.2 Suppl 2, S41–S52. DOI: [10.1016/j.jaci.2009.09.046](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2009.09.046).
- Schymkowitz, J. et al. (2005). “The FoldX Web Server: An Online Force Field”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 33.suppl 2, W382–W388. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gki387](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gki387).
- ScienceDirect Topics (2025). *Junctional Diversity*. Topical overview. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/immunology-and-microbiology/junctional-diversity#chapters-articles>.
- Sellés Vidal, L. et al. (2023). “A Primer to Directed Evolution: Current Methodologies and Future Directions”. In: *RSC Chemical Biology* 4.4, pp. 271–291. DOI: [10.1039/D2CB00231K](https://doi.org/10.1039/D2CB00231K).
- Setliff, I. et al. (2019). “High-Throughput Mapping of B Cell Receptor Sequences to Antigen Specificity”. In: *Cell* 179.7, pp. 1636–1646. DOI: [10.1016/j.cell.2019.11.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2019.11.003).
- Shuai, R. W., J. A. Ruffolo, and J. J. Gray (2023). “IgLM: Infilling Language Modeling for Antibody Sequence Design”. In: *Cell Systems* 14.11, 979–989.e4. DOI: [10.1016/j.cels.2023.10.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cels.2023.10.001).
- Stavnezer, J., J. E. J. Guikema, and C. E. Schrader (2008). “Mechanism and Regulation of Class Switch Recombination”. In: *Annual Review of Immunology* 26, pp. 261–292. DOI: [10.1146/annurev.immunol.26.021607.090248](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.immunol.26.021607.090248).
- Suzuki, M., C. Kato, and A. Kato (2015). “Therapeutic Antibodies: Their Mechanisms of Action and the Pathological Findings They Induce in Toxicity Studies”. In: *Journal of Toxicologic Pathology* 28.3, pp. 133–139. DOI: [10.1293/tox.2015-0031](https://doi.org/10.1293/tox.2015-0031).
- Thermo Fisher Scientific (2025). *Antibody Structure and Classification—Note 7.1*. Technical note. URL: <https://www.thermofisher.com/it/en/home/references/molecular-probes-the-handbook/technical-notes-and-product-highlights/antibody-structure-and-classification.html>.
- Tonegawa, S. (1983). “Somatic Generation of Antibody Diversity”. In: *Nature* 302.5909, pp. 575–581. DOI: [10.1038/302575a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/302575a0).

- Torre, B. G. de la and F. Albericio (2024). "The Pharmaceutical Industry in 2023: An Analysis of FDA Drug Approvals from the Perspective of Molecules". In: *Molecules* 29.3, p. 585. DOI: [10.3390/molecules29030585](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules29030585).
- Vaswani, A., N. Shazeer, and N. Parmar (2017). "Attention is All You Need". In: *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*. Red Hook, NY, USA: Curran Associates Inc., pp. 6000–6010.
- Watson, J. L., D. Juergens, N. Bennett, et al. (2023). "De Novo Design of Protein Structure and Function with RFDiffusion". In: *Nature* 620.7976, pp. 1089–1100. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-023-06415-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06415-8).
- Xu, J. and M. M. Davis (2000). "Diversity in the CDR3 Region of VH Is Sufficient for Most Antibody Specificities". In: *Immunity* 13.1, pp. 37–45. DOI: [10.1016/S1074-7613\(00\)00006-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1074-7613(00)00006-6).
- Yang, Z. et al. (2023). "AlphaFold2 and Its Applications in the Fields of Biology and Medicine". In: *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy* 8.1, p. 115. DOI: [10.1038/s41392-023-01381-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-023-01381-z).

Chapter 2 - TemBERTure: advancing protein thermostability prediction with deep learning and attention mechanisms

This chapter was published as:

Rodella, C., Lazaridi, S., & Lemmin, T. (2024). TemBERTure: advancing protein thermostability prediction with deep learning and attention mechanisms. *Bioinformatics Advances*, 4(1), vbae103. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioadv/vbae103>

Authors contribution: As the main author, I was responsible for study design; model development and training; drafting the manuscript; critical revision; and final approval of the manuscript. Symela Lazaridi was responsible for study design; data acquisition and analysis; drafting the manuscript; critical revision; and final approval of the manuscript. Thomas Lemmin contributed to conceptualization; study design; drafting the manuscript; critical revision; and final approval of the manuscript.

2.1 Introduction

Biocatalysts have become integral to numerous industrial processes, driving e.g. advances in pharmaceutical, food, and biofuel productions (Himmel et al., 2007; Singh et al., 2016; Kuddus, 2018). In these applications, protein thermostability plays a crucial role (Adams and Kelly, 1995; Bommarius et al., 2006). Proteins that can endure high temperatures are essential for accelerating and enhancing chemical reactions, leading to reduced production costs (Singh et al., 2016). However, exposure to elevated temperatures can cause denaturation and loss of biological activity (Matsuura et al., 2015), underscoring the importance of improving our understanding of protein thermostability.

Despite notable progress in experimental techniques for measuring protein thermostability, the process remains time-consuming and challenging to scale up, resulting in limited data on protein thermostability (Stourac et al., 2021). Currently, ProTherm_{DB} is the largest dataset of experimental thermodynamic data for protein stability (Nikam et al., 2021), encompassing a comprehensive collection of 32000 proteins, of which 38% are wild-type sequences and 51% single point mutations. Recently, novel experimental techniques have emerged that allow for the determination of the thermal stability of proteins across the entire genome of a cell. These techniques involve the integration of mass spectrometry with limited proteolysis (Leuenberger et al., 2017), or liquid chromatography (Jarzab et al., 2020). In addition to experimental techniques, the growth temperature of organisms is commonly employed as a proxy for protein thermostability (Ahmed, Zulfqar, and Khan, 2022; Chakravarty and Varadarajan, 2002; Lin and Chen, 2011; Modarres et al., 2018;

Vieille and Zeikus, 2001).

Protein thermostability is a complex interplay between a protein's intrinsic properties, encoded in its amino acid sequence and structure, and extrinsic factors such as pH, solvent conditions, and the presence of stabilizing agents. Extrinsic factors can be important in vivo. However, large datasets of in vivo thermostability data along with the metadata are still currently lacking, thus making in vivo thermostability modeling difficult. On the other hand, understanding and predicting the inherent stability encoded in a protein's sequence and structure is crucial, in particular, for biotechnological applications. By optimizing intrinsic thermostability, proteins become less reliant on specific external conditions, increasing their versatility and applicability in diverse biotechnological settings.

Statistical comparisons of thermophilic and non-thermophilic protein sequences have identified key features associated with thermostability, including higher proportions of hydrophobic and charged residues and specific dipeptide motifs of thermophilic proteins (Fukuchi and Nishikawa, 2001; Vieille and Zeikus, 2001; Y. Ding et al., 2004; Liang et al., 2005; Zhou et al., 2008). A higher occurrence of hydrogen bonds, salt bridges, disulfide bonds, and hydrophobic interactions is also observed in thermophilic proteins (Haney et al., 1997; Sadeghi et al., 2006; Bleicher et al., 2011; Bashirova et al., 2019).

Extensive research has led to the development of several machine learning models aimed at predicting protein thermostability, treating it as a classification task (Gromiha and Suresh, 2007; Zhang and Fang, 2006; Zhang and Fang, 2007; Wu et al., 2009; Lin and Chen, 2011; Nakariyakul et al., 2012; H. Tang et al., 2017; Charoenkwan, Chotpatiwetchkul, et al., 2021; Charoenkwan, Schaduengrat, et al., 2022). Early models such as Thermopred employed a support vector machines (SVM) classifier trained on a dataset of 793 non-thermophilic and 915 thermophilic protein sequences (Lin and Chen, 2011), which became a foundation for training subsequent models (Nakariyakul et al., 2012; H. Tang et al., 2017). An expanded version of this dataset, consisting of 1368 thermophilic and 1443 non-thermophilic proteins, was utilized for training the iThermo model, a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) (Ahmed, Zulfiqar, and Khan, 2022) and the Sapphire framework, a staking-based ensemble model (Charoenkwan, Schaduengrat, et al., 2022). Other models have approached the problem as a regression task to directly predict the melting temperature (Yang, X. Ding, et al., 2019; Yang, Zhao, et al., 2022).

Transformer-based models such as bidirectional encoder representations from transformers (BERT) (Devlin et al., 2019), have improved natural language processing (NLP). By considering proteins as a string of amino acids, NLP can be applied to biology and more specifically to protein modeling and classification. ProtTrans (Elnaggar et al., 2022) a family of models including protBERT, leverages transformers to extract protein characteristics from sequence data. BertThermo (Pei et al., 2023) uses the protBERT embeddings with classical machine learning models for thermophilicity classification, whereas DeepSTABp incorporates ProtTrans-XL embeddings and growth temperature to predict protein melting temperature (Jung et al., 2023). Similarly, TemStaPro (Pudžiuvėlytė et al., 2024) is an ensemble of models incorporating ProtT5-XL (Elnaggar et al., 2022) embeddings to feed-forward densely connected neural network models, and ProLaTherm (Haselbeck et al., 2023) integrates the encoder part of a T5-3B (Raffel et al., 2020) model with ProtT5-XL (Elnaggar et al., 2022) as the feature extractor.

To overcome the shortcomings of present model approaches, we developed TemBERTure, a deep learning package for protein thermostability prediction. It consists of three components: (i) TemBERTure_{DB}, a large-curated database of thermophilic and non-thermophilic sequences, (ii) TemBERTure_{CLS}, a classifier, and (iii) TemBERTure_{T_m}, a regression model, which predicts, respectively, the thermal

class (non-thermophilic or thermophilic) and melting temperature of a protein, based on its primary sequence. Both models are built upon the existing protBERT-BFD language model (Elnaggar et al., 2022) and fine-tuned through an adapter-based approach (Houlsby et al., 2019; Poth et al., 2023). Our findings demonstrate the remarkable capability of deep learning to differentiate protein classes based on their sequences. However, they also highlight its limitations due to the current lack of available data. Despite these limitations, the insights gained from the attention scores within these models offer promising clues to unraveling the underlying mechanisms of protein thermostability and thus can suggest new research directions in biotechnology and protein engineering.

2.2 Methods

This section is composed of four main parts. Part 1 outlines the workflow for establishing comprehensive curated databases of thermophilic and non-thermophilic protein sequences sourced from various experiments and data collection, with TemBERTure_{DB} as the primary training resource and two additional databases used for bias and generalization assessment. Parts 2 and 3 describe the architecture and training of TemBERTure_{CLS} and TemBERTure_{T_m}, respectively. And finally, Part 4 provides the technical details used for the analyses.

2.2.1 Database creation

TemBERTure_{DB} TemBERTure_{DB} leveraged data from the Meltome Atlas experiment (Jarzab et al., 2020). We obtained pre-processed protein sequences from the ProtStab2 dataset (Yang, Zhao, et al., 2022). These sequences were supplemented by retrieving all sequences from UniProtKB (Consortium, 2023) corresponding to the same 13 organisms as in the Meltome Atlas. To address the class imbalance between thermophilic and non-thermophilic sequences, we enriched the thermophilic dataset by sourcing additional data from the BacDive database (Reimer et al., 2022). Here, we classified sequences based on the growth temperature of their respective organisms: thermophilic (>60° C) and non-thermophilic (<30°C). Protein sequences were retrieved for each organism from the NCBI database (Sayers et al., 2022). Ambiguous and short (< 30 amino acids) sequences were excluded. MMseqs (Hauser et al., 2016) was then employed to cluster the sequences within each dataset, using a threshold of 50% for thermophilic and 80% for non-thermophilic. To further address the class imbalance, we augmented the non-thermophilic dataset with challenging examples. These examples were retrieved from non-thermophilic organisms (BacDive) and exhibited high sequence similarity (80% < identity < 95%) to the thermophilic sequences (Fig 2.1). The final TemBERTure_{DB} was stored as an SQL database facilitating efficient data retrieval for downstream analyses (Appendix Table A.1)

BacDive Within the BacDive database, organisms were classified based on growth temperature: thermophilic (>60°C) and non-thermophilic (<30°C). Protein sequences were then retrieved for each organism from the NCBI database, and ambiguous or short sequences (<30° amino acids) were excluded. Given the substantial disparity between the number of non-thermophilic and thermophilic sequences, we used MMseqs in cascading mode to cluster the non-thermophilic sequences. We then undersampled the centroids (representatives of each cluster) to align with the number of thermophilic centroids identified using MMseqs with a 50% identity threshold (Appendix Table A.2).

Meltome We leveraged data curated within TemBERTure_{DB} and excluded the non-thermophilic counterparts of the high-similarity sequence pairs retrieved from the BacDive database (Appendix Table A.3).

FIGURE 2.1: **TemBERTure database creation and model architecture.** (A) TemBERTure_{DB} creation pipeline: protein sequences from organisms within the Meltome Atlas were retrieved from the UniProt database and categorized based on their thermophilicity (right: thermophilic, left: non-thermophilic). Additional sequences were then collected from BacDive (Reimer et al., 2022) and NCBI (Sayers et al., 2022) databases at various temperature thresholds to augment the dataset. The final database comprises approximately 0.3 million each for thermophilic and non-thermophilic proteins, further divided into training, testing, and validation sets that are representative of the temperature distribution. (B) TemBERTure_{CLS} model architecture was based on the proBERT-BFD framework, with lightweight bottleneck adapter layers inserted between each transformer layer (shown in gray). The model takes a protein sequence as input and outputs a score indicating the classification score of the sequence being thermophilic or non-thermophilic.

Splitting For model training, we partitioned the datasets into an 80:10:10 ratio for the training, validation, and test sets, respectively. To mitigate any potential information leakage between sets, all sequences were clustered with MMseqs at a 50% identity threshold. Centroids and their corresponding clusters were then assigned to the same split.

For the regression task, we exclusively used the initial Meltome dataset. Melting temperatures were categorized into temperature bins of 10°C, and 10 data points from each temperature bin were randomly selected for both the test and validation sets. To address the imbalance in the distribution of melting temperatures within the training set, we implemented a combination of undersampling and oversampling techniques. Temperature bins with an abundance of data points (40–55°C) were undersampled, whereas bins with a scarcity of data points (20–40 and 60–90°C) were oversampled. This approach ensured a balanced number of data points across all temperature bins.

2.2.2 TemBERTure_{CLS}

TemBERTure_{CLS} (Fig. 2.1B) is a sequence-based classifier that takes the amino acid sequence as input and outputs the corresponding thermal class of the protein along with its associated score.

It was built on top of the pre-trained protBERT-BFD model (Elnaggar et al., 2022), a BERT model composed of 30 layers, 16 heads, and 1024 hidden layers and trained on over 2 billion protein sequences from the BFD100 (Steinegger and Söding, 2018; Steinegger, Mirdita, et al., 2019) dataset. In order to reduce the number of trainable parameters and enhance the efficiency of the training process, we opted for an adapter-based fine-tuning technique (Houlsby et al., 2019; Poth et al., 2023) where light weight bottleneck layers are inserted between each transformer layer.

TemBERTure_{CLS} was thus implemented as a BertAdapterModel with Pfeiffer adapters (Pfeiffer et al., 2021) configuration using the PyTorch framework via adapters (Houlsby et al., 2019; Poth et al., 2023) library. It was initiated with the protBERT-BFD (Elnaggar et al., 2022) weights through the HuggingFace API (Wolf et al., 2019) and the Pfeiffer adapter architecture layers were added after the feed-forward block of each transformer layer (Vaswani et al., 2017; Wolf et al., 2020). In this way, we reduced the number of trainable parameters from 420 million to 5 million.

Training Protein sequences were tokenized at the amino acid level utilizing the protBERT-BFD (Elnaggar et al., 2022) tokenizer, with all sequences truncated to a maximum length of 512. For each dataset, a separate hyperparameter search was carried out to optimize the training and architecture of the model (Appendix Table A.4). This hyperparameter search was performed using W&B Sweeps (Biewald, 2020) grid hyperparameter search. The adapter training was carried out for a maximum of 20 epochs for each dataset with a batch size of 16, using AdamW optimizer (Loshchilov and Hutter, 2017) with default Hugging Face (Wolf et al., 2019) configuration. The model that achieved the lowest validation loss was then saved for evaluation. To ensure model robustness, the final configuration of each model was trained three times under identical conditions, varying only the random seed. This approach allowed us to assess the model’s independence from specific random seeds and to confirm its reliability across different runs. All models were trained on a single NVIDIA A100 80G GPU.

2.2.3 TemBERTure_{T_m}

TemBERTure_{T_m} is a sequence-based regression model designed to predict the protein melting temperature (T_m) directly from its amino acid sequence. This model has the same underlying architecture configuration and tokenization as TemBERTure_{CLS}, with a regression head. Leveraging the pre-trained protBERT-BFD model, we adopted again an adapter-based fine-tuning technique to reduce trainable parameters.

2.2.4 Training

The model was trained on a curated dataset created specifically for predicting protein melting temperatures, based on TemBERTure_{DB}. All sequences are truncated to a maximum length of 512. The training was carried out for a maximum of 200 epochs for each run with a batch size of 16 and using AdamW optimizer (Loshchilov and Hutter, 2017) with default Hugging Face (Wolf et al., 2019) values. We conducted, with W&B Sweeps (Biewald, 2020) an extensive search to identify the optimal configuration of the regression head (Appendix Table A.5). We then explored various weight initialization approaches for the model. In addition to random initialization, we investigated transfer learning from TemBERTure_{CLS} at different training stages. This involved introducing classifier weights at 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of the first epoch, along with weights from the fully trained classifier. To assess model stability and consistency across random initializations, all models were trained three times with different random seeds. For each configuration, the model achieving the lowest validation loss was saved for further evaluation. All training runs utilized a single NVIDIA A100 80G GPU.

2.2.5 Analysis

Ensemble evaluation for melting temperature prediction To improve prediction accuracy, we evaluated different ensembles of models on the validation set. We built these ensembles by selecting subsets of the initial 18 models. These 18 models encompassed all distinct initialization methods (random and transfer learning with TemBERTure_{CLS} weights) and their replicates. We investigated three ensemble approaches: greedy algorithm, weighted ensemble, and a method leveraging TemBERTure_{CLS}. Additionally, we experimented with various averaging techniques (standard deviation and interquartile range, IQR) to combine predictions and identify the optimal value for each data point. Overall, these ensemble strategies aimed to harness the strengths of multiple models and achieve a configuration effective across a broad temperature range. Detailed descriptions are provided in the Ensemble evaluation for melting temperature prediction in the Supplementary Information (Appendix A).

High attention score The IQR method was used to identify amino acids within a protein sequence with a high attention score (HAS). We calculated a threshold by adding 1.5 times the IQR to the third quartile (Q3) of the attention scores. Attention scores exceeding this threshold are flagged as outliers, indicating a noticeably HAS and potentially significant influence on the model's decisions.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 TemBERTure_{DB}

To train our deep learning models for predicting protein thermostability, we curated TemBERTure_{DB}, a comprehensive dataset built upon the Meltome Atlas (Jarzab et al., 2020) that includes data for over 48 000 proteins across 13 different species (Fig. 2.1A). We further enriched it with all protein sequences from UniProtKB for each organism (Consortium, 2023). This initially resulted in a highly imbalanced dataset with only 44000 sequences from thermophilic organisms (growth temperature above 60°C) compared to 4.3 million sequences from non-thermophilic organisms (growth temperatures: 16–36°C). To address this imbalance, we incorporated thermophilic proteomes from BacDive, adding 0.9 million sequences (Reimer et al., 2022). However, the thermophilic dataset remained biased toward bacterial and archaeal sequences. Therefore, we included similar bacterial sequences (<30°C growth temperature) with high identity (>80%) to thermophiles. This added valuable non-thermophilic examples outside the target class, for a more challenging training set (Appendix Table A.1).

To ensure that both classes contained diverse protein families and folds, we clustered each class separately using MMseqs (Hauser et al., 2016), resulting in a balanced dataset of 300 000 sequences per class. We partitioned it into training, validation, and test sets at an 80:10:10 ratio, ensuring that sequences with high similarity remained within the same split, to avoid information leakage. To enhance model learning and generalization, pairs of highly similar sequences from different classes were exclusively reserved for training, effectively bridging the gap between thermophilic and non-thermophilic sequences (Appendix Table A.6).

2.3.2 TemBERTure_{CLS}

TemBERTure_{DB} served as the training dataset for TemBERTure_{CLS}, a sequence-based classifier designed to predict the thermal class of a protein solely from its amino acid sequence (2.1B). TemBERTure_{CLS} is a binary classifier, where the thermophilic class is defined as a sequence coming from organisms with a growth temperature above 60°C. TemBERTure_{CLS} leveraged protBERT-BFD, a pre-trained protein language model (Elnaggar et al., 2022) utilized adapter layers (Houlsby

et al., 2019; Poth et al., 2023) for efficient task-specific learning. This approach offers faster (up to 50%) and more robust training (avoiding catastrophic forgetting) than full fine-tuning, thus enabling rapid model experimentation and optimization without sacrificing performance.

TemBERTure_{CLS} achieved an overall accuracy of 0.89, an F1-score of 0.9, and a Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) of 0.78, with balanced predictive performance across both classes (0.88 and 0.90 F1-score for non-thermophilic and thermophilic sequence, respectively). Low standard deviation across multiple trained models confirms robust training. We, therefore, chose to retain the initially trained model as the final TemBERTure_{CLS} model. When comparing the performance of TemBERTure_{CLS} to state-of-the-art models, we observed that many of the latter tend to overpredict the non-thermophilic class (Fig. 2.2). Despite achieving a competitive average precision of 0.79 for thermophilic sequences, their recall fell below 0.7, resulting in numerous misclassifications of non-thermophilic proteins. This highlights the limitations in the generalizability of current methods (Appendix Table A.7).

FIGURE 2.2: **Comparison of TemBERTure_{CLS} with state-of-the-art models on the TemBERTure_{DB} test set.** Recall and precision are shown separately for thermophilic (right) and non-thermophilic (left) thermal categories.

To assess the generalization of TemBERTure_{CLS}, we tested it on the widely used iThermo dataset (Ahmed, Zulfiqar, and Khan, 2022) and the TemStaPro test set (Pudžiuvėlytė et al., 2024). After removing similar sequences (over 50% identity), the final test sets contained 65 and 1495 thermophilic sequences and 505 and 10 849 non-thermophilic sequences for iThermo and TemStaPro, respectively. This substantial reduction in dataset size resulted in highly imbalanced non-overlapping sets. Consequently, we evaluated TemBERTure_{CLS} performance using the macro-averaged F1-score, recall, and precision (Appendix Table A.8). TemBERTure_{CLS} maintained high

accuracy, achieving 86% on iThermo and 83% on TemStaPro. To explore TemBERTure_{CLS} ability to perform on sequences from novel organisms, we created a new test set with sequences from organisms in the BacDive database (Reimer et al., 2022). Although non-thermophilic sequence precision remained high (0.81), precision for thermophilic sequences dropped (0.74), suggesting limitations in generalizing to completely new organisms.

To further investigate this observation, we trained separate models, with the same architecture as TemBERTure_{CLS}, with two distinct datasets: one derived from BacDive (Reimer et al., 2022), focusing solely on bacterial and archaeal organisms, and another one from the Meltome Atlas (Jarzab et al., 2020), augmented solely with thermophilic sequences (Appendix Table A.2 and Tablr A.3). Each model performed well on the dataset derived from the same source as its training data. However, performances dropped significantly when tested on the other datasets (Fig. 2.3A). These variations were less pronounced for the thermophilic class, most likely because all datasets used BacDive for selecting thermophilic organisms. In contrast, the non-thermophilic class exhibited greater performance variations. The BacDive-trained model’s performance dropped significantly, when tested on the TemBERTure_{DB} or Meltome_{DB} data (almost random classifications), whereas TemBERTure_{CLS} and the Meltome-trained model maintained comparable performance across all datasets, indicating the necessity of using diverse training datasets to improve generalizability. To assess potential data leakage between training and test sets, we clustered TemBERTure_{DB} test sequences based on their maximum identity to training set sequences (Fig. 2.3B). TemBERTure_{CLS} performance remained consistent across all identity ranges for the non-thermophilic class. A decrease in performance was observed specifically within the thermophilic class for sequences with less than 20% identity. However, the performance remained comparable to the one previously observed when using a test set from a different source than the training data. This could be attributed to either overfitting to specific training data patterns or the inherent difficulty of classifying these sequences (e.g. orphan proteins).

2.3.3 TemBERTure_{Tm}

Building on these promising TemBERTure_{CLS} results, we developed TemBERTure_{Tm}, to predict protein melting temperature (T_m) from its primary sequence. Extracting the readily available protein melting temperature data from the Meltome Atlas, we again leveraged protBERT-BFD and adapter layers for training TemBERTure_{Tm}. Even though the model achieved a seemingly high Pearson correlation of 0.78, a more detailed analysis revealed a clear limitation (Fig. 2.4A). The predicted temperatures displayed a surprising bimodal distribution, concentrated around non-thermophilic (below 60°C) and thermophilic (above 80°C) ranges. This suggests a bias toward classifying temperatures into these broad categories rather than accurately predicting the melting points. This bias agrees with the weak correlation within each class (0.41 for non-thermophilic, -0.33 for thermophilic) and high accuracy (82%) of TemBERTure_{Tm} as a classifier using a 70°C threshold. Moreover, TemBERTure_{Tm} displayed significant variability among replicates trained with different random seeds, suggesting instability and limitations within the training process.

Given the limited size (around 30 000 sequences) of the Meltome Atlas dataset, we explored transfer learning. We hypothesized that pre-trained adapter weights from TemBERTure_{CLS}, which captured thermal class features, could improve TemBERTure_{Tm} regression performance. Our approach involved replacing the random initialization of the adapter layers with weights from various stages of the classification training process. Since TemBERTure_{Tm} prediction followed a bimodal distribution, we chose different training stages for the adapter weights, aiming to balance leveraging learned thermal features and enabling the regression to move beyond this bias. However, this approach did not yield any significant improvements in performance.

FIGURE 2.3: **TemBERTure database creation and model architecture.** (A) Confusion matrix comparing the performance of the TemBERTure_{CLS} model with models trained on data derived from only BacDive and Meltome. The evaluation is performed on three separate test sets: TemBERTure_{DB}, BacDive_{DB}, and Meltome_{DB} test sets. Each cell in the matrix represents the proportion of predictions made by a specific model on a specific test set. (B) TemBERTure_{CLS} performance on TemBERTure_{DB} test sequences clustered by maximum identity to training data. Shades of blue (top row) indicates correct predictions for the non-thermophilic category, while shades of red (bottom row) represent the performance for thermophilic sequences. Off-diagonal entries indicate instances of misclassification.

In order to improve the performance, we explored diverse ensembling strategies (see Ensemble evaluation for melting temperature prediction in Appendix A). First, we established an upper bound on achievable performance using an oracle approach. From all TemBERTure_{T_m} variations, the oracle selected the prediction from all TemBERTure_{T_m} variations that was closest to the experimentally measured melting temperature. This yielded a best-case scenario with an MAE of 2.64°C and an R^2 of 0.94 on the test set, highlighting the potential of the underlying approach. However, the ensemble techniques only led to a marginal change in performance (Appendix Table A.9). A more promising approach involved leveraging thermal class information. We first predicted a protein’s class (non-thermophilic or thermophilic) using TemBERTure_{CLS} to predict the thermal class (non-thermophilic or thermophilic) of the protein sequence. Then, we selected a subset of best performing TemBERTure_{T_m} models for each class. This resulted in a combination of five models for non-thermophilic predictions (all transfer learning) and two models for thermophilic predictions (Appendix Table A.9), i.e. one with random weights and one with partial first-epoch weights. This highlights the importance of incorporating class information, achieving

FIGURE 2.4: **Predicted melting temperatures.** (A) Scatter plot comparing the measured melting temperatures to predicted melting temperature. Each point is colored based on the thermal category (blue: non-thermophilic and red: thermophilic). The dashed gray line represents a perfect prediction. Standard deviations are calculated from the predictions of three replicates. (B) Distributions of melting temperature for various organisms, represented by a colored gradient ranging from red (high growth temperature) to blue (low growth temperature). The measured melting temperature distributions are shown in gray, while the predicted distributions using TemBERTure T_m are shown in color. Gray circles mark the growth temperatures of each organism and the temperatures noted in parentheses indicating the average melting temperatures of the organism’s proteome.

a decrease in MAE (6.31°C) and an increase in R^2 (0.78) on the test set compared to other ensemble techniques.

Despite limitations in predicting individual melting points, TemBERTure T_m showed promise in capturing broader thermal properties. We used the model to predict the melting temperatures of unmeasured proteins from organisms within the Meltome Atlas. Interestingly, the predicted distribution mirrored the known distribution of measured melting temperatures across diverse organisms (Fig. 2.4B). This suggests that, although TemBERTure T_m has some difficulties in predicting individual values, it still might capture underlying patterns related to protein thermostability across species.

2.3.4 Interpretability

To explore the intricate relationships between amino acid properties and thermostability, we conducted an analysis of the attention mechanisms in the TemBERTure CLS model. Attention mechanisms offer an interpretable scoring function, highlighting segments of the input sequence that are most important for a particular prediction by assigning them higher scores. In the context of TemBERTure CLS , this would allow for a comprehensive identification of crucial amino acids and regions within a sequence that may influence the thermostability prediction. We defined HAS regions as exceeding the IQR of attention values across the entire sequence. All analyses were performed using the first replica of TemBERTure CLS .

Effect of fine-tuning To investigate the impact of fine-tuning on the model’s attention patterns, we compared the frequencies of HAS amino acids between the pre-trained protBERT-BFD model and TemBERTure CLS . We hypothesized that changes in HAS frequencies might correlate with features linked to thermostability. Although the overall attention scores remained remarkably similar between the two models, we observed a shift in the frequency of HAS for specific amino acids

(Fig. 2.5A). For thermophilic proteins, leucine, arginine, and alanine appeared more frequently as HAS, whereas the frequency only increased for leucine in non-thermophilic sequences (Appendix Fig. A.1).

FIGURE 2.5: **Frequency of high attention score (HAS) by amino acid.** (A) Scatter plot comparing the frequency of HAS amino acids of the pre-trained proBERT-BFD model to TemBERTure_{CLS}. Each point represents an amino acid and is colored in gray if the frequency of HAS increased in TemBERTure_{CLS}. (B) Bubble plot comparing the frequency of each amino acid in the test set to its HAS frequency. Red bubble indicates that the frequency of HAS is higher for thermophilic and blue bubbles for non-thermophilic. Each bubble is scaled to the difference in frequency between both classes.

Amino acids enrichment We conducted a more in-depth analysis by comparing the enrichment levels of each amino acid within the protein sequences with their natural occurrence frequencies. We calculated the background frequency of each amino acid in the TemBERTure_{DB} test set and compared it to the frequency at which they appeared as HAS (Fig. 2.5B and Appendix Fig. A.2). This analysis revealed distinct patterns between thermophilic and non-thermophilic proteins. For example, we observed an increase in HAS frequency for several hydrophobic residues, such as alanine, phenylalanine, and leucine, which potentially reflect their role in stabilizing the protein core through tight packing. Interestingly, cysteine, which is known for forming stabilizing disulfide bridges and coordinating metals (Pace and Weerapana, 2014), received higher attention in non-thermophiles. Glutamine and asparagine, susceptible to deamidation at high temperatures (Ahern and Klibanov, 1985; Tomazic and Klibanov, 1988; Rahimzadeh et al., 2012), showed decreased HAS, in agreement with their expected scarcity in these organisms. TemBERTure_{CLS} also showed a clear preference for different charged amino acids, with an increase in HAS for arginine and a decrease in HAS for lysine. However, it is crucial to underscore the potential complexity in interpreting HAS scores. An increase in HASs might suggest functional importance; however, their interpretation requires caution due to dependence on the local amino acid environment. Conversely, decreased HAS for specific amino acids might not indicate a negative impact, but rather reflect the model’s focus on their specific critical interactions within the protein structure.

Structural analysis In order to gain some structural insights from the attention scores, we analysed 17 pairs of homologous thermophilic and non-thermophilic proteins correctly classified by TemBERTure_{CLS}. These pairs shared moderate sequence similarity (identity score: 0.28–0.54). Although the overall attention patterns between homologous proteins showed some correlation, the

HAS amino acids exhibited more variability. Between homologous proteins, the model assigned a similar number of HAS to both conserved and non-conserved amino acids (Fig. 2.6A and Appendix Fig. A.3). Interestingly, the specific amino acids receiving HAS often differed between homologs, even in conserved regions. This is further supported by the presence of many HAS within insertion regions, highlighting the model’s ability to focus on regions beyond the conserved core for thermostability prediction.

FIGURE 2.6: Representative structural analysis of attention score. (A) Scatter plot comparing the attention scores assigned by the TemBERTure_{CLS} model to individual amino acids in two homologous protein structures (PDB ID: 1LDN [thermophilic] and 1LDG [non-thermophilic]) with 46% sequence identity. Each marker represents an amino acid, categorized by its conservation level: circles for non-conserved, diamonds for conserved, and triangles for insertions. HAS amino acids in the thermophilic structure are highlighted in red, while those in the non-thermophilic counterpart are highlighted in blue. (B and C) Cartoon representation of both protein structures. The width and color indicate the attention score values, with regions with higher attention scores appearing thicker and redder. (D) Cartoon representation of 1LDN colored based on the entropy at each amino acid position. Higher entropy (green, thicker regions) indicates greater sequence variability.

To understand how TemBERTure_{CLS} leverages structural information beyond sequence similarity, we mapped the attention scores directly onto protein structures (Fig. 2.6B and C; Appendix Fig. A.4). Higher attention scores localized similarly across homologs, regardless of sequence entropy (Fig. 2.6D and Appendix Fig. A.5). Notably, higher attention scores often resided in helical regions and in the protein core, potentially revealing the prioritization of structurally important elements for predicting thermostability.

2.4 Discussion

Protein thermostability is crucial for various applications in biotechnology and biology. Traditional experimental methods for assessing it are laborious, expensive, and prone to errors. Here, we developed a new set of tools which allowed us to explore the potential of deep learning models to predict protein thermostability. Our study highlights the crucial role that data diversity plays in training robust models. We observed significant performance improvement with datasets encompassing a wider range of sequences from various organisms. Conversely, insufficient diversity, as seen in the BacDive derived dataset, led to models that struggled with challenging test sets. This emphasizes the need for a holistic approach to data curation, in order to ensure balanced representation of diverse species in the training data.

Although the Meltome Atlas presents an impressive number of melting temperatures, it suffers from certain biases, in particular, the data primarily represents non-thermophilic organisms with a temperature gap between 60 and 70°C. And yet, TemBERTure_{T_m}'s predictions, while not accurate for absolute melting temperatures, still captured the overall distribution of melting temperatures observed across different species in the dataset. This suggests the model might have prioritized recognizing the species origin of the sequence rather than intrinsic thermostability features. This agrees with previous findings showing that sequence embeddings from language models can already capture these broad differences between thermophilic and non-thermophilic organisms (Pudžiuvėlytė et al., 2024). Additionally, the presence of thermostable proteins within non-thermophilic proteomes further underscores the limitations of using growth temperature alone as a thermostability proxy.

Various statistical approaches have attempted to identify important changes in amino acid composition linked to thermostability (Schäfer et al., 1996; Kumar et al., 2000; Vieille and Zeikus, 2001; Sadeghi et al., 2006; Folch, Rooman, et al., 2008; Folch, Dehouck, et al., 2010; Ahmed, Zulfiqar, and L. Tang, 2022). However, such analyses heavily depend on dataset curation, leading to contradictory results. Furthermore, while certain biophysical properties of residues may elucidate their prevalence in thermostable proteins, thermophilicity is a multifaceted attribute influenced by the positioning and microenvironment of amino acids within the protein. This study presents the concept of leveraging attention scores to gain more nuanced insights into protein thermostability. Even though we observed some global trends consistent with previous analyses (e.g. enrichment of specific amino acids), TemBERTure_{CLS} also highlighted the value of analyzing these interactions within the context of the 3D protein structure. However, our findings suggest that the present attention scores still need to be refined, since they capture both thermostability-related features and organism-specific characteristics. Further research is needed to refine them for a more precise understanding of protein thermostability.

In conclusion, this study shed light on the limitations of current approaches for predicting protein thermostability and introduced new avenues for exploration. It highlighted the importance of using diverse training data, thus extending the analysis beyond single-species, and exploiting important features of the models, such as attention scores. Although our study demonstrates the importance of careful data splitting strategies, the precise impact of different sequence identity thresholds warrants further investigation. These findings can be expected to lay the groundwork for future research to develop even more robust and informative methods for predicting protein thermostability.

References

- Adams, M. W. W. and R. M. Kelly (1995). "Enzymes from microorganisms in extreme environments". In: *Chem Eng News Archive* 73, pp. 32–42. DOI: [10.1021/cen-v073n051.p032](https://doi.org/10.1021/cen-v073n051.p032).
- Ahern, T. J. and A. M. Klivanov (1985). "The mechanism of irreversible enzyme inactivation at 100°C". In: *Science* 228, pp. 1280–1284. DOI: [10.1126/science.4001942](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.4001942).
- Ahmed, Z., H. Zulfiqar, and A. A. Khan (2022). "iThermo: a sequence-based model for identifying thermophilic proteins using a multi-feature fusion strategy". In: *Frontiers in Microbiology* 13, p. 790063. DOI: [10.3389/fmicb.2022.790063](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.790063).
- Ahmed, Z., H. Zulfiqar, and L. Tang (2022). "A statistical analysis of the sequence and structure of thermophilic and non-thermophilic proteins". In: *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 23, p. 10116. DOI: [10.3390/ijms231710116](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms231710116).
- Bashirova, A., S. Pramanik, and P. Volkov (2019). "Disulfide bond engineering of an endoglucanase from *Penicillium verruculosum* to improve its thermostability". In: *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 20, p. 1602. DOI: [10.3390/ijms20071602](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20071602).
- Biewald, L. (2020). *Experiment Tracking with Weights and Biases*. <https://www.wandb.com/>.
- Bleicher, L., E. T. Prates, and T. C. F. Gomes (2011). "Molecular basis of the thermostability and thermophilicity of laminarinases: X-ray structure of the hyperthermostable laminarinase from *Rhodothermus marinus* and molecular dynamics simulations". In: *Journal of Physical Chemistry B* 115, pp. 7940–7949. DOI: [10.1021/jp200330z](https://doi.org/10.1021/jp200330z).
- Bommarius, A. S., J. M. Broering, and J. F. Chaparro-Riggers (2006). "High-throughput screening for enhanced protein stability". In: *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* 17, pp. 606–610. DOI: [10.1016/j.copbio.2006.10.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copbio.2006.10.001).
- Chakravarty, S. and R. Varadarajan (2002). "Elucidation of factors responsible for enhanced thermal stability of proteins: a structural genomics based study". In: *Biochemistry* 41, pp. 8152–8161. DOI: [10.1021/bi025523t](https://doi.org/10.1021/bi025523t).
- Charoenkwan, P., W. Chotpatiwetchkul, and V. S. Lee (2021). "A novel sequence-based predictor for identifying and characterizing thermophilic proteins using estimated propensity scores of dipeptides". In: *Scientific Reports* 11, p. 23782. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-021-03293-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-03293-w).
- Charoenkwan, P., N. Schaduangrat, and M. A.-U.-A. Moni (2022). "SAPPHIRE: a stacking-based ensemble learning framework for accurate prediction of thermophilic proteins". In: *Computers in Biology and Medicine* 146, p. 105704. DOI: [10.1016/j.combiomed.2022.105704](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2022.105704).
- Consortium, T. U. (2023). "UniProt: the universal protein knowledgebase in 2023". In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 51, pp. D523–D531. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkac1052](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac1052).
- Devlin, J. et al. (2019). "BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding". In: *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics (NAACL-HLT)*. Minneapolis, Minnesota: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 4171–4186. DOI: [10.18653/v1/N19-1423](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/N19-1423).

- Ding, Y., Y. Cai, and G. Zhang (2004). "The influence of dipeptide composition on protein thermostability". In: *FEBS Letters* 569, pp. 284–288. DOI: [10.1016/j.febslet.2004.06.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.febslet.2004.06.009).
- Elnaggar, A., M. Heinzinger, and C. Dallago (2022). "ProfTrans: toward understanding the language of life through self-supervised learning". In: *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 44, pp. 7112–7127. DOI: [10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3095381](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3095381).
- Folch, B., Y. Dehouck, and M. Rooman (2010). "Thermo- and mesostabilizing protein interactions identified by temperature-dependent statistical potentials". In: *Biophysical Journal* 98, pp. 667–677. DOI: [10.1016/j.bpj.2009.10.050](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpj.2009.10.050).
- Folch, B., M. Rooman, and Y. Dehouck (2008). "Thermostability of salt bridges versus hydrophobic interactions in proteins probed by statistical potentials". In: *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling* 48, pp. 119–127. DOI: [10.1021/ci700237g](https://doi.org/10.1021/ci700237g).
- Fukuchi, S. and K. Nishikawa (2001). "Protein surface amino acid compositions distinctively differ between thermophilic and mesophilic bacteria". In: *Journal of Molecular Biology* 309, pp. 835–843. DOI: [10.1006/jmbi.2001.4718](https://doi.org/10.1006/jmbi.2001.4718).
- Gromiha, M. M. and M. X. Suresh (2007). "Discrimination of mesophilic and thermophilic proteins using machine learning algorithms". In: *Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics* 70, pp. 1274–1279. DOI: [10.1002/prot.21616](https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.21616).
- Haney, P., J. Konisky, and K. K. Koretke (1997). "Structural basis for thermostability and identification of potential active site residues for adenylate kinases from the archaeal genus *Methanococcus*". In: *Proteins* 28, pp. 117–130. DOI: [10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0134\(199705\)28:1<117::AID-PROT12>3.0.CO;2-M](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0134(199705)28:1<117::AID-PROT12>3.0.CO;2-M).
- Haselbeck, F., M. John, and Y. Zhang (2023). "Superior protein thermophilicity prediction with protein language model embeddings". In: *NAR Genomics and Bioinformatics* 5, lqad087. DOI: [10.1093/nargab/lqad087](https://doi.org/10.1093/nargab/lqad087).
- Hauser, M., M. Steinegger, and J. Söding (2016). "MMseqs software suite for fast and deep clustering and searching of large protein sequence sets". In: *Bioinformatics* 32, pp. 1323–1330. DOI: [10.1093/bioinformatics/btw006](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btw006).
- Himmel, M. E., S.-Y. Ding, and D. K. Johnson (2007). "Biomass recalcitrance: engineering plants and enzymes for biofuels production". In: *Science* 315, pp. 804–807. DOI: [10.1126/science.1137016](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1137016).
- Houlsby, N., A. Giurgiu, and S. Jastrzebski (2019). "Parameter-Efficient Transfer Learning for NLP". In: *Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Machine Learning*. PMLR, pp. 2790–2799.
- Jarzab, A., N. Kurzawa, and T. Hopf (2020). "Meltome atlas—thermal proteome stability across the tree of life". In: *Nature Methods* 17, pp. 495–503. DOI: [10.1038/s41592-020-0801-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-020-0801-4).
- Jung, F., K. Frey, and D. Zimmer (2023). "DeepSTABp: a deep learning approach for the prediction of thermal protein stability". In: *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24, p. 7444. DOI: [10.3390/ijms24087444](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24087444).

-
- Kuddus, M., ed. (2018). *Enzymes in Food Technology: Improvements and Innovations*. Singapore: Springer Singapore. DOI: [10.1007/978-981-13-1933-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-1933-4).
- Kumar, S., C.-J. Tsai, and R. Nussinov (2000). "Factors enhancing protein thermostability". In: *Protein Engineering* 13, pp. 179–191. DOI: [10.1093/protein/13.3.179](https://doi.org/10.1093/protein/13.3.179).
- Leuenberger, P., S. Ganscha, and A. Kahraman (2017). "Cell-wide analysis of protein thermal unfolding reveals determinants of thermostability". In: *Science* 355, eaai7825. DOI: [10.1126/science.aai7825](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aai7825).
- Liang, H.-K., C.-M. Huang, and M.-T. Ko (2005). "Amino acid coupling patterns in thermophilic proteins". In: *Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics* 59, pp. 58–63. DOI: [10.1002/prot.20386](https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.20386).
- Lin, H. and W. Chen (2011). "Prediction of thermophilic proteins using feature selection technique". In: *Journal of Microbiological Methods* 84, pp. 67–70. DOI: [10.1016/j.mimet.2010.10.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mimet.2010.10.013).
- Loshchilov, I. and F. Hutter (2017). "Decoupled Weight Decay Regularization". In: *International Conference on Learning Representations*.
- Matsuura, Y., M. Takehira, and Y. Joti (2015). "Thermodynamics of protein denaturation at temperatures over 100°C: cutA1 mutant proteins substituted with hydrophobic and charged residues". In: *Scientific Reports* 5, p. 15545. DOI: [10.1038/srep15545](https://doi.org/10.1038/srep15545).
- Modarres, H. P., M. R. Mofrad, and A. Sanati-Nezhad (2018). "ProtDataTherm: a database for thermostability analysis and engineering of proteins". In: *PLoS One* 13, e0191222. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0191222](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0191222).
- Nakariyakul, S., Z.-P. Liu, and L. Chen (2012). "Detecting thermophilic proteins through selecting amino acid and dipeptide composition features". In: *Amino Acids* 42, pp. 1947–1953. DOI: [10.1007/s00726-011-0923-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-011-0923-1).
- Nikam, R., A. Kulandaisamy, and K. Harini (2021). "ProThermDB: thermodynamic database for proteins and mutants revisited after 15 years". In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 49, pp. D420–D424. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkaa1035](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa1035).
- Pace, N. J. and E. Weerapana (2014). "Zinc-binding cysteines: diverse functions and structural motifs". In: *Biomolecules* 4, pp. 419–434. DOI: [10.3390/biom4020419](https://doi.org/10.3390/biom4020419).
- Pei, H., J. Li, and S. Ma (2023). "Identification of thermophilic proteins based on sequence-based bidirectional representations from transformer-embedding features". In: *Applied Sciences* 13, p. 2858. DOI: [10.3390/app13052858](https://doi.org/10.3390/app13052858).
- Pfeiffer, J., A. Kamath, and A. Rücklé (2021). "AdapterFusion: non-destructive task composition for transfer learning". In: *Proceedings of the 16th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 487–503. DOI: [10.18653/v1/2021.eacl-main.39](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.eacl-main.39).
- Poth, C., H. Sterz, and I. Paul (2023). "Adapters: a Unified Library for Parameter-efficient and Modular Transfer Learning". In: *Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*.

- Pudžiuvėlytė, I., K. Olechnovič, and E. Godliauskaite (2024). “TemStaPro: protein thermostability prediction using sequence representations from protein language models”. In: *Bioinformatics* 40, btae157. DOI: [10.1093/bioinformatics/btae157](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btae157).
- Raffel, C., N. Shazeer, and A. Roberts (2020). “Exploring the Limits of Transfer Learning with a Unified Text-to-Text Transformer”. In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 21, 140:5485–5551.
- Rahimzadeh, M., K. Khajeh, and M. Mirshahi (2012). “Probing the role of asparagine mutation in thermostability of *Bacillus* KR-8104 α -Amylase”. In: *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 50, pp. 1175–1182. DOI: [10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2011.11.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2011.11.014).
- Reimer, L. C., J. Sardà Carbasse, and J. Koblitz (2022). “BacDive in 2022: the knowledge base for standardized bacterial and archaeal data”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 50, pp. D741–D746. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkab961](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab961).
- Sadeghi, M., H. Naderi-Manesh, and M. Zarrabi (2006). “Effective factors in thermostability of thermophilic proteins”. In: *Biophysical Chemistry* 119, pp. 256–270. DOI: [10.1016/j.bpc.2005.09.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpc.2005.09.018).
- Sayers, E. W., E. E. Bolton, and J. R. Brister (2022). “Database resources of the National Center for Biotechnology Information”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 50, pp. D20–D26. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkab112](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab112).
- Schäfer, T., H. Bönisch, and S. Kardinahl (1996). “Three extremely thermostable proteins from *Sulfolobus* and a reappraisal of the ‘traffic rules’”. In: *Biological Chemistry Hoppe-Seyler* 377, pp. 505–512. DOI: [10.1515/bchm3.1996.377.7-8.505](https://doi.org/10.1515/bchm3.1996.377.7-8.505).
- Singh, R., M. Kumar, and A. Mittal (2016). “Microbial enzymes: industrial progress in 21st century”. In: *3 Biotech* 6, p. 174. DOI: [10.1007/s13205-016-0485-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-016-0485-8).
- Steinegger, M., M. Mirdita, and J. Söding (2019). “Protein-level assembly increases protein sequence recovery from metagenomic samples manyfold”. In: *Nature Methods* 16, pp. 603–606. DOI: [10.1038/s41592-019-0437-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0437-4).
- Steinegger, M. and J. Söding (2018). “Clustering huge protein sequence sets in linear time”. In: *Nature Communications* 9, p. 2542. DOI: [10.1038/s41467-018-04964-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-04964-5).
- Stourac, J. J., M. Dubrava, and J. Musil (2021). “FireProtDB: database of manually curated protein stability data”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 49, pp. D319–D324. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkaa981](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa981).
- Tang, H., R.-Z. Cao, and W. Wang (2017). “A two-step discriminated method to identify thermophilic proteins”. In: *International Journal of Biomathematics* 10, p. 1750050. DOI: [10.1142/S1793524517500504](https://doi.org/10.1142/S1793524517500504).
- Tomazic, S. J. and A. M. Klibanov (1988). “Why is one *Bacillus* alpha-amylase more resistant against irreversible thermoinactivation than another?” In: *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 263, pp. 3092–3096. DOI: [10.1016/S0021-9258\(18\)69039-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258(18)69039-8).
- Vaswani, A., N. Shazeer, and N. Parmar (2017). “Attention is All You Need”. In: *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*. Red Hook, NY, USA: Curran Associates Inc., pp. 6000–6010.

-
- Vieille, C. and G. J. Zeikus (2001). "Hyperthermophilic enzymes: sources, uses, and molecular mechanisms for thermostability". In: *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews* 65, pp. 1–43. DOI: [10.1128/MMBR.65.1.1-43.2001](https://doi.org/10.1128/MMBR.65.1.1-43.2001).
- Wolf, T., L. Debut, and V. Sanh (2019). *HuggingFace's Transformers: State-of-the-Art Natural Language Processing*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.03771.
- (2020). "Transformers: State-of-the-Art Natural Language Processing". In: *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: System Demonstrations*. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 38–45. DOI: [10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-demos.6](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-demos.6).
- Wu, L., J.-H. Lee, and H.-D. Huang (2009). "An expert system to predict protein thermostability using decision tree". In: *Expert Systems with Applications* 36, pp. 9007–9014. DOI: [10.1016/j.eswa.2008.12.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2008.12.020).
- Yang, Y., X. Ding, and G. Zhu (2019). "ProTstab—predictor for cellular protein stability". In: *BMC Genomics* 20, p. 804. DOI: [10.1186/s12864-019-6138-7](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-019-6138-7).
- Yang, Y., J. Zhao, and L. Zeng (2022). "ProTstab2 for prediction of protein thermal stabilities". In: *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 23, p. 10798. DOI: [10.3390/ijms231810798](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms231810798).
- Zhang, G. and B. Fang (2006). "Support vector machine for discrimination of thermophilic and mesophilic proteins based on amino acid composition". In: *Protein and Peptide Letters* 13, pp. 965–970. DOI: [10.2174/092986606778777560](https://doi.org/10.2174/092986606778777560).
- (2007). "LogitBoost classifier for discriminating thermophilic and mesophilic proteins". In: *Journal of Biotechnology* 127, pp. 417–424. DOI: [10.1016/j.jbiotec.2006.07.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiotec.2006.07.020).
- Zhou, X.-X., Y.-B. Wang, and Y.-J. Pan (2008). "Differences in amino acid composition and coupling patterns between mesophilic and thermophilic proteins". In: *Amino Acids* 34, pp. 25–33. DOI: [10.1007/s00726-007-0589-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-007-0589-x).

Chapter 3 - Discriminating HIV-1 broadly neutralizing antibodies via CDR-H3 language model embeddings and perplexity

Authors contribution: As the main author, I was responsible for study design; data acquisition and preparation; models development and training; analysis; drafting the manuscript; critical revision; and final approval of the manuscript. Thomas Lemmin contributed to conceptualization; study design; critical revision; and final approval of the manuscript.

3.1 Introduction

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) is a retrovirus that infects and weakens the immune system, making individuals susceptible to opportunistic infections. Despite the development of Antiretroviral Therapy (ART), the HIV pandemic continues to spread, with approximately 39.9 million people living with HIV worldwide (UNAIDS, 2025). Each year, approximately 1.3 million people contract HIV, and around 630,000 die from related complications. About one-third of those living with HIV are undiagnosed, not receiving care, or not on effective treatment (Landovitz et al., 2023).

Despite decades of research, the quest for a cure or effective prevention strategies for HIV-1 infection continues. Several promising approaches are being explored, including the development of broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAbs) (Thavarajah et al., 2024). bnAbs are a rare and unique class of antibodies that have been isolated from untreated people with HIV (Thavarajah et al., 2024; Landais and Moore, 2018). These antibodies can neutralize a wide range of HIV-1 viral strains by targeting specific regions on the HIV-1 envelope protein, such as the CD4-binding site and variable loops. Although these antibodies were initially discovered for their ability to neutralize free viruses, they can also induce the death of cells expressing the envelope protein (Bruel et al., 2016). This dual capability indicates that they might be more effective than ART, which is unable to eliminate infected cells. Modifications to these antibodies can extend their therapeutic effects for months, making them promising candidates for HIV-1 prevention, treatment, and cure (Thavarajah et al., 2024). However, within the vast antibody repertoire of an individual, bnAbs constitute only a minuscule fraction. Despite extensive research, only a few hundred bnAbs have been identified to date. The challenge lies not only in their rarity but also in the complexity of the immune repertoire.

The advent of next-generation sequencing (NGS) has profoundly transformed immunology, enabling high-throughput profiling of B-cell receptors (BCRs) and generating datasets comprising billions of antibody sequences (Norman et al., 2020; Kenlay et al., 2024; Lees and Shepherd, 2017). Over the years, a variety of computational approaches, such as sequence alignment (Zong et al., 2023), motif detection (Sethna et al., 2019), (Marcou et al., 2017), clonal lineage tracing (Wang et al.,

2023), and structural modeling (Norman et al., 2020; Kenlay et al., 2024), have provided valuable insights into antibody repertoire architecture and evolution. These methods have been instrumental in characterizing somatic hypermutation, inferring antigen specificity, and guiding vaccine design.

However, as antibody repertoire datasets continue to grow in scale and complexity, traditional approaches face inherent limitations in sensitivity, generalizability, and computational scalability. To address these challenges, the field has increasingly turned to machine learning, and more recently, to transformer-based language models specifically tailored to antibody sequences. Specialized models such as AntiBERTy (Ruffolo et al., 2021), AntiBERTa (Leem et al., 2022), IgBert and IgT5 (Kenlay et al., 2024) have been developed to learn complex, context-aware representations of variable regions. Trained on large antibody corpora, these models can capture subtle sequence dependencies and structural motifs that underpin antigen recognition.

This methodological advancement underscores the immense potential for developing specialized computational tools capable of identifying HIV-targeted bnAbs from comprehensive NGS datasets. Such tools are crucial for analyzing entire antibody repertoires from HIV patients, offering vital insights into the natural diversity and dynamics of these antibodies. For example, machine learning frameworks have successfully identified distinct HIV-1 bnAbs targeting the CD4-binding site directly from sequence data, demonstrating their effectiveness in extracting functionally relevant signals (Fogliarini et al., 2024).

In this study, we aim to explore HIV-1 antibody repertoires using Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools. To this end, we developed **H3BERTa**, a transformer-based language model specifically designed for the immunoglobulin heavy-chain third complementarity-determining region (CDR-H3), a key determinant of antigen recognition. The model was pretrained on CDR-H3 sequences derived from B-cell receptors (BCRs) collected from the Observed Antibody Space (OAS) (Olsen et al., 2022), and has demonstrated the ability to learn contextual representations and capture the statistical properties of antibody repertoires.

Building on the robustness of H3BERTa, we explore the development of H3bnAbScan, a classifier designed to identify bnAbs across different binding affinity categories. By leveraging H3BERTa’s learned representations, this approach improves the accuracy and efficiency of bnAb detection, even in data-scarce settings where conventional fine-tuning methods typically underperform. This highlights the potential of language model-based strategies to support antibody discovery and therapeutic development.

3.2 Results

The immunoglobulin heavy-chain third complementarity-determining region (CDR-H3) plays a central role in antigen recognition, serving as the most diverse and functionally critical region of the antibody repertoire. Generated through V(D)J recombination, CDR-H3 often governs binding specificity and affinity. In the context of HIV-1, several potent broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAbs), including PG9 and PG16, feature unusually long CDR-H3 loops that penetrate the dense glycan shield of the viral envelope glycoprotein (Env) to access conserved, otherwise inaccessible epitopes (Jardine et al., 2016; Kwong et al., 2013). While these structural features underpin their broad neutralization capacity, such long and diverse CDR-H3 loops are rare in natural B-cell repertoires, posing a challenge for vaccine elicitation (Kwong et al., 2013; Pejchal et al., 2010;

FIGURE 3.1: Schematic overview of the proposed deep learning framework. (A) CDR-H3 sequences were collected from the Observed Antibody Space (OAS) database, comprising IgG and IgA antibodies from healthy, non-vaccinated donors. Sequences were first clustered using LINCLUST at 70% identity. Centroid sequences were retained, removing those with more than two ambiguous amino acids or CDR-H3 loops shorter than three amino acids. The resulting set was further clustered at 30% identity to ensure sequence diversity. The final dataset was split into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) sets and used to train the H3BERTa model. (B) Semi-supervised adversarial fine-tuning to identify HIV-1 bnAbs. A generator converts random noise into synthetic CDR-H3 loops, while real sequences come from two sources: labelled bnAbs and non-neutralising antibodies respectively in the Los Alamos HIV database and the OAS database, and unlabelled repertoires from Cincinnati Children’s Hospital. All sequences are embedded into the H3BERTa encoder and passed to a discriminator trained jointly to (i) distinguish real from synthetic loops and (ii) classify real loops as broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAb) or non neutralizing antibodies (nnAb). After training, the generator is discarded and the discriminator serves as the bnAb predictor.

Barnes et al., 2018; Yu and Guan, 2014).

To address this, we developed H3BERTa, a transformer-based language model trained on CDR-H3 sequences and designed to learn contextual representations of antibody diversity (Fig. 3.1A). By treating amino acid residues as discrete tokens and CDR-H3 loops as sentences, H3BERTa captures the statistical and functional properties of B-cell repertoires. These embeddings form the foundation of H3bnAbScan, a semi-supervised framework for identifying candidate bnAbs within large-scale B-cell receptor (BCR) datasets (Fig. 3.1B). Together, these tools enable *in silico* exploration of human antibody repertoires, revealing statistically distinct features between healthy and HIV-1-elicited responses, and facilitating the detection of bnAb-like sequences.

3.2.1 H3BERTa

H3BERTa is a transformer-based language model built on a RoBERTa architecture (Liu et al., 2019) with approximately 86 million trainable parameters. The model was pretrained on approximately 18 million sequences derived from the Observed Antibody Space (OAS), filtered specifically for IgG and IgA isotypes from healthy, unvaccinated donors. This isotype selection reflects the biological relevance of IgG and IgA in HIV-1-specific immune responses. IgG antibodies constitute the majority of known broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAbs) (Mahomed, 2024), due to their high serum abundance and potent effector functions. Meanwhile, IgA antibodies play a key role in mucosal immunity, and IgA variants of bnAbs have been shown to enhance neutralization and protection at mucosal surfaces (Jia et al., 2020; Lorin et al., 2022). The inclusion of both isotypes thus provides a comprehensive foundation for understanding humoral responses relevant to both

systemic and mucosal immunity in HIV infection.

The H3BERTa model was trained for 113 epochs until convergence, achieving an evaluation loss of 1.58 on the masked language modeling objective. To further characterize its amino acid predictions and gain a more nuanced understanding of performance beyond sequence identity, we computed pairwise substitution scores using the BLOSUM62 matrix. H3BERTa yielded an average BLOSUM62 score of 2.55 for its predictions. While BLOSUM62 provides a general measure of amino acid similarity, its derivation from conserved protein families means it may not fully account for the unique evolutionary pressures acting on the highly variable CDR-H3 region, which is shaped by somatic hypermutation.

Comparison of CDR-H3 and full heavy chain embeddings

To evaluate whether the CDR-H3 region alone carries sufficient information to capture biologically meaningful repertoire-level patterns, we compared H3BERTa, trained exclusively on CDR-H3 sequences, to AntiBERTa (Choi, 2022), a transformer-based language model pre-trained on full-length heavy chain sequences. This comparison served as a critical validation of our CDR-H3-centric modeling strategy, assessing its capacity to retain relevant immunological differences despite restricting input to the most diverse and antigen-contacting region.

Analysis of learned representations revealed distinct, biologically coherent clustering patterns. UMAP dimensionality reduction of H3BERTa’s embeddings for a subset of antibody sequences demonstrated clustering primarily by J-gene segment (Fig. 3.2 top row). This observation is consistent with the CDR-H3 region’s strong dependence on J-gene usage, which directly influences its length and amino acid composition at the V-D-J junction. In contrast, AntiBERTa’s full heavy chain embeddings, which encompass the entire variable region, exhibited clustering primarily by V-gene segment (Fig. 3.2 bottom row). This distinction aligns with the established role of the V-gene in shaping the overall antibody paratope and its broader influence on the antibody’s structural framework. These findings indicate that while H3BERTa focuses on the specific information encoded within CDR-H3, it captures distinct yet complementary biological signals compared to models trained on full sequences.

Quantitatively, the perplexity scores obtained by H3BERTa and AntiBERTa demonstrated moderate correlation with a Pearson correlation of $r = 0.41$ and a Spearman correlation of $\rho = 0.60$ on a healthy donor repertoire (Fig. B.1). These results collectively indicate that the CDR-H3 region encodes a substantial portion of the immunological signal associated with repertoire-level variation, supporting the utility of a CDR-H3-specific language model for antibody repertoire analysis and the identification of broadly neutralizing antibodies.

Comparison of H3BERTa embedding spaces between bnAb and healthy repertoires

To determine whether H3BERTa’s latent embeddings capture the V(D)J recombination–driven diversity underlying antigen specificity and clonality, we projected CDR-H3 sequences from both a bnAb donor and the same healthy controls used for the previous analysis into the model’s representation space (Fig. B.2). The repertoires were extracted randomly from a larger cohort (Roskin and et al., 2020) that includes patients with chronic HIV as well as HIV-uninfected controls from corresponding geographical regions. Coloring each point by IGHJ usage revealed three conserved “islands” in both repertoires: a prominent IGHJ6 cluster (upper region), an IGHJ4 core (basal region), and a minor satellite corresponding to the IGHJ3 group (rightward region). Marginal

FIGURE 3.2: AntiBERTa and H3BERTa encode complementary germline-gene features in healthy-donor heavy-chain repertoires. UMAP projections of antibody heavy-chain sequences from a representative healthy donor. Left column (AntiBERTa): embeddings computed from the *entire* heavy-chain amino-acid sequence. Right column (H3BERTa): embeddings computed *exclusively* from the CDR-H3 segment of the same sequences. Each point represents one unique heavy chain. Top row—coloured by immunoglobulin heavy-chain *joining* gene (IGHJ). Bottom row—coloured by immunoglobulin heavy-chain *variable* gene (IGHV). Kernel-density ridges along the upper (UMAP1) and right-hand (UMAP2) margins summarise the one-dimensional distribution of each gene. AntiBERTa embeddings separate sequences mainly by IGHV while showing limited IGHJ segregation; H3BERTa shows the converse pattern, yielding compact IGHJ-specific islands and intermixed IGHV signals. These reciprocal patterns highlight how full-sequence versus CDR-H3-focused language models capture distinct yet complementary germline-gene information.

density curves along each UMAP axis overlapped almost perfectly between donors, indicating that the spatial distribution and relative abundance of J-gene segments are dictated by germline-encoded structural constraints rather than by antigen-driven selection (Chi et al., 2020; D’Angelo et al., 2018).

In the lower panels of B.2, the same UMAP projection is recolored by IGHV usage. Both the bnAb donor and the healthy controls display a largely continuous landscape: most V-gene segments produce broad, overlapping peaks of similar height and width across donors. Only IGHV7 in the healthy repertoire stands out as a distinct shoulder at high UMAP-1, suggesting a modest naïve-stage expansion or specialization of that germline. The near-perfect superimposition of V-gene marginal densities confirms that H3BERTa embeddings encode intrinsic biophysical and structural features of IGHV segments, yielding a stable CDR-H3 geometric scaffold that antigen encounters only subtly reshape.

As a control, we also ran PCA and UMAP on CDR-H3 repertoires from five additional bnAb donors and five healthy donors (Fig. B.3), and the same J-gene-defined segmentation recapitulated across all ten datasets as well as the V-gene segmentation (Fig. B.4). PCA—being a linear projection that identifies orthogonal axes of maximal global variance—inevitably blends subtle, germline-driven differences into broad, overlapping clouds of points. By contrast, UMAP builds a high-dimensional k-nearest-neighbor graph and then optimizes a non-linear embedding to preserve local topology, thereby compressing sequences sharing the same germline J segment into tight, well-separated “islands” and stretching apart intermediate regions. This contrast illustrates that the discrete, germline-encoded clusters only emerge clearly when local neighborhood structure is emphasized, as in UMAP, rather than under PCA’s global-variance framework.

Characterization of the immune repertoire using H3BERTa

To investigate whether H3BERTa’s learned representations could distinguish between functionally distinct antibody repertoires, we analyzed the pseudo-perplexity (PPL) values assigned by H3BERTa to CDR-H3 sequences from two patient cohorts: uninfected controls (healthy group) and broadly neutralizing HIV-infected individuals (bnAb group). These samples were drawn from the same study cohort (Roskin and et al., 2020), comprising 4,400,181 sequences from healthy donors and 4,249,699 from the bnAb group. PPL, as a measure of a language model’s uncertainty in predicting sequence elements, serves as an indicator of how well a sequence conforms to the statistical patterns learned during pre-training. Our goal was to determine if differences in these patterns could reflect underlying immunological distinctions between the groups, given that bnAb development is associated with altered immune dynamics.

To quantify global differences in CDR-H3 sequence perplexity distributions, we computed pairwise Wasserstein distances between the H3BERTa-assigned perplexity distributions of individual repertoire samples. The Wasserstein distance, or Earth Mover’s Distance, is particularly well-suited for comparing distribution shapes, including shifts in central tendency and changes in tails.

A hierarchical clustering analysis, using the Wasserstein distance as a similarity metric, revealed a clear separation between the healthy and bnAb groups (Fig. 3.3A). Within the healthy cohort, two highly distinct clusters, each comprising four or five individuals, were observed, clearly separated from other healthy repertoires. The remaining healthy donors formed two additional, less sharply delineated clusters. In the bnAb group, we see a dominant cluster included the majority of bnAb repertoires as well as three healthy donors, indicating some overlap in perplexity profiles. The

FIGURE 3.3: Perplexity landscape of antibody repertoires quantified with H3BERTa. (A) Hierarchical clustering of donor repertoires based on pair-wise Wasserstein distances between their H3BERTa perplexity distributions. Columns and rows correspond to individual repertoires; colour intensity reflects the distance scale shown at left (yellow = similar, purple/black = dissimilar). Side annotation: green, healthy donors; blue, donors who elicited broadly neutralizing antibodies. (B,C) Sequence features of CDR-H3s partitioned into low-, central- and high-perplexity (PPL) thirds (orange, magenta and dark violet, respectively). (B): mean amino-acid frequency in each bin. Low-PPL loops are strongly enriched for aromatic tyrosine (Y), whereas high-PPL loops show elevated levels of hydrophobic leucine (L), basic lysine (K) and conformationally restricted proline (P). (C) box-plots of CDR-H3 length reveal that low-PPL sequences are typically longer (median ~ 17 – 18 aa) than central (~ 15 aa) and high-PPL (~ 14 aa) sequences. Together, these trends indicate that longer, T-rich loops are more predictable for the language model, whereas shorter loops enriched in L/K/P incur higher perplexity, highlighting distinct physicochemical regimes across donor repertoires.

rest of the bnAb donors were more dispersed, forming smaller and heterogeneous clusters.

This suggests lower intra-group variability of healthy repertoires compared to bNAbs, which display more dispersed distances, potentially reflecting higher heterogeneity in their repertoire profiles. Isolated intersections between healthy and bnAb repertoires occasionally produce intermediate-distance values (light orange), indicating partial overlap in perplexity profiles. Indeed, healthy repertoires show the smallest, most tightly clustered distances, indicating a uniform perplexity landscape among B cells (Fig. B.5). bnAb repertoires exhibit larger, more dispersed distances, reflecting varied somatic hypermutation and maturation states. Cross-group distances are substantially higher than either intra-group comparison, demonstrating that H3BERTa effectively distinguishes more naïve patterns from broadly neutralizing repertoires based on their full perplexity profiles (Fig. B.5).

Despite the marked differences observed in intra- and inter-group perplexity distances, the merged perplexity distributions of healthy and bnAb repertoires appear largely superimposable B.6. This overlap is apparent even when zooming into the low-density region, as shown in the inset of B.6. These observations suggest that, although repertoire-level perplexity effectively captures global distinctions—such as overall diversity and maturation trajectories—perplexity values are distributed across a broadly shared range in both groups. Since no clear differences emerged from the overall perplexity distributions, we sought to determine whether group-level differences might instead be concentrated at the distributional extremes. To this end, we investigated the upper and lower tails, defined as values falling outside the 5th–95th percentile range, to assess whether subtle but biologically relevant shifts were masked within the central portion of the distribution.

Tail behavior of the perplexity distributions

Given that the repertoire-level clustering indicated systematic differences, we sought to gain deeper insight into the nature of these distributional distinctions. We investigated whether these differences were more pronounced in the extremes of the perplexity distributions, focusing on the upper and lower tails (values falling outside the 5th–95th percentile range). Notably, the central percentile ranges were nearly identical between the two groups (Healthy: [2.22,16.61]; HIV-1: [2.23,16.41]), suggesting that potential group-specific signals might indeed be concentrated in the distribution tails (Fig. B.6, inset).

To formally assess these differences, we applied the non-parametric Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) test separately to the upper and lower tails. Our analysis revealed highly significant deviations from the null hypothesis in both tails (Upper tail: $\text{stat} = 0.032$, $p = 2 \times 10^{-87}$; Lower tail: $\text{stat} = 0.057$, $p = 3 \times 10^{-254}$). These results provide strong evidence that the two groups differ in the overall distributional shape of extreme perplexity values, with the divergence being particularly pronounced in the lower tail, where HIV-1 sequences appear more frequently associated with unusually low perplexity scores.

To complement the KS analysis, the Mann–Whitney U test was applied to detect potential location shifts in the tail distributions. This test also yielded highly significant results for both tails (Upper tail: $U = 2.41 \times 10^6$, $p = 4 \times 10^{-61}$; Lower tail: $U = 2.18 \times 10^{10}$, $p = 0$), reinforcing the conclusion that the observed differences between groups are primarily driven by the tails rather than the center of the distribution.

Importantly, our analysis of CDR-H3 length and overall amino acid composition across donor groups did not reveal substantial global variations between healthy and bnAb classes (B.7). This

indicates that the observed differences in perplexity distributions, particularly in the tails, are not simply driven by overt compositional or length-based disparities between the patient groups. Instead, these findings underscore the biological relevance of H3BERTa’s PPL scores, which appear to capture more subtle, yet meaningful, biophysical and evolutionary attributes of antibody repertoires that extend beyond simple sequence statistics.

To further characterize the perplexity-defined regions, we analyzed the amino acid composition and CDR-H3 loop length within the Low, Central, and High PPL groups (as defined previously).

Amino acid composition varied systematically across the PPL strata (Figure 3.3B). Loops with Low PPL were strongly enriched in the aromatic residue tyrosine (Y). In contrast, High PPL loops showed a marked increase in hydrophobic leucine (L), along with more moderate enrichments in basic lysine (K) and conformationally restricted proline (P). These compositional shifts indicate distinct biochemical profiles associated with different levels of perplexity.

A clear trend in CDR-H3 loop length was observed across the perplexity-defined groups (3.3C, Figure B.8). Low-PPL sequences were typically the longest (median = 17 – 18 residues), followed by central-PPL (median = 15 residues), and high-PPL sequences, which were the shortest (median = 14 residues) and most compact. Notably, H3BERTa consistently assigned central or high PPL scores to rare ultra-long CDR-H3 sequences; for example, 322 out of 8,649,880 total sequences exceeded 50 amino acids in length, with the longest reaching 77 residues.

To evaluate whether model-derived perplexity correlates with underlying biochemical properties, we analyzed net charge at physiological pH (7.0) and hydrophobicity using the GRAVY (Grand Average of Hydropathy) score. Low-PPL sequences exhibited significantly lower net charge than both Central and High PPL groups (Mann–Whitney U test: Low vs Central: $U = 1.69 \times 10^{12}$, $p = 0$; Low vs High: $U = 5.09 \times 10^{10}$, $p = 0$; Central vs High: $U = 8.12 \times 10^{10}$, $p = 0$), while High-PPL sequences tended to have higher net charge than both other groups (Central vs High: $U = 1.16 \times 10^{12}$, $p < 10^{-10}$) (Figure B.9A). In contrast, GRAVY scores showed only minimal shifts across groups despite statistical significance (e.g., Low vs Central: $U = 1.69 \times 10^{12}$, $p < 10^{-10}$, indicating that hydrophobicity is only weakly associated with perplexity (Fig. B.9B).

3.2.2 Classifier

Having characterized repertoire-level patterns using H3BERTa-derived perplexity and embeddings, we next assessed whether the model could also operate at the single-sequence level. Specifically, we explored whether H3BERTa representations could support the classification of individual CDR-H3 loops according to their HIV-1 binding affinity.

To evaluate H3BERTa’s utility in downstream classification tasks, we curated a labeled dataset for training a classifier to distinguish broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAbs) from non-neutralizing antibodies (nnAbs). This dataset comprised 390 experimentally validated CDR-H3 sequences, with 195 sequences categorized as bnAbs and 195 as nnAbs. The bnAb sequences were sourced from the Los Alamos National Laboratory’s HIV Database (CATNAP) (Yoon and et al., 2015), a curated repository of experimentally validated HIV antibody neutralization data. For the negative class (nnAbs), we included sequences from HIV-infected patients that lacked neutralizing activity, as well as hard negative examples from healthy individuals obtained from the OAS database. The inclusion of these hard negative examples, which possess high sequence similarity to known

bnAbs, was specifically designed to challenge the classifier. Nevertheless, CDR-H3 length distribution of bnAbs exhibit a broader and slightly right-shifted relative to nnAbs, characterized by a higher proportion of longer loops (Figure B.10).

SVM

We trained a linear-kernel Support Vector Machine (SVM) using H3BERTa-derived embeddings as input features. This simple, interpretable model served as an initial probe to test whether the learned representations encode sufficient discriminative information for distinguishing bnAbs from nnAbs at the sequence level.

To assess generalization, model performance was evaluated on both a validation set and an independent test set. On the validation set, the model achieved an overall accuracy of 92% and a macro-averaged F1-score of 0.92, indicating strong and balanced performance across classes.

Class-specific metrics revealed that for the non-neutralizing antibodies (nnAbs), the model attained a precision of 0.86, a perfect recall of 1.00, and an F1-score of 0.92—meaning all nnAbs were correctly identified. For the broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAbs), precision reached 1.00, recall was 0.83, and the F1-score was 0.91. In total, 83.3% of bnAbs were correctly classified, while the remaining 16.7% were misclassified as nnAbs.

On the independent test set, performance remained consistent, with an overall accuracy of 93% and a macro F1-score of 0.92. For the nnAbs class, precision was 0.90, recall was 0.95, and F1-score was 0.93; for the bnAbs, precision was 0.95, recall was 0.90, and F1-score was 0.92. This corresponded to correct classification of 95.0% of nnAbs and 90.0% of bnAbs. Misclassifications were limited, with a slightly higher false negative rate observed for bnAbs (10.0%) compared to false positives in the nnAbs group (5.0%).

Visualization of the decision boundary in the PCA-reduced H3BERTa embedding space showed that most sequences were linearly separable, with only a few misclassifications near the margin (Fig. 3.4).

To evaluate the classifier's performance under more realistic, imbalanced conditions, the H3BERTa-based SVM was applied to a full B cell repertoire from an HIV-infected individual known to produce bnAbs. In this repertoire, where bnAbs typically constitute a very small fraction, the model classified 24% of the sequences as bnAbs. This notably elevated proportion indicates a substantial number of false positive classifications, highlighting that while the classifier can identify bnAb-like sequences, its precision needs improvement for direct application in complex, unselected repertoires.

To assess whether incorporating the full antibody sequence improves classification performance, we trained an SVM classifier using embeddings derived from AntiBERTa on the same curated dataset. On the validation set, the AntiBERTa-based SVM achieved an overall accuracy of 82% and a macro-averaged F1-score of 0.81, showing robust performance in distinguishing between nnAbs and bnAbs. Class-specific metrics were: precision 0.80, recall 0.73, and F1-score 0.76 for nnAbs; and precision 0.83, recall 0.88, and F1-score 0.85 for bnAbs. Specifically, 88.2% of bnAb sequences and 72.7% of nnAb sequences were correctly classified. However, performance dropped considerably on the independent test set, where overall accuracy decreased to 53%. The classification rates for both classes were nearly balanced, with 53.8% of nnAbs and 52.6% of bnAbs correctly

FIGURE 3.4: Decision boundary of a linear SVM trained on H3BERTa embeddings projected onto the first two PCA components. Correctly classified samples are shown in green, while misclassified samples are highlighted in red.

identified. The macro-averaged precision, recall, and F1-score for the test set were all 0.53, indicating substantially reduced discriminative power and a high false positive rate for bnAbs.

Overall, the SVM based on H3BERTa embeddings consistently outperformed the AntiBERTa-based model, achieving higher accuracy and more balanced precision–recall trade-offs across both classes on both the validation and test sets. This suggests that H3BERTa’s CDR-H3 specific representations enable more robust generalization and reliable discrimination for this task.

GAN-BERT

To overcome the limitations of supervised classification with scarce labeled data, we adopted a semi-supervised learning approach based on adversarial fine-tuning. Specifically, we employed GAN-BERT (Croce et al., 2020), a framework that integrates a pre-trained encoder with adversarial training to improve classification performance when labeled examples are limited. In our adaptation, the H3BERTa model replaced the original BERT encoder and was fine-tuned on CDR-H3 sequences from HIV-infected individuals (Figure 3.1B).

The model was trained using a combination of labeled sequences and a large set of unlabeled CDR-H3 loops drawn from antibody repertoires of HIV-infected donors with varying degrees of neutralization breadth, as well as from HIV-uninfected controls. To enhance the proportion of functionally relevant sequences, we filtered for heavy-chain sequences with <85% V gene identity, reflecting extensive somatic hypermutation. Two variants of the unlabeled dataset were tested: one including both HIV-positive and HIV-negative repertoires, and a second excluding the HIV-negative group to focus solely on repertoires from individuals with confirmed or partial neutralization breadth.

Despite the functional differences among these groups, V gene identity distributions were remarkably similar (B.11). Consistently, the best model performance was achieved using the HIV-positive-only dataset, indicating that repertoires from bnAb and nAb donors—even if mostly composed of non-neutralizing sequences—contain sufficient information to support robust fine-tuning of H3BERTa for classification tasks.

Model Performance Following hyperparameter optimization (Methods 3.4), the final GAN-BERT model demonstrated strong classification performance on both the validation and independent test sets.

On the validation set, the model achieved an accuracy of 83.3%, with a precision of 0.80, recall of 0.89, and an F1 score of 0.84. The Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) was 0.67, and the area under the ROC curve (AUC) reached 0.83, indicating good overall discriminative ability. Performance on the independent test set was consistent, with a slightly improved accuracy of 85.0%, precision of 0.79, recall of 0.95, and F1 score of 0.86. The MCC increased to 0.71, and the AUC reached 0.85, confirming the model's ability to generalize beyond the training data. The high recall (0.95) for the nnAb class suggests strong sensitivity, while the relatively high precision (0.79) indicates that false positives remain controlled.

To further assess the model's capacity to identify functionally relevant antibodies, we evaluated its predictions on three HIV-1 antibodies reported in the RAIN study (Fogliolini et al., 2024), including two bnAbs and one weak neutralizer. The model correctly classified all three, assigning classification scores above 0.90, further validating its ability to capture relevant sequence-level signals within CDR-H3.

As with the SVM-based approach, we evaluated the GAN-BERT model on a complete B cell repertoire from an HIV-infected individual known to produce bnAbs (3.4). The model classified 18% of all sequences as bnAbs, suggesting again an elevated false positive rate. However, this represents a clear improvement over the SVM model, which predicted 24% of sequences as bnAbs. These results highlight the advantage of the GAN-BERT approach in improving precision under more realistic, imbalanced conditions. Nonetheless, the remaining rate of false positives underscores the need for additional labeled data or complementary filtering strategies to further enhance specificity in complex repertoire settings.

3.3 Discussion

In this study, we introduced H3BERTa, a transformer-based language model tailored to the CDR-H3 region of antibodies, and demonstrated its ability to capture biologically meaningful features of immune repertoires. By training on over 18 million CDR-H3 sequences derived from healthy human IgG and IgA repertoires, H3BERTa learned a rich representation of antibody language that encodes both structural and evolutionary signals. Building on these contextual embeddings, we introduced H3BERTa-bnAbScan, a semi-supervised framework that navigates HIV-1 B-cell repertoires and flags candidate HIV-1 bnAbs, streamlining in-silico antibody optimization.

Despite the reduced input context, H3BERTa achieved performance comparable to AntiBERTa (Leem et al., 2022) in distinguishing repertoire-level features. This indicates that the CDR-H3 region—though representing only a fraction of the heavy chain—encodes a highly concentrated and informative immunogenetic signal. The ability of H3BERTa to recapitulate repertoire-level distinctions using only CDR-H3 sequences supports the utility of region-focused models in repertoire analysis, particularly in settings where interpretability and sequence resolution are critical.

A key strength of H3BERTa lies in its latent embedding space, which effectively reflects the germline-driven architecture of the antibody repertoire. The model distinguishes major IGHJ gene families as discrete "islands" in the UMAP-projected embedding space, confirming that the model internalizes structural constraints encoded by J-gene usage. Interestingly, this segmentation remains stable across both healthy and HIV-1 bnAb donors, supporting the hypothesis that bnAbs emerge

from pre-existing germline frameworks rather than de novo motifs. (Prabakaran et al., 2014; Jardine et al., 2016). Conversely, IGHV gene usage was distributed more continuously, indicating that while the model captures V-gene-specific features, their representation is less discretely clustered, likely due to broader variability and overlapping sequence characteristics. A similar predominance of J-gene separation over V-gene clustering has been reported previously, underscoring that early recombination events imprint the principal geometric scaffold upon which somatic hypermutation later acts (Davidsen and et al., 2019).

H3BERTa also enables fine-grained comparison of repertoire-level perplexity distributions, offering a unique lens into repertoire diversity and maturation. Despite overall overlap in perplexity profiles between healthy and bnAb repertoires, Wasserstein distance analysis and hierarchical clustering revealed robust group-specific signatures. Healthy repertoires were more homogeneous, while bnAb repertoires exhibited greater variability-potentially reflecting more diverse antigenic experiences or somatic hypermutation trajectories. Notably, these distinctions were most pronounced in the distributional tails, as confirmed by both KS and Mann-Whitney U tests. Specifically, bnAb repertoires were enriched in sequences with unusually low perplexity scores, hinting at functional motifs that the model identifies as canonical or easily “understood”, probably reflecting a model bias toward memory B cells. Crucially, the observed divergences in perplexity distributions were not attributable to overt global differences in CDR-H3 length or amino acid composition between the healthy and bnAb cohorts. This finding highlights H3BERTa’s capacity to detect more subtle, intrinsic sequence characteristics that distinguish these populations, moving beyond simple feature-based analyses.

The association of long, tyrosine-rich loops with low perplexity likely reflects conserved immunogenetic patterns frequently observed in healthy IgG/IgA repertoires, potentially shaped by antigen-driven selection and common structural motifs. Conversely, short loops enriched in leucine, lysine, and proline – with higher perplexity – may represent rarer sequence configurations that deviate from typical repertoire statistics. These may include less functionally selected sequences or repertoires shaped by atypical selection pressures.

Interestingly, electrostatic properties were linked to model uncertainty. Sequences with higher net charge were consistently associated with higher perplexity, suggesting that electrostatics may play a key role in shaping the “surprise” the model experiences when encountering certain motifs. This aligns with prior literature (Ghraichy et al., 2021) indicating that antigen binding and maturation are often accompanied by changes in surface charge and loop flexibility.

In downstream classification, H3BERTa’s embeddings proved effective. The linear SVM classifier achieved high accuracy on a balanced dataset, demonstrating the embeddings’ discriminative power. Notably, the H3BERTa-based SVM consistently outperformed the AntiBERTa-based model, which utilizes full heavy chain embeddings. This superiority underscores the strategic advantage of focusing exclusively on the CDR-H3 region: by concentrating on the most diverse and antigen-contacting part of the antibody, H3BERTa may extract more relevant and less noisy features for neutralization classification compared to models that process the entire heavy chain.

However, the application of this supervised classifier to a full, highly imbalanced B cell repertoire from a bnAb-producing individual highlighted a critical limitation: despite high accuracy on balanced validation sets, the model yielded a substantial proportion of false positives (24% of sequences classified as bnAbs where they are typically rare). This indicates that while effective for distinguishing pre-selected bnAbs, a fully supervised approach struggles with the inherent rarity of bnAbs in real repertoires.

To address this challenge, we transitioned to a GAN-BERT based approach. This deep learning framework effectively leverages the extensive knowledge acquired during H3BERTa's pre-training, allowing for robust fine-tuning even with a restricted labeled dataset. This strategy is particularly well-suited for identifying rare functional sequences in vast unlabeled repertoires, as it capitalizes on H3BERTa's ability to learn complex sequence patterns without extensive manual feature engineering. In this case, we managed to lower the percentage of sequences classified as bnabs to 18%.

Our results show that H3BERTa captures not only structural and germline-defined features of antibody repertoires but also subtle evolutionary and biophysical signals tied to affinity maturation and immune history. This makes it a versatile tool for profiling immune repertoires in health and disease, with promising applications in antibody discovery, vaccine design, and immune monitoring.

Looking ahead, we will test H3BERTa on additional data and evaluate its ability to predict antigen specificity and neutralization breadth from sequence alone. We also plan to expand validate performance in other disease settings, and refine our GAN-BERT approach to enhance specificity for therapeutic antibody screening.

3.4 Materials and Methods

3.4.1 H3BERTa

H3BERTa is a transformer-based language model designed specifically for CDR-H3 loop sequences of B-cell receptors. The model was trained on sequences sourced from the Observed Antibody Space (OAS) database.

Dataset As shown in Fig. 3.1A, the H3BERTa training dataset was constructed by extracting the CDR-H3 sequences from the OAS database (Olsen et al., 2022), specifically selecting entries from healthy human donors with no documented history of vaccination or disease, and including all available B cell sources. IgG and IgA isotype sequences were extracted and CDR-H3 loops were identified using IMGT annotations. To reduce redundancy, the sequences were clustered at 70% identity using MMseqs2 (Hauser et al., 2016), retaining only the cluster centroids. Sequences containing more than two ambiguous amino acids (e.g., 'X') or with CDR-H3 loops shorter than three residues were excluded, resulting in a final dataset of nearly 18 million sequences. The remaining centroids were further clustered at 30% identity to create three distinct splits: training (80%), validation (10%), and testing (10%). To ensure data consistency, all sequences within a 30% identity cluster were assigned to the same split, with larger clusters preferentially allocated to the training set.

Model We used the RoBERTa architecture (Liu et al., 2019) as the base model and conducted an extensive architecture search to explore variations in model depth and complexity. The search involved adjusting the hidden size (from 512 to 768), intermediate size (from 2048 to 3072), the number of attention heads (from 4 to 12), and the number of attention layers (from 4 to 12). This exploration resulted in a range of model sizes, with the number of trainable parameters varying from 16 million to 86 million. The final model configuration features a hidden size of 768, an intermediate size of 3072, 12 attention heads, and 12 attention layers, totaling 86 million parameters. Sequences were tokenized at the amino acid level, with a maximum sequence length fixed at 100

residues.

Training The batch size was set to 1024, and we tested learning rates of $1e-3$, $5e-5$, and $1e-6$, with $5e-5$ emerging as optimal. The training process took approximately one month on a single A100 80G NVIDIA GPU to reach convergence at epoch 113.

Blosum score During the masking objective for each masked position in the sequence, we compared the model’s top prediction to the original amino acid and retrieved the corresponding substitution score from the BLOSUM62 matrix (via Biopython’s `Bio.Align.substitution_matrices` module). If a given amino acid pair was not present in the matrix – for example, due to the presence of non-canonical residues or special tokens like [UNK] – a penalty score of -5 was assigned. The BLOSUM scores were aggregated across all masked positions to obtain an overall measure of prediction quality that accounts for biochemical similarity, rather than exact matches alone.

3.4.2 Classifier

Dataset We compiled our labeled dataset using information from multiple studies available in the Los Alamos National Laboratory’s HIV Database (CATNAP) (Yoon and et al., 2015). Our selection was restricted to human-derived data.

We categorized antibodies into two groups:

- Broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAbs): Antibodies with an average neutralization detection rate exceeding 25%.
- Non-neutralizing antibodies (nnAbs): Antibodies with no detectable neutralization activity.

We retrieved available nucleotide sequences and processed them using the Python package PyIR (Soto et al., 2020), isolating the CDR-H3 based on IMGT annotations. To mitigate initial class imbalance and introduce challenging negative examples, we enriched the nnAbs category by including CDR-H3 sequences from healthy individuals that shared over 70% sequence identity with bnAbs retrieved using `blastp` with the following default parameters `-evaluate 2e-5 -outfmt 6 -word_size 2 -threshold 11 -matrix PAM30 -window_size 40 -comp_based_stats 0`. This resulted in a perfectly balanced dataset comprising 195 sequences per class. To prevent information leakage, we used MMseqs2, specifically the Linclust algorithm with default parameters, to cluster sequences within each antibody category prior to splitting. The resulting clusters were then used to partition the dataset into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) subsets using a standard split strategy. All sequences within a given cluster were assigned to the same dataset split, with larger clusters preferentially allocated to the training set to ensure sufficient representation, while preserving the independence of the validation and test sets. Additionally, each split was randomly shuffled to eliminate potential ordering effects before training and evaluation.

SVM We employed the pretrained H3BERTa model, which was trained on healthy antibody repertoires, as a fixed embeddings extractor. Each input CDR-H3 sequence was tokenized at the single-residue level and fed through the model. To obtain a fixed-length embedding for each sequence, we applied mean pooling over the final hidden states, averaging only over positions

corresponding to valid (non-padded) tokens as indicated by the attention mask. The resulting embeddings, representing contextualized sequence-level features, were subsequently used to train a linear Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier. The classifier was implemented using the scikit-learn library, trained on the designated training set, and evaluated on a held-out test set to assess generalization performance.

GAN-BERT For the detection of bnAbs, we employed the GAN-BERT approach (Croce et al., 2020), an adversarial classifier that combines a pre-trained language model with adversarial training. This method leverages both a small labeled dataset and a larger unlabeled dataset.

Labeled Dataset For the labeled dataset, we used the same annotated data described in 3.4, which was also employed to train and test the SVM classifier.

Unlabeled Dataset Antibody heavy-chain repertoire sequences were obtained from a previously published dataset (Roskin and et al., 2020), comprising 139 individuals with chronic HIV infection (46 with broad neutralization breadth, 50 with limited breadth) and 43 HIV-uninfected controls. Repertoires were labeled according to donor-level neutralization phenotype: bnAbs (broad neutralization), nAbs (limited neutralization), and nnAbs (HIV-negative controls/healthy donors).

Sequences were filtered by V gene germline identity, retaining only those below 85%. Unique CDR-H3 loops were extracted and used as a dataset.

Two configurations of the unlabeled dataset were constructed. In the balanced version, approximately 10,000 sequences from each of the bnAb and nAb groups were combined with 20,000 randomly sampled sequences from the nnAb group. In the HIV-positive-only version, only bnAb and nAb repertoires were included (10,000 sequences per group), assuming the majority of sequences in these repertoires to be non-neutralizing.

Model We implemented a semi-supervised learning model based on the GAN-BERT framework (Croce et al., 2020), utilizing the Hugging Face Transformers library. Our model employs H3BERTa as the language model backbone and integrates a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) consisting of a generator and a discriminator.

The generator (G) is a multilayer feedforward neural network. It takes as input a random vector of size 1000, sampled from a normal distribution, and produces "fake" embedding vectors of dimension 768, matching the dimensionality of the real H3BERTa embeddings. The generator architecture consists of 1 hidden fully connected layer with 768 units, followed by a LeakyReLU activation function (with negative slope 0.01) and a dropout layer with rate 0.1.

The discriminator (D) is a multilayer feedforward neural network that takes as input either a real embedding from H3BERTa (corresponding to a CDR-H3 sequence) or a fake embedding generated by G. Its output is a three-way classification, distinguishing between the nnAbs and bnAbs categories, as well as a third category representing the fake embeddings generated by G. The discriminator architecture consists of 2 fully connected layers with 768 units each, each followed by a LeakyReLU activation and dropout (rate 0.1).

The H3BERTa model was fine-tuned during training. The real embeddings used as input to the discriminator were obtained by passing the CDR-H3 sequences through the H3BERTa model. Both

generator and discriminator were optimized using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $5e-5$ and $\text{epsilon}=1e-8$. The model was trained across 1 GPU without a learning rate scheduler with a warmup proportion of 0.1.

Training We conducted a hyperparameter search to optimize our model's performance. The following hyperparameters were explored:

- Learning rates: 5×10^{-5} and 5×10^{-6} .
- Hidden layers in both the generator and discriminator: 1, 2, and 3 layers.
- Generator input dimensionality (Noise size): 10, 50, 100, 500, and 1000.
- Dropout rate: 0.0, 0.1, 0.2, and 0.3 applied at the output layer of the discriminator.
- Batch size: 16, 32, 64, 128, and 256.

The final model was trained on a shuffled version of the balanced, unlabeled dataset described for the unsupervised objective, and on the labeled dataset introduced for the supervised objective. Sequences were tokenized at the amino acid level, with a maximum sequence length of 100 residues.

Training was conducted using a combination of a generative adversarial loss and a supervised cross-entropy loss applied to the labeled data. The overall loss function was defined as a weighted sum of the GAN loss and the supervised loss.

The optimal configuration—selected based on the lowest validation loss—comprised a batch size of 16, learning rates of $5e-5$ for both the generator and the discriminator, one hidden layer in the generator, two hidden layers in the discriminator, a noise vector size of 1000, and a dropout rate of 0.1. Model training was performed on a single NVIDIA A100 80GB GPU.

3.4.3 Analysis

Single Repertoire Analysis From the same dataset used to train the classifier, we selected the first repertoires in alphabetical order from each class: one from the healthy group (id: 700010496, number of sequences: 104417) and one from the bnAb group (id: 703010564, number of sequences: 83850).

Immune Repertoires Analysis We employed the same unlabeled dataset used for training the GAN-BERT classifier, focusing specifically on uninfected individuals (healthy donors) and HIV-1-infected individuals with confirmed broadly neutralizing antibody (bnAb) responses. The dataset consisted of CDR-H3 immune repertoire sequences from 42 healthy and 46 HIV-1-infected donors. Unlike the classification task, no filtering or preprocessing steps were applied to the sequences prior to analysis. Pseudo-perplexity scores for all CDR-H3 sequences were computed using our H3BERTa model, and the resulting scores were subsequently analyzed to assess repertoire-level differences between the two groups.

PPL To estimate the pseudo-perplexity of individual sequences using a masked language model (MLM) like H3BERTa, we followed the token-by-token masking approach introduced by (Salazar et al., 2020). Given a pre-trained MLM and a target sequence, each non-special token in the sequence was iteratively replaced with the model’s mask token. The masked sequence was then passed through the model to compute the log-probability of the true token at the masked position, conditioned on the rest of the sequence. This process was repeated for all tokens (excluding special tokens), and the final pseudo-perplexity was computed as the exponential of the negative average log-probability:

$$\text{PseudoPerplexity}(x) = \exp \left(-\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log P(x_i | x_{-i}) \right) \quad (3.1)$$

where x_i is the true token at position i , and x_{-i} denotes the sequence with the i th token masked. This method provides a token-level approximation of perplexity suitable for uni bidirectional models. The implementation was performed using PyTorch and HuggingFace Transformers. Gradients were disabled during inference.

References

- Barnes, C. O. et al. (2018). “Structural Characterization of a Highly Potent V3-Glycan Broadly Neutralizing Antibody Bound to Natively Glycosylated HIV-1 Envelope”. In: *Nature Communications* 9.1, p. 1251. DOI: [10.1038/s41467-018-03632-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-03632-y).
- Bruel, T. et al. (2016). “Elimination of HIV-1-Infected Cells by Broadly Neutralizing Antibodies”. In: *Nature Communications* 7, p. 10844. DOI: [10.1038/ncomms10844](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10844).
- Chi, X., Y. Li, and X. Qiu (2020). “V(D)J Recombination, Somatic Hypermutation and Class Switch Recombination of Immunoglobulins: Mechanism and Regulation”. In: *Immunology* 160.3, pp. 233–247. DOI: [10.1111/imm.13176](https://doi.org/10.1111/imm.13176).
- Choi, Y. (2022). “Artificial Intelligence for Antibody Reading Comprehension: AntiBERTa”. In: *Patterns* 3.7, p. 100535. DOI: [10.1016/j.patter.2022.100535](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2022.100535).
- Croce, D., G. Castellucci, and R. Basili (2020). “GAN-BERT: Generative Adversarial Learning for Robust Text Classification with a Bunch of Labeled Examples”. In: *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 2114–2119. DOI: [10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.191](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.191).
- D’Angelo, S. et al. (2018). “Many Routes to an Antibody Heavy-Chain CDR3: Necessary, Yet Insufficient, for Specific Binding”. In: *Frontiers in Immunology* 9, p. 395. DOI: [10.3389/fimmu.2018.00395](https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2018.00395).
- Davidson, K. and et al. (2019). “Deep Generative Models for T Cell Receptor Protein Sequences”. In: *eLife* 8, e46935. DOI: [10.7554/eLife.46935](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.46935).
- Fogliarini, M. et al. (2024). “RAIN: Machine Learning-Based Identification for HIV-1 bNAbs”. In: *Nature Communications* 15.1, p. 5339. DOI: [10.1038/s41467-024-49676-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-49676-1).
- Ghraichy, M. et al. (2021). “Different B Cell Subpopulations Show Distinct Patterns in Their IgH Repertoire Metrics”. In: *eLife* 10, e73111. DOI: [10.7554/eLife.73111](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.73111).
- Hauser, M., M. Steinegger, and J. Söding (2016). “MMseqs software suite for fast and deep clustering and searching of large protein sequence sets”. In: *Bioinformatics* 32, pp. 1323–1330. DOI: [10.1093/bioinformatics/btw006](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btw006).
- Jardine, J. G. et al. (2016). “HIV-1 Broadly Neutralizing Antibody Precursor B Cells Revealed by Germline-Targeting Immunogen”. In: *Science* 351.6280, pp. 1458–1463. DOI: [10.1126/science.aad9195](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aad9195).
- Jia, M. et al. (2020). “VSV-Displayed HIV-1 Envelope Identifies Broadly Neutralizing Antibodies Class-Switched to IgG and IgA”. In: *Cell Host & Microbe* 27.6, 963–975.e5. DOI: [10.1016/j.chom.2020.03.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chom.2020.03.024).
- Kenlay, H. et al. (2024). “Large Scale Paired Antibody Language Models”. In: *PLOS Computational Biology* 20.12, e1012646. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pcbi.1012646](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1012646).

- Kwong, P. D., J. R. Mascola, and G. J. Nabel (2013). "Broadly Neutralizing Antibodies and the Search for an HIV-1 Vaccine: The End of the Beginning". In: *Nature Reviews Immunology* 13.9, pp. 693–701. DOI: [10.1038/nri3516](https://doi.org/10.1038/nri3516).
- Landais, E. and P. L. Moore (2018). "Development of Broadly Neutralizing Antibodies in HIV-1-Infected Elite Neutralizers". In: *Retrovirology* 15.1, p. 61. DOI: [10.1186/s12977-018-0443-0](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12977-018-0443-0).
- Landovitz, R. J., H. Scott, and S. G. Deeks (2023). "Prevention, Treatment and Cure of HIV Infection". In: *Nature Reviews Microbiology* 21.10, pp. 657–670. DOI: [10.1038/s41579-023-00914-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-023-00914-1).
- Leem, J. et al. (2022). "Deciphering the Language of Antibodies Using Self-Supervised Learning". In: *Patterns* 3.7, p. 100513. DOI: [10.1016/j.patter.2022.100513](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2022.100513).
- Lees, W. D. and A. J. Shepherd (2017). "Studying Antibody Repertoires with Next-Generation Sequencing". In: *Methods in Molecular Biology*. Ed. by K. A. Howard and M. H. M. Nielsen. Vol. 1526. Humana Press, pp. 257–270. DOI: [10.1007/978-1-4939-6613-4_15](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-6613-4_15).
- Liu, Y. et al. (2019). "RoBERTa: A Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach". In: *arXiv eprint*: [1907.11692](https://arxiv.org/abs/1907.11692).
- Lorin, V. et al. (2022). "Epitope Convergence of Broadly HIV-1 Neutralizing IgA and IgG Antibody Lineages in a Viremic Controller". In: *Journal of Experimental Medicine* 219.3, e20212045. DOI: [10.1084/jem.20212045](https://doi.org/10.1084/jem.20212045).
- Mahomed, S. (2024). "Broadly Neutralizing Antibodies for HIV Prevention: A Comprehensive Review and Future Perspectives". In: *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* 37.2, e00152–22. DOI: [10.1128/cmr.00152-22](https://doi.org/10.1128/cmr.00152-22).
- Marcou, Q., T. Mora, and A. M. Walczak (2017). *IGoR: A Tool for High-Throughput Immune Repertoire Analysis*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1705.08246. DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.1705.08246](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1705.08246).
- Norman, R. A. et al. (2020). "Computational Approaches to Therapeutic Antibody Design: Established Methods and Emerging Trends". In: *Briefings in Bioinformatics* 21.5, pp. 1549–1567. DOI: [10.1093/bib/bbz095](https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbz095).
- Olsen, T. H., I. H. Moal, and C. M. Deane (2022). "AbLang: An Antibody Language Model for Completing Antibody Sequences". In: *Bioinformatics Advances* 2.1, vbac046. DOI: [10.1093/bioadv/vbac046](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioadv/vbac046).
- Pejchal, R. et al. (2010). "Structure and Function of Broadly Reactive Antibody PG16 Reveal an H3 Subdomain That Mediates Potent Neutralization of HIV-1". In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 107.25, pp. 11483–11488. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.1004600107](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1004600107).
- Prabakaran, P., W. Chen, and D. S. Dimitrov (2014). "The Antibody Germline/Maturation Hypothesis, Elicitation of Broadly Neutralizing Antibodies Against HIV-1 and Cord Blood IgM Repertoires". In: *Frontiers in Immunology* 5, p. 398. DOI: [10.3389/fimmu.2014.00398](https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2014.00398).
- Roskin, K. M. and et al. (2020). "Aberrant B Cell Repertoire Selection Associated with HIV Neutralizing Antibody Breadth". In: *Nature Immunology* 21.2, pp. 199–209. DOI: [10.1038/s41590-019-0581-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41590-019-0581-0).

-
- Ruffolo, J. A., J. J. Gray, and J. Sulam (2021). “Deciphering Antibody Affinity Maturation with Language Models and Weakly Supervised Learning”. In: *arXiv*. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2112.07782](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.07782). arXiv: [2112.07782](https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.07782) [q-bio.BM].
- Salazar, J. et al. (2020). “Masked Language Model Scoring”. In: *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 2699–2712. DOI: [10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.240](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.240).
- Sethna, Z. et al. (2019). “OLGA: Fast Computation of Generation Probabilities of B- and T-Cell Receptor Amino Acid Sequences and Motifs”. In: *Bioinformatics* 35.17, pp. 2974–2981. DOI: [10.1093/bioinformatics/btz035](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz035).
- Soto, C. et al. (2020). “PyIR: a scalable wrapper for processing billions of immunoglobulin and T cell receptor sequences using IgBLAST”. In: *BMC Bioinformatics* 21.1, p. 314. DOI: [10.1186/s12859-020-03649-5](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-020-03649-5).
- Thavarajah, J. J., B. L. Hønge, and C. M. Wejse (2024). “The Use of Broadly Neutralizing Antibodies (bNAbs) in HIV-1 Treatment and Prevention”. In: *Viruses* 16.6, p. 911. DOI: [10.3390/v16060911](https://doi.org/10.3390/v16060911).
- UNAIDS (2025). *Global HIV & AIDS Statistics—Fact Sheet*. <https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/fact-sheet>.
- Wang, K., X. Hu, and J. Zhang (2023). “Fast Clonal Family Inference from Large-Scale B Cell Repertoire Sequencing Data”. In: *Cell Reports Methods* 3.10, p. 100601. DOI: [10.1016/j.crmeth.2023.100601](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crmeth.2023.100601).
- Yoon, H. and et al. (2015). “CATNAP: A Tool to Compile, Analyze and Tally Neutralizing Antibody Panels”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 43.W1, W213–W219. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkv404](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv404).
- Yu, L. and Y. Guan (2014). “Immunologic Basis for Long HCDR3s in Broadly Neutralizing Antibodies Against HIV-1”. In: *Frontiers in Immunology* 5, p. 250. DOI: [10.3389/fimmu.2014.00250](https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2014.00250).
- Zong, F. et al. (2023). “Abalign: A Comprehensive Multiple Sequence Alignment Platform for B-Cell Receptor Immune Repertoires”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 51.W1, W17–W24. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkad400](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad400).

Chapter 4 - Bridging the Chains: A Deep Learning Framework for Heavy-to-Light Antibody Sequence Translation and B Cell Classification

Authors contribution: Lea Brönnimann was responsible for study design; data acquisition and analysis; models development and training; drafting the manuscript; critical revision; and final approval of the manuscript. Thomas Lemmin contributed to conceptualization; study design; drafting the manuscript; critical revision; and final approval of the manuscript. As the third and last author and Lea's mentor, I provided methodological and scientific oversight; study design; assisted with data acquisition and analysis; drafting the manuscript; offered methodological guidance throughout the project; provided critical feedback; and gave final approval of the manuscript.

4.1 Introduction

Antibodies are critical effector molecules of the adaptive immune system, produced by B cells to specifically recognize and neutralize pathogenic threats (Suzuki et al., 2015). The canonical antibody structure consists of two identical heavy chains (HCs) and two identical light chains (LCs), arranged in a characteristic Y-shaped configuration that spatially separates antigen recognition from effector functions (Suzuki et al., 2015; Mirsky et al., 2015). The immense diversity of antibodies arises from precise genetic mechanisms including V(D)J recombination, junctional diversity, and somatic hypermutation (Ralph and Matsen, 2022). Heavy chain construction involves the selection and joining of V, D, and J gene segments with random non-templated nucleotide additions at junctions, while light chain rearrangement follows a similar but simpler VJ process that lacks D genes and involves fewer insertions and deletions (Mirsky et al., 2015; Chiu et al., 2019). Consequently, light chains are significantly less diverse than heavy chains, with heavy chains potentially exceeding light chain diversity by a factor of 10^6 (Nemazee, 2006). This remarkable combinatorial diversity enables recognition of virtually any foreign epitope. Understanding how this diversity is organized and utilized within antibody repertoires is therefore essential for advancing fundamental immunology, rational vaccine design, and the development of engineered therapeutic antibodies with enhanced specificity and reduced immunogenicity (Marks and Deane, 2020; Harris and Cohen, 2024).

The advent of next-generation sequencing (NGS) has revolutionized the study of antibody repertoires, allowing the high-throughput characterization of immune responses at an unprecedented scale (Marks and Deane, 2020). By sequencing the variable regions of both heavy and light chains, researchers can map the diversity and evolution of antibody responses in health and disease. However, NGS generates massive datasets that present significant analytical challenges. While these technologies can efficiently capture sequence information from millions of individual B cells, they typically lose the natural pairing information between heavy and light chains during the sequencing process (Dudzic et al., 2024). This loss of pairing information creates a critical knowledge

gap, as the function and specificity of an antibody critically depend on the correct association of its heavy and light chains. Consequently, computational immunology faces a fundamental challenge: how to accurately reconstruct or predict these essential pairing relationships from sequence data alone. The scale and complexity of antibody repertoire datasets further compound this challenge, necessitating advanced computational approaches that can effectively process and interpret vast amounts of immunological data (Marks and Deane, 2020; Froning, 2017; Novobrantseva, 2005).

Recent advances in deep learning, particularly the emergence of language models, have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in extracting meaningful patterns from large-scale biological datasets (You and Xu, 2024; Graves et al., 2020; Ofer et al., 2021). The application of these models to biological sequences is conceptually grounded in the principle that amino acid sequences encode protein structure and function through positional context and relationships, analogous to how words in sentences convey meaning through order and context (Burbach and Briney, 2024). These models, inspired by natural language processing techniques, have been successfully applied to biological sequences, revealing hidden structures and relationships within repertoires. While studies on protein and antibody language models have shown substantial progress (You and Xu, 2024; Olsen et al., 2022; Ruffolo et al., 2021; Brandes et al., 2022; Kenlay et al., 2024; Wasdin, 2024), there has been limited exploration into the specific task of predicting heavy-light chain pairings and generating one chain given the other (Burbach and Briney, 2024; Guo et al., 2023). This gap is significant because certain heavy chains demonstrate strong preferences for specific light chains, suggesting that the pairing itself can be crucial for developing stable, efficacious therapeutic antibodies (Jayaram et al., 2012; Joshi et al., 2019). It has been observed that many antibody pairs naturally favor cognate heavy/light chain pairing (Joshi et al., 2019) and that randomly paired heavy and light chains often result in autoreactive or non-functional B cell receptors (Novobrantseva, 2005). This preference leads to higher yields of correctly assembled B α IgG, reducing the need for extensive engineering of antibody fragments (Fabs) to achieve desired pairing (Joshi et al., 2019). This simplifies the development process and can improve the therapeutic efficacy of bi-specific antibodies, making targeted treatments more accessible and effective. Heavy and light chain pairing influences antibody structure by affecting the paratope and VH-VL interface (Fernández-Quintero et al., 2021). Additionally, recent investigations demonstrate that memory B cells exhibit a pronounced heavy-light interdependence (Jaffe et al., 2022). In these cells, the usage of an identical heavy chain V gene is closely associated with the preferential selection of a specific light chain V gene, a pattern that is markedly less evident in naive B cells. This suggests that in memory B cells, the heavy chain effectively predicts the optimal light chain, highlighting the role of evolutionary pressures in shaping immune responses.

In this work, we leverage deep learning approaches to address the challenge of heavy-light chain pairing. We develop and evaluate a set of specialized transformer models: HeavyBERTa (RoBERTa-based) for heavy chain sequences, LightGPT (GPT-2-based) for light chain sequences, classification models for predicting B cell developmental states, and a Heavy2Light encoder-decoder architecture that translates heavy chain sequences into corresponding light chains. These models enable us to infer pairing relationships and improve our understanding of repertoire architecture. Our findings provide a framework for applying deep learning to antibody sequence analysis, with implications for both fundamental immunology and therapeutic antibody discovery.

4.2 Results

Understanding heavy-light chain relationships in antibody repertoires requires models that can capture both individual chain characteristics and inter-chain dependencies. However, paired

heavy-light chain sequences are vastly outnumbered by unpaired sequences, with public databases containing billions of unpaired sequences but only a few million paired examples. While it is feasible to train a translation model directly on this paired data, the relatively limited size restricts the capacity of large models to generalize effectively and fully capture repertoire diversity. To address this imbalance and leverage the full extent of available data, we adopted a two-stage modeling strategy. First, we developed two domain-specific language models: HeavyBERTa, based on a masked language modeling (MLM) architecture for heavy chains, and LightGPT, a causal language model for light chains. These models were pre-trained separately on over 2 billion heavy and light chain sequences from the Observed Antibody Space (OAS (Olsen et al., 2022)), restricted to sequences from unsorted B cells, memory B cells, and plasma B cells isolated from peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs). To eliminate potential bias from immune activation, we exclusively used data from healthy human donors with no documented disease or recent vaccination history (Fig. 4.1A and B; Table C.1).

To learn heavy-light pairing relationships, we then combined the pre-trained HeavyBERTa and LightGPT models into an encoder-decoder architecture, Heavy2Light (Fig. 4.1C). The model was fine-tuned using paired antibody sequences drawn from the paired subset of OAS (2 million sequences from healthy human donors without vaccination or disease exposure) and the Patent and Literature Antibody Database (PLAbDab) (Abanades et al., 2024), a self-updating repository containing over 150'000 paired antibody sequences curated from patents and academic literature. Fine-tuning was performed using adapters (Pfeiffer et al., 2020), enabling parameter-efficient training that preserves pre-trained representations while adapting to the pairing task. This approach reduces computational requirements and accelerates training time compared to full model fine-tuning.

We first trained HeavyBERTa using two model sizes in predicting missing residues in the heavy chain sequence through a masking task. Both variants demonstrated robust performance in hidden residue prediction (Supplementary Table C.2). The larger HeavyBERTa configuration achieved marginally superior accuracy (89.12%) compared to the smaller configuration (88.95%) in predicting missing residues in the heavy chain. The LightGPT model exhibited comparable performance in light chain prediction, achieving an accuracy of 86.35%.

Our pre-trained models exhibit a strong capacity to capture biologically meaningful features from antibody chain sequences. To assess the structure of the learned representations, we visualized the output embeddings using t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE). The resulting projections reveal clear clustering by V gene families, despite the absence of any gene family annotations during training. HeavyBERTa (Fig. 4.2A, top) effectively distinguishes heavy chain V gene families, with well-separated, compact clusters and minimal overlap. LightGPT (Fig. 4.2C) similarly captures distinctions among the more numerous light chain families, particularly the clear separation between kappa and lambda loci, though individual V gene family boundaries appear more diffuse. While both t-SNE and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) projections (Supplementary Fig. C.1) were strongly dominated by V gene identity, we sought to evaluate whether the learned embeddings also encode features related to J gene usage. To this end, we applied Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), which revealed clear separability of sequences by J gene segments (Supplementary Fig. C.2). This result indicates that the models capture immunogenetic information beyond V gene signatures, including meaningful distinctions at other genomic loci.

Building upon these observations, we next investigated whether the embeddings have captured the B cell developmental states. The maturation process is a crucial aspect of immune repertoire analysis, where the sequence differences between naive and memory B cells arise from somatic hypermutation and selection during affinity maturation (Meffre et al., 2001). LDA applied to the

FIGURE 4.1: Data processing and training strategy. (A) Data processing pipeline showing the preparation of datasets for the pre-training and fine-tuning of our models. The CDR3 regions (CDRH3 for the HeavyBERTa dataset and CDRL3 for the LightGPT dataset) of unpaired sequences from the OAS (plasma B cells from unsorted samples, memory B cells) are clustered at 100%. Subsequently, the full sequence (heavy or light, for the respective dataset) of resulting centroids are clustered at 70% identity thresholds and allocated based on 50% centroids to create HeavyBERTa and LightGPT datasets. Paired sequences from OAS and PLAbDab are processed similarly with healthy human donor selection and 30% identity-based allocation, resulting in 80% training, 10% testing, and 10% validation splits for the Heavy2Light dataset. (B) Pre-training phase illustrating the training objectives for each model. HeavyBERTa employs bidirectional transformer architecture with masked language modeling on randomly masked heavy chain sequences, while LightGPT uses unidirectional (left-to-right) transformer architecture for autoregressive next-token prediction on light chain sequences. Both models learn sequence representations through their respective self-supervised objectives. (C) Fine-tuning phase demonstrating the encoder-decoder architecture where pre-trained HeavyBERTa (encoder) and LightGPT (decoder) are combined with cross-attention mechanisms and parameter-efficient adapter modules. Only the adapters and cross-attention parameters are trained (highlighted in blue), while the pre-trained model weights remain frozen. This Heavy2Light model translates input heavy chain sequences into corresponding light chain sequences, leveraging the learned representations from both pre-trained components.

embeddings of heavy and light chains showed that both models are able to separate between naive and memory populations (Fig. 4.2B and 4.2D), indicating that the models learned representations that reflect biological differences related to B cell maturation. This inherent ability to differentiate B cell states from sequence alone motivated us to fine-tune the HeavyBERTa and LightGPT models for direct classification of sequences according to their B cell origin. The HeavyBERTa model achieved high classification performance, with an overall accuracy of 92.31% and balanced performance across both naive (F1 score: 0.93) and memory (F1 score: 0.92) classes (Supplementary Table C.3). This suggests the model effectively captures sequence features associated with somatic hypermutation patterns. In contrast, the LightGPT model demonstrated slightly lower performance (overall accuracy: 79.17%), with notably stronger identification of memory B cells (recall: 0.90) than naive B cells (recall: 0.58). This performance disparity may reflect biological differences in mutation rates and selection pressures between chain types during affinity maturation.

We further validated our classification results by examining the heavy-light chain V gene pairing patterns. It has been shown that memory B cells exhibit pronounced heavy-light interdependence, characterized by an enhanced V gene coherence where identical heavy chain V genes preferentially associate with specific light chain V genes (Jaffe et al., 2022). We tested whether this phenomenon would also be observed in previously unlabeled sequences when classified by

FIGURE 4.2: Dimensionality reduction of learned embeddings reveals biologically meaningful clustering patterns. T-SNE visualization of final layer embeddings demonstrates clear clustering of V gene families for both HeavyBERTa (A) and LightGPT (B) models. Each point represents an individual sequence, colored by V gene family assignment (kappa gene families displayed in cool colors and lambda gene families in warm colors), showing the models' ability to capture immunogenetic patterns without explicit supervision. LDA of final layer embeddings effectively separates memory and naive B cell populations for HeavyBERTa (B), as well as LightGPT (D), indicating that the learned representations encode biologically relevant features associated with B cell developmental states. The distinct clustering patterns demonstrate that both models have internalized fundamental immunological principles governing antibody sequence organization.

our HeavyBERTa model. Our results confirmed the expected interdependence phenomenon in memory B cells (Supplementary Table C.4). In the labeled OAS database, memory B cells demonstrated substantially higher V gene coherence (55.82%) compared to naive B cells (13.83%). This pattern was even more pronounced when applying our HeavyBERTa classifier to previously unlabeled sequences from unsorted B cell populations, where sequences classified as memory origin showed 80.57% coherence versus only 5.60% in those classified as naive origin. When combining all data, memory B cells maintained consistently higher coherence (60.63%) than naive B cells (11.90%). These findings validate both the biological phenomenon of enhanced heavy-light chain interdependence in memory B cells and demonstrate that our computational model successfully captures sequence features associated with B cell maturation states that correlate with established pairing preferences.

Given the demonstrated ability of our models to capture biologically meaningful patterns and the observed heavy-light chain interdependencies, we next explored whether these learned representations could be used for sequence generation tasks. To assess the biological validity of our generated light chain sequences, we first evaluated sequences produced unconditionally by the LightGPT model. These sequences exhibited high germline similarity across all antibody regions (Fig. 4.3A). Framework regions consistently showed the highest germline identity, with FR3 reaching 97.39%, FR2 at 96.39%, and FR1 at 95.68%. The complementarity-determining regions displayed somewhat lower but still substantial germline similarity, with CDR2 at 90.00%, CDR3 at 89.34%, and CDR1 at 87.90%. Overall, the unconditioned sequences achieved a full-sequence germline similarity of 95.86% (Supplementary Table C.5). The total mean length of the generated sequences recognized as biologically valid was 80.59 amino acids distributed appropriately across framework and CDR regions. Despite this sequence-level fidelity, structural evaluation revealed limitations in folding quality (Fig. 4.3B). While the generated light chains generally preserved the immunoglobulin fold topology, predicted Template Modeling (pTM) scores ranged from 0.59 to 0.83, indicating considerable variability in confidence. Similarly, predicted Local Distance Difference Test (pLDDT) values revealed structural uncertainty, particularly in the variable loops and certain framework regions.

While the LightGPT model effectively captured light chain sequence pattern—evidenced by high germline similarity—its unconditioned generation approach proved insufficient for producing consistently well-folded structures. This limitation suggested a need for additional biological context to improve structural fidelity. To address this, we explored whether conditioning light chain generation on a given heavy chain could enhance structural coherence by capturing inter-chain dependencies. Building on the strengths of the individual HeavyBERTa and LightGPT models, we developed Heavy2Light, an encoder-decoder architecture that generates light chains conditioned on paired heavy chain sequences, thereby explicitly modeling heavy-light interactions.

The sequence identity between generated and true light chain pairs reveals substantial variation across antibody regions (Fig. 4.4A). Framework regions demonstrated moderate to high similarity, with FR2 achieving the highest mean identity of 74.28%, followed by FR3 at 71.10% and FR1 at 59.43%. The complementarity-determining regions showed lower scores, with CDR2 at 42.37%, CDR3 at 35.81%, and CDR1 at 36.57%. Overall, the model achieved a total sequence identity of 62.00% between generated and true light chain sequences (Table C.6). The mean length of the FWR1 region in the generated light chain sequences is 25.81 amino acids, while CDR1 measures 8.45, FWR2 is 17.04, CDR2 is 3.06, FWR3 is 36.02, and CDR3 is 7.70 amino acids in length. The total length of the generated variable region amounts to 111.26 amino acids (Table C.6), which is

FIGURE 4.3: Characterization of unconditionally generated light chain sequences reveals high germline similarity and proper structural folding. (A) Germline analysis of sequences generated by LightGPT shows high sequence identity across all antibody regions. Violin plots display the distribution of germline similarity percentages for individual framework regions (FR1-3) and complementarity-determining regions (CDR1-3), as well as total sequence identity (top row). Corresponding sequence lengths in amino acids are shown for each region and total sequence length (bottom row), demonstrating that generated sequences maintain biologically realistic proportions. (B) Structural validation of generated light chains through structure prediction. Representative folded structures are colored by predicted Local Distance Difference Test (pLDDT) confidence scores, with corresponding predicted Template Modeling (pTM) scores indicating overall structural quality. The proper immunoglobulin fold topology and high confidence scores demonstrate that unconditionally generated sequences maintain structural integrity consistent with naturally occurring antibody light chains.

FIGURE 4.4: Comparison of conditionally generated light chains with their true paired counterparts reveals distinct pairing patterns and preserved structural integrity across similarity ranges. (A) Sequence identity analysis between Heavy2Light-generated light chains and their corresponding true paired sequences shows variable similarity across antibody regions. Violin plots display the distribution of sequence identity percentages for individual framework regions (FR1-3) and complementarity-determining regions (CDR1-3), as well as total sequence identity (upper panel). Corresponding sequence lengths in amino acids are shown for each region and total sequence length (lower panel), demonstrating maintained structural proportions despite sequence variation. (B) Chain-type specific similarity patterns reveal distinct distributions between kappa and lambda light chains. Violin plots show that kappa chains exhibit a trimodal distribution with distinct peaks at approximately 45%, 70%, and 85% sequence identity, suggesting underlying structural or functional categories that influence predictability. Lambda chains show a more uniform distribution without clear modes, and kappa chains achieve higher average sequence identity (66.03%) compared to lambda chains (54.56%). (C) Structural preservation across similarity ranges demonstrates robust fold conservation through structural superposition analysis. Examples from three similarity classes show generated light chains (orange) aligned with their true paired counterparts (green), illustrating that the Heavy2Light model preserves proper immunoglobulin fold topology even at low sequence similarity (30.97%), indicating successful capture of essential structural constraints for antibody folding.

moderately longer than the average lengths observed in the training and test datasets, measuring 96.41 and 95.64 amino acids, respectively. Nevertheless, the lengths of the individual framework and complementarity-determining regions remain consistent with those found in the original datasets, Table C.7).

The sequence identity distributions show distinct chain-type specific patterns (Fig. 4.4B). Kappa light chains exhibited a trimodal distribution with peaks at approximately 45%, 70%, and 85% sequence identity, suggesting underlying structural or functional categories that influence pairing predictability. Lambda chains also exhibited three modes, although the dominant peak was centered around 45%, with fewer sequences reaching higher identity levels. On average, Kappa chains achieved higher sequence identity (66.03%) compared to lambda chains (54.56%), indicating stronger pairing constraints and more predictable sequence relationships in the kappa chain repertoire. To investigate whether these patterns could be attributed to V gene family usage, we analyzed the distribution of kappa V gene families across identity ranges. Although IGKV1 was overrepresented, this alone did not explain the trimodal distribution (Supplementary Fig. C.3), suggesting that more complex sequence–structure relationships underlie the observed trends. The Heavy2Light model generated 19'649 unique sequences from a test set of 58'839 sequences, representing 44.23% of the 44,421 unique true light sequences present in the test set. This relatively limited diversity of generated sequences represents a notable limitation of the current model. The IGKV1 gene family was overrepresented in the generated light sequences, accounting for 50.37% of generated sequences which occur at least 100 times in the dataset, followed by IGKV3 (23.00%) and IGKV2 (9.81%) (Supplementary Fig. C.4A). This dominance of IGKV1 was maintained across the complete set of generated sequences (39.35%), though with increased representation of IGKV3 (25.31%, Supplementary Fig. C.4B). IGKV1 was also the most prevalent gene family in both the true light chains of the test set (45.03%) and training set (30.58%), while IGKV3 represented the second most common family with 15.07% and 26.33%, respectively (Supplementary Fig. C.4 B and C).

Despite only moderate sequence similarities, structural evaluation demonstrated strong preservation of immunoglobulin fold (Fig. 4.4C). Structural superposition analyses across three representative similarity classes showed that generated light chains aligned well with their true paired counterparts, maintaining correct fold topology even at low sequence similarity (as low as 30.97%). These results suggest that the Heavy2Light model successfully captures essential structural constraints for antibody folding, prioritizing functional fold preservation over exact sequence reproduction. The robust structural conservation across varied sequence similarities demonstrates the model's ability to generate light chains that maintain the fundamental immunoglobulin framework while accommodating the natural diversity inherent in antibody pairing relationships.

To evaluate the biological compatibility of generated light chains with their corresponding heavy chain inputs, we used ImmunoMatch (Guo et al., 2023), a protein language model that estimates the pairing probability between antibody chains. Generated sequences achieved a mean pairing probability score of 0.4291, with 44.25% exceeding the threshold of 0.5, indicating that nearly half of the generated light chains are predicted to be strongly compatible with their corresponding heavy chains (Supplementary Fig. C.5A). This supports the model's ability to generate not only structurally plausible but also biologically relevant chain pairings. Notably, there was no correlation between the similarity score of the generated light sequence to the true light sequence and its pairing score (Supplementary Fig. C.5B). Some generated sequences with high similarity to the reference light chain were not predicted to pair well with the heavy chain, while conversely, some light chain sequences with low sequence recovery were still predicted to have favorable pairing compatibility.

FIGURE 4.5: Characterization of conditionally generated light chain sequences demonstrates enhanced structural quality. (A) Germline analysis of light chain sequences generated by the Heavy2Light model conditioned on paired heavy chain input shows high sequence identity across all antibody regions. Violin plots display the distribution of germline similarity percentages for individual framework regions (FR1-3) and complementarity-determining regions (CDR1-3), as well as total sequence identity (top row). Corresponding sequence lengths in amino acids are shown for each region and total sequence length (bottom row), demonstrating that conditioned generation produces sequences with biologically realistic proportions and enhanced structural completeness compared to unconditioned generation. (B) Structural validation of conditionally generated light chains through structure prediction. Representative folded structures are colored by predicted Local Distance Difference Test (pLDDT) confidence scores, with corresponding predicted Template Modeling (pTM) scores indicating overall structural quality. The improved pTM scores and proper immunoglobulin fold topology demonstrate that conditioning on paired heavy chains guides the model toward generating light chains with superior structural integrity and enhanced folding confidence compared to unconditioned generation.

The conditioning strategy implemented in the Heavy2Light model not only strengthened sequence–structure relationships but also improved the biological plausibility of the generated light chains. When conditioned on a paired heavy chain, the model produced light chains with high germline similarity across all antibody regions (Fig. 4.5A). Framework regions retained high germline identity, with FR3 achieving 96.23%, FR2 at 96.23%, and FR1 at 93.49%. The complementarity-determining regions displayed moderate germline similarity, with CDR3 at 90.09%, CDR2 at 90.33%, and CDR1 at 83.55%. Overall, conditionally generated sequences achieved a total germline similarity of 93.68%, demonstrating that heavy chain conditioning preserved the fundamental immunogenetic patterns while allowing for appropriate variability in the CDR regions.

Notably, the Heavy2Light model produced sequences with enhanced structural completeness compared to unconditioned generation. The total sequence length increased to a mean of 96.80 amino acids, representing a substantial improvement over the 80.59 amino acids observed in unconditioned sequences. This extension was distributed across multiple regions, with particularly notable increases in FR1 (25.61 vs. 20.84 amino acids), FR3 (36.00 vs. 32.21 amino acids), and CDR1 (7.79 vs. 6.87 amino acids), while maintaining the highly constrained CDR2 length (3.02 amino acids in both approaches). The germline similarities as well as the mean lengths of each region and in total are similar to the distributions of sequence identity and mean lengths of the training and test set (Fig. C.6).

Structural validation showed improved folding quality for Heavy2Light-generated sequences (Fig. 4.5B). The conditionally generated sequences achieved pTM scores ranging from 0.94 to 0.95, compared to the more variable performance (0.59 – 0.83) of unconditioned generation. The pLDDT confidence scores suggest better structural predictions with more high-confidence regions (>90). These findings suggest that conditioning light chain generation on the heavy chain context provides critical structural guidance, enabling the model to produce more complete and fold-consistent antibody sequences.

4.3 Discussion

Recent advances in deep learning have opened new avenues for interpreting the immense diversity and complexity of the adaptive immune repertoire. In this study, we leveraged transformer-based language models to explore a longstanding challenge in immunology and protein engineering: understanding and predicting the relationships between antibody heavy and light chains. Our two-pronged approach by first pre-training HeavyBERTa and LightGPT on large-scale, unpaired sequences, then fine-tuning them on paired antibody datasets, illustrates the capacity of modern sequence models to learn rich, immunologically meaningful representations that generalize to multiple tasks.

Our fine-tuned models accurately classified antibody sequences by B cell developmental origin, solely from sequence data. HeavyBERTa achieved a high accuracy of 92.31%, while LightGPT performed moderately well with 79.17% accuracy. The higher performance for heavy chains likely stems from their greater sequence variability due to VDJ recombination, junctional diversity, and D-segment usage (Mirsky et al., 2015; Ralph and Matsen, 2022; Chiu et al., 2019), which collectively provide a richer discriminative signal for classification. The biological validity of this classification was reinforced through V gene coherence analysis, which confirmed well-established patterns of heavy-light interdependence in memory B cells (Jaffe et al., 2022). Notably, sequences classified by HeavyBERTa exhibited even stronger coherence than the original annotated datasets, suggesting that the model captures key maturation-related features. However,

variability in dataset composition, especially the underrepresentation of naive B cells in the OAS database (Dudzic et al., 2024; Olsen et al., 2022), may limit the generalizability of these findings and warrants further investigation across more balanced repertoires.

The Heavy2Light model was able to generate light chains with a moderate overall sequence identity of 62% compared to their native pairs. Although only 44.25% of generated sequences surpassed the ImmunoMatch pairing probability threshold, this still indicates that a substantial proportion of outputs achieve biologically plausible pairing. The surprisingly weak correlation between sequence recovery of generated versus actual light chains and ImmunoMatch pairing scores presents an intriguing paradox that warrants further investigation. This phenomenon manifests as a subset of predicted sequences with high pairing probability despite low sequence recovery, and conversely, sequences with high sequence recovery but low predicted pairing likelihood. A plausible explanation for this apparent discrepancy potentially lies in the selective preservation of functionally critical sequence determinants. Generated light chains with high pairing scores but low sequence similarity may have successfully captured essential structural features required for heavy-light chain interaction while introducing numerous non-critical sequence variations. This hypothesis is supported by a previous study (Chailyan et al., 2011) demonstrating that specific amino acid residues at defined positions within antibody variable domains serve as key determinants for two distinct modes of heavy-light chain variable domain interaction. If computationally generated light chains preserve these critical amino acid signatures characteristic of either interaction mode, we hypothesize that they would be correctly identified as compatible pairings despite exhibiting substantial sequence divergence from their native counterparts.

Importantly, conditioning on the heavy chain significantly improved the structural and biological realism of generated light chains. Conditioned sequences not only displayed high germline similarity (93.68%) but also showed longer, more complete antibody regions—reflecting improved coverage of framework and CDR segments. Structural prediction metrics further confirmed these gains, with conditioned sequences achieving consistently high pTM and pLDDT scores, indicating better foldability and confidence in modeled structures. These findings suggest that the Heavy2Light model captures relevant inter-chain dependencies that help guide productive antibody folding, even in cases where primary sequence similarity is modest.

One of the most unexpected findings was the trimodal distribution of sequence similarity in generated kappa light chains. While V gene usage bias did not account for this phenomenon (Fig. C.3), we hypothesize that these multimodal distributions may reflect underappreciated biological organization within the light chain repertoire and merit further investigation. We propose that this trimodal pattern corresponds to distinct functional categories within the kappa repertoire, each presenting different challenges for sequence prediction. The low similarity mode may represent highly promiscuous light chains, those capable of pairing with multiple heavy chains, which are predominantly public sequences with minimal non-templated bases (DeKosky et al., 2015). This interpretation is supported by the inherent difficulty in predicting a single "correct" light chain when a given heavy chain can functionally pair with multiple diverse light chains. Conversely, higher similarity modes may correspond to more specialized pairing relationships, such as light chains with restricted pairing specificity or antigen-driven variants that have co-evolved with their cognate heavy chains to optimize specific paratope configurations. This interpretation suggests that the trimodal distribution reflects a spectrum from highly promiscuous, broadly compatible light chains to increasingly specialized, co-evolved heavy-light chain pairings.

The dominant low-identity mode observed for lambda chains aligns with previous findings that lambda light chains exhibit greater structural flexibility, particularly due to a longer and more diverse CDR-L3 region (Van Der Kant et al., 2019). This expanded conformational and sequence

space might increase the difficulty of accurate sequence prediction. Additionally, the VL–VH interface is less stabilized in lambda compared to kappa chains (Van Der Kant et al., 2019). The kappa light chain variable domain forms a well-defined and conserved interaction network with the heavy chain, characterized by stabilizing structural features at the interface. In contrast, the lambda light chain engages in more variable and distributed contacts (Van Der Kant et al., 2019). This less stereotyped pairing in lambda chains potentially further complicates inference of the light chain sequence from the heavy chain context.

Our results contribute to an emerging paradigm in which antibody sequence modeling is not limited to classification or annotation, but extends into generative biology—where models propose novel, yet biologically grounded, sequences. While our pairing success rate (44% passing ImmunoMatch threshold) indicates room for improvement, it is notable given the complexity and degeneracy of antibody pairing rules. Unlike prior work that relies heavily on template grafting or structure-aware refinement, our sequence-only approach achieves meaningful biological outputs from paired data alone. This has important implications for repertoire engineering, especially in contexts where structural or antigen data are scarce.

While promising, our study also highlights areas for future improvement. Enhancing pairing accuracy will likely require integrating more diverse and experimentally validated datasets, incorporating structural constraints during training, and exploring alternative generative architectures (e.g., diffusion models or autoregressive transformers with contrastive objectives). In parallel, expanding analyses to include functional outputs such as antigen specificity, neutralization potency, or epitope targeting would extend the translational utility of these models. Moreover, the application of such models to infer repertoire dynamics in health and disease offers a powerful avenue for systems immunology.

Altogether, this work underscores the feasibility of using deep learning to model the complex sequence relationships underlying antibody generation and maturation. By combining discriminative and generative modeling approaches, we demonstrate how transformer-based architectures can reveal immunological insights and enable context-aware design of antibody sequences, setting the stage for data-driven advances in immunotherapy, vaccine design, and synthetic immunology.

4.4 Methods

4.4.1 Models

We pre-trained two antibody-specific language models based on the transformer (Wolf et al., 2020) architecture: HeavyBERTa for heavy chain sequences and LightGPT for light chain sequences. For HeavyBERTa, we implemented two RoBERTa-based configurations to evaluate the impact of model size on performance. The small configuration featured a hidden size of 512, an intermediate size of 2048, 4 attention heads, and 4 transformer layers, totaling approximately 13.15 million parameters. We then scaled up to a larger configuration with a hidden size of 768, an intermediate size of 3072, 12 attention heads, and 12 transformer layers, resulting in approximately 86.06 million parameters. For LightGPT, we used a GPT-2 architecture with a hidden size of 768, 12 attention heads, and 12 transformer layers, totaling approximately 85.86 million parameters. Both architectures utilized a vocabulary of 25 tokens, comprising 20 standard amino acids plus 5 special tokens. For downstream applications, we employed parameter-efficient fine-tuning using bottleneck adapters (Pfeiffer et al., 2020) with multi-head and output adapter configurations enabled. The adapters utilized a reduction factor of 16 and Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) as activation

function (Supplementary Table C.8). The Heavy2Light encoder-decoder model combined the pre-trained HeavyBERTa (encoder) and LightGPT (decoder) architectures with cross-attention mechanisms, where only adapter modules and cross-attention parameters remained trainable while pre-trained weights were frozen (Fig. 4.1). Similarly, for the classification of heavy and light chain sequences into naive or memory B cell states, we fine-tuned the respective pre-trained models (HeavyBERTa for heavy chains, LightGPT for light chains) using the same adapter configuration, adding classification heads while keeping the base model parameters frozen.

4.4.2 Data preparation

All models were trained using data from the Observed Antibody Space (OAS (Olsen et al., 2022)). Additionally, paired data from the Patent and Literature Antibody Database (PLAbDab (Abanades et al., 2024)) was used for the Heavy2Light fine-tuning dataset. Four different datasets were created: a heavy chain dataset for HeavyBERTa pre-training, a light chain dataset for LightGPT pre-training, a paired sequences dataset for Heavy2Light fine-tuning and another paired dataset for the b cell classification.

4.4.3 Pre-training datasets for HeavyBERTa and LightGPT

For the HeavyBERTa and LightGPT pre-training datasets, unsorted B cells from peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs), memory B cells, and plasma B cells were selected. For the OAS data, we selected only sequences from healthy donors without disease or vaccination history. Additionally, we incorporated all available paired sequences from the PLaBdab database. To reduce sequence redundancy and ensure proper data splits, we implemented a hierarchical clustering strategy for the pre-training datasets. First, CDR3 sequences (CDRH3 for heavy chains, CDRL3 for light chains) from the OAS database were clustered at 100% sequence identity using MMseqs2's linclust module (version 13.45111) (Steinegger and Söding, 2017). The centroids from these clusters were then used to extract full-length heavy or light chain sequences, which were subsequently clustered at 70% sequence identity. These 70% identity clusters formed the basis of our training datasets. To prevent highly similar sequences from appearing in both training and test sets, we performed an additional clustering step at 50% sequence identity and allocated sequences to training, validation, and test datasets based on clusters rather than random assignment. This approach ensures that sequences within the same 50% identity cluster remain together in the same dataset split, thereby preventing data leakage and providing more robust model evaluation.

4.4.4 Fine-tuning dataset for Heavy2Light

For the Heavy2Light fine-tuning dataset, we combined paired sequences from both OAS (human, healthy donors without vaccination or disease) and PLaBdab databases. After duplicate removal, the paired sequences were clustered at 30% sequence identity for allocation into training (80%), testing (10%), and validation (10%) splits, following the same cluster-based allocation strategy to maintain sequence independence across datasets.

4.4.5 Fine-tuning dataset for naive/memory B cell classification

Fine-tuning dataset for naive/memory B cell classification To construct a balanced and non-redundant dataset of naive and memory B-cell receptor sequences, we started with all the paired data sequences available from OAS. For each antibody chain (heavy and light) separately, we extracted the aligned amino acid sequences and filtered them to retain unique entries. To balance the dataset, we randomly sampled an equal number of Naive and Memory B-cell sequences, using

the smaller of the two class sizes as reference. To minimize sequence redundancy across data splits, we clustered the sequences using `linclust` with default parameters, processing heavy and light chains separately. Clustering information was then used to perform non-overlapping train, validation, and test splits: all sequences from the same cluster were assigned to the same subset. This strategy mitigates information leakage across splits. The final dataset was divided into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) sets, with larger clusters preferentially assigned to the training set.

4.4.6 Pre-training and fine-tuning

HeavyBERTa pre-training

Two RoBERTa-based configurations were pre-trained on unpaired heavy chain sequences using masked language modeling. Both models were trained with identical hyperparameters: a learning rate of $5e-5$, weight decay of 0.1, batch size of 16, and the AdamW optimizer with linear learning rate scheduling. The small configuration (4 layers, 512 hidden size) was trained for 22 epochs over 136,254,500 training steps, requiring approximately 244 hours of computation. The large configuration (12 layers, 768 hidden size) was trained for 9.18 epochs over 56,832,000 training steps, requiring approximately 673 hours (for more information, see Supplementary Table C.9).

LightGPT pre-training

The GPT-2-based model was pre-trained on unpaired light chain sequences using autoregressive language modeling. Training was conducted for 83 epochs over 12,265,000 steps with a batch size of 16, learning rate of $5e-5$, weight decay of 0.1, and AdamW optimization with linear scheduling. The model required approximately 606 hours of training time (Supplementary Table C.10).

Fine-tuning Heavy2Light encoder-decoder model

The Heavy2Light translation model was fine-tuned using parameter-efficient adapter-based training, combining the pre-trained HeavyBERTa encoder (small configuration) with the LightGPT decoder in an encoder-decoder architecture. Training was conducted for 50 epochs with a batch size of 64, learning rate of $1e-5$, weight decay of 0.1, and gradient clipping with a maximum norm of 1.0. We used AdamW as optimizer with linear learning rate scheduling. For sequence generation, nucleus sampling was implemented with a top-p value of 0.85, temperature of 0.8, and top-k disabled (set to 0). Generation length was constrained with a maximum of 115 new tokens. The model was trained for 367,750 steps over approximately 34.9 hours (Supplementary Table C.8).

Classification model fine-tuning

Classification models for naive/memory B cell prediction were fine-tuned using the same adapter-based approach on their respective pre-trained base models. The HeavyBERTa classifier was trained for 200 epochs with a learning rate of $3e-6$, batch size of 64, maximum sequence length of 150, and dropout rate of 0.1. The LightGPT classifier was trained for 50 epochs with an identical learning rate and batch size but with a higher dropout rate of 0.3. Both models utilized AdamW optimization with weight decay of 0.01 and maintained frozen base model parameters while training only the adapter modules and classification heads (Supplementary Table C.11).

4.4.7 Evaluation

The generated light sequences were evaluated using global alignment-based percentage similarity. The alignment of the generated and true sequences was done with global alignment (Needleman-Wunsch), with a gap opening penalty of -10 and a gap extension penalty of -4. Chai-1 (Boitreaud et al., 2024) was used for protein structure predictions of the generated and true light chains. The generated and corresponding true light chain was aligned, superimposed and visualised using ChimeraX (Meng et al., 2023). All dimensionality reduction visualizations were generated with the following parameters and configurations. Embeddings were extracted from the final hidden layer of each pre-trained model using mean pooling across sequence positions. PCA, t-SNE, and LDA were performed using scikit-learn (version 1.5.1). T-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) was applied with a perplexity of 30. PyIR (Soto et al., 2020), a wrapper for the IgBLAST (Ye et al., 2013) immunoglobulin and T-cell analyser, was used to calculate the percent identity to the germline.

4.4.8 Pairing compatibility assessment using ImmunoMatch

To evaluate the biological compatibility of generated light chains with their corresponding heavy chain inputs, we employed the ImmunoMatch (Guo et al., 2023) classification model to assess pairing probabilities between the generated light chains and their corresponding heavy chain inputs. Before the classification, the duplicates were removed, and the sequences were trimmed using PyIR (Soto et al., 2020) to standardize the antibody variable regions and remove any extraneous sequences outside the canonical antibody framework. The classification was performed on the final dataset of unique, trimmed sequences to evaluate how well the Heavy2Light model captures biologically relevant heavy-light chain pairing relationships.

4.4.9 Heavy-light chain V gene coherence

To investigate heavy-light chain interdependence patterns, we analyzed paired sequences from the OAS database. We grouped heavy chains based on their CDRH3 regions and their V gene. We then removed all groups containing only single entries and excluded groups consisting of sequences from only one patient (Jaffe et al., 2022). For coherence calculation, we applied our trained HeavyBERTa classifier to predict B cell origin (naive or memory) for heavy chain sequences in paired datasets. For each group containing more than one sequence and originating from different patients, we determined whether the light chain V gene was identical across all sequences sharing the same heavy chain V gene. Coherence was calculated as the fraction of groups showing identical light chain V gene usage within each predicted B cell category.

4.4.10 Hardware and software

All models were trained using the HuggingFace Transformers Library (version 4.40.2) (Wolf et al., 2020). We used the Adapters (version 1.0.0.dev0) (Pfeiffer et al., 2020) library for the encoder-decoder models to facilitate modular fine-tuning. We used the PyTorch backend (version 2.3.1) (Paszke et al., 2019) for both the HuggingFace Transformers Library and the Adapters library. Pre-training and fine-tuning were conducted on NVIDIA A100 or H100 Tensor Core GPUs (each with 80GB of RAM), depending on availability.

References

- Abanades, B. et al. (2024). “The Patent and Literature Antibody Database (PLAbDab): an evolving reference set of functionally diverse, literature-annotated antibody sequences and structures”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 52.D1, pp. D545–D551. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkad1056](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad1056).
- Boitreaud, J. et al. (2024). “Chai-1: Decoding the Molecular Interactions of Life”. In: *bioRxiv*. Preprint. DOI: [10.1101/2024.10.10.615955](https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.10.10.615955).
- Brandes, N. et al. (2022). “ProteinBERT: A Universal Deep-Learning Model of Protein Sequence and Function”. In: *Bioinformatics* 38.8, pp. 2102–2110. DOI: [10.1093/bioinformatics/btac020](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btac020).
- Burbach, S. M. and B. Briney (2024). “Improving Antibody Language Models with Native Pairing”. In: *Patterns* 5.5, p. 100967. DOI: [10.1016/j.patter.2024.100967](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2024.100967).
- Chailyan, A., P. Marcatili, and A. Tramontano (2011). “The Association of Heavy and Light Chain Variable Domains in Antibodies: Implications for Antigen Specificity”. In: *FEBS Journal* 278.16, pp. 2858–2866. DOI: [10.1111/j.1742-4658.2011.08207.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-4658.2011.08207.x).
- Chiu, M. L. et al. (2019). “Antibody Structure and Function: The Basis for Engineering Therapeutics”. In: *Antibodies* 8.4, p. 55. DOI: [10.3390/antib8040055](https://doi.org/10.3390/antib8040055).
- DeKosky, B. J. et al. (2015). “In-depth determination and analysis of the human paired heavy- and light-chain antibody repertoire”. In: *Nature Medicine* 21.1, pp. 86–91. DOI: [10.1038/nm.3743](https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.3743).
- Dudzic, P. et al. (2024). “Conserved Heavy/Light Contacts and Germline Preferences Revealed by a Large-Scale Analysis of Natively Paired Human Antibody Sequences and Structural Data”. In: *bioRxiv*. Preprint, version 3. DOI: [10.1101/2024.12.20.629642](https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.20.629642).
- Fernández-Quintero, M. L. et al. (2021). “Germline-Dependent Antibody Paratope States and Pairing Specific VH-VL Interface Dynamics”. In: *Frontiers in Immunology* 12, p. 675655. DOI: [10.3389/fimmu.2021.675655](https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.675655).
- Froning, K. J. (2017). “Computational Design of a Specific Heavy Chain/K Light Chain Interface for Expressing Fully IgG Bispecific Antibodies”. In: *Protein Science* 26.10, pp. 2021–2038. DOI: [10.1002/pro.3240](https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.3240).
- Graves, J. et al. (2020). “A Review of Deep Learning Methods for Antibodies”. In: *Antibodies* 9.2, p. 12. DOI: [10.3390/antib9020012](https://doi.org/10.3390/antib9020012).
- Guo, Z. et al. (2023). “Diffusion Models in Bioinformatics and Computational Biology”. In: *Nature Reviews Bioengineering* 2.2, pp. 136–154. DOI: [10.1038/s44222-023-00114-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s44222-023-00114-9).
- Harris, C. T. and S. Cohen (2024). “Reducing Immunogenicity by Design: Approaches to Minimize Immunogenicity of Monoclonal Antibodies”. In: *BioDrugs* 38.2, pp. 205–226. DOI: [10.1007/s40259-023-00641-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40259-023-00641-2).
- Jaffe, D. B. et al. (2022). “Functional antibodies exhibit light chain coherence”. In: *Nature* 611.7935, pp. 352–357. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-022-05371-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05371-z).

- Jayaram, N., P. Bhowmick, and A. C. R. Martin (2012). “Germline VH/VL pairing in antibodies”. In: *Protein Engineering, Design and Selection* 25.10, pp. 523–529. DOI: [10.1093/protein/gzs043](https://doi.org/10.1093/protein/gzs043).
- Joshi, K. K. et al. (2019). “Elucidating heavy/light chain pairing preferences to facilitate the assembly of bispecific IgG in single cells”. In: *mAbs* 11.7, pp. 1254–1265. DOI: [10.1080/19420862.2019.1640549](https://doi.org/10.1080/19420862.2019.1640549).
- Kenlay, H. et al. (2024). “Large Scale Paired Antibody Language Models”. In: *PLOS Computational Biology* 20.12, e1012646. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pcbi.1012646](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1012646).
- Marks, C. and C. M. Deane (2020). “How Repertoire Data Are Changing Antibody Science”. In: *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 295.29, pp. 9823–9837. DOI: [10.1074/jbc.REV120.010181](https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.REV120.010181).
- Meffre, E. et al. (2001). “Somatic Hypermutation Shapes the Antibody Repertoire of Memory B Cells in Humans”. In: *Journal of Experimental Medicine* 194.3, pp. 375–378. DOI: [10.1084/jem.194.3.375](https://doi.org/10.1084/jem.194.3.375).
- Meng, E. C. et al. (2023). “UCSF ChimeraX: Tools for structure building and analysis”. In: *Protein Science* 32.11, e4792. DOI: [10.1002/pro.4792](https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.4792).
- Mirsky, A., L. Kazandjian, and M. Anisimova (2015). “Antibody-Specific Model of Amino Acid Substitution for Immunological Inferences from Alignments of Antibody Sequences”. In: *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 32.3, pp. 806–819. DOI: [10.1093/molbev/msu340](https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msu340).
- Nemazee, D. (2006). “Receptor Editing in Lymphocyte Development and Central Tolerance”. In: *Nature Reviews Immunology* 6.10, pp. 728–740. DOI: [10.1038/nri1939](https://doi.org/10.1038/nri1939).
- Novobrantseva, T. (2005). “Stochastic Pairing of Ig Heavy and Light Chains Frequently Generates B Cell Antigen Receptors That Are Subject to Editing In Vivo”. In: *International Immunology* 17.4, pp. 343–350. DOI: [10.1093/intimm/dxh214](https://doi.org/10.1093/intimm/dxh214).
- Ofer, D., N. Brandes, and M. Linial (2021). “The Language of Proteins: NLP, Machine Learning & Protein Sequences”. In: *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal* 19, pp. 1750–1758. DOI: [10.1016/j.csbj.2021.03.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2021.03.022).
- Olsen, T. H., I. H. Moal, and C. M. Deane (2022). “AbLang: An Antibody Language Model for Completing Antibody Sequences”. In: *Bioinformatics Advances* 2.1, vbac046. DOI: [10.1093/bioadv/vbac046](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioadv/vbac046).
- Paszke, A. et al. (2019). “PyTorch: An Imperative Style, High-Performance Deep Learning Library”. In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 32. Curran Associates Inc., pp. 8024–8035.
- Pfeiffer, J. et al. (2020). “AdapterHub: A Framework for Adapting Transformers”. In: *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: System Demonstrations*. Ed. by Q. Liu and D. Schlangen. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 46–54. DOI: [10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-demos.7](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-demos.7).
- Ralph, D. K. and F. A. I. Matsen (2022). “Inference of B Cell Clonal Families Using Heavy / Light Chain Pairing Information”. In: *PLOS Computational Biology* 18.11, e1010723. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010723](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010723).

-
- Ruffolo, J. A., J. J. Gray, and J. Sulam (2021). “Deciphering Antibody Affinity Maturation with Language Models and Weakly Supervised Learning”. In: *arXiv*. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2112.07782](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.07782). arXiv: [2112.07782](https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.07782) [q-bio.BM].
- Soto, C. et al. (2020). “PyIR: a scalable wrapper for processing billions of immunoglobulin and T cell receptor sequences using IgBLAST”. In: *BMC Bioinformatics* 21.1, p. 314. DOI: [10.1186/s12859-020-03649-5](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-020-03649-5).
- Steinegger, M. and J. Söding (2017). “MMseqs2 Enables Sensitive Protein Sequence Searching for the Analysis of Massive Data Sets”. In: *Nature Biotechnology* 35.11, pp. 1026–1028. DOI: [10.1038/nbt.3988](https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.3988).
- Suzuki, M., C. Kato, and A. Kato (2015). “Therapeutic Antibodies: Their Mechanisms of Action and the Pathological Findings They Induce in Toxicity Studies”. In: *Journal of Toxicologic Pathology* 28.3, pp. 133–139. DOI: [10.1293/tox.2015-0031](https://doi.org/10.1293/tox.2015-0031).
- Van Der Kant, R. et al. (2019). “Adaption of human antibody λ and κ light chain architectures to CDR repertoires”. In: *Protein Engineering, Design and Selection* 32.3, pp. 109–127. DOI: [10.1093/protein/gzz012](https://doi.org/10.1093/protein/gzz012).
- Wasdin, P. T. (2024). “Generation of Antigen-Specific Paired Chain Antibody Sequences Using Large Language Models”. In: *Bioinformatics*. DOI: [10.1101/2024.12.20.629482](https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.20.629482).
- Wolf, T., L. Debut, and V. Sanh (2020). “Transformers: State-of-the-Art Natural Language Processing”. In: *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: System Demonstrations*. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 38–45. DOI: [10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-demos.6](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-demos.6).
- Ye, J. et al. (2013). “IgBLAST: an immunoglobulin variable domain sequence analysis tool”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 41.W1, W34–W40. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkt382](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkt382).
- You, A. and X. Xu (2024). “Deep Learning-Driven Protein Design”. In: *Advances in Computer Signals and Systems* 8.1, pp. 170–175. DOI: [10.23977/acss.2024.080120](https://doi.org/10.23977/acss.2024.080120).

Conclusions and Future Directions

Summary of key findings

This dissertation presents a comprehensive paradigm for exploiting large protein language models (pLMs) to address pivotal problems in protein engineering and antibody discovery, demonstrating both methodological innovation and new applications.

In Chapter 2, our **protein thermostability framework**, TemBERTure, demonstrates that transformer-based language models can capture key signals of protein thermostability directly from sequence: models trained on diverse, multi-species datasets reliably reproduced the overall melting temperature distribution of the Meltome Atlas and generalized substantially better than those trained on narrow, organism-biased collections. Despite modest accuracy in predicting exact temperature values, TemBERTure_{T_m} distinguished thermophilic from mesophilic proteins by learning species-normalized stability patterns, while TemBERTure_{CLS} achieved a high accuracy in discriminating thermophiles from non-thermophiles. Attention maps highlighted amino-acid positions and motifs—such as increased aromatic and charged residues in stabilizing microenvironments—that correlate with higher thermal resistance. Importantly, attention-driven analysis within a structural context revealed residue interactions congruent with known thermostability determinants (e.g. hydrophobic core packing), underscoring the model’s ability to infer biophysically meaningful features without explicit 3D input. These results validate the feasibility of sequence-only, deep-learning approaches for large-scale thermostability screening and point to attention scores as a promising route toward mechanistic interpretability.

Chapter 3 advances a region-focused modeling strategy via **H3BERTa**, a RoBERTa-based language model pretrained on 18 million antibody complementarity determining region H3 (CDR-H3) loops. Using H3BERTa, allowed us to capture biologically meaningful patterns in antibody repertoires: its embeddings naturally clustered by J-gene usage, and sequence perplexity correlated with loop length and amino-acid composition. Hierarchical clustering of pseudo-perplexity distributions robustly separated healthy and bnAb donor repertoires, with significant differences driven by the distribution tails rather than central values. When applied to single-sequence classification, a linear SVM on H3BERTa embeddings achieved over 90% accuracy and outperformed a full-chain model (AntiBERTa), while a semi-supervised GAN-BERT fine-tuning reduced false positives in realistic, imbalanced repertoires. These results demonstrate that a CDR-H3-focused language model can both recapitulate repertoire-level distinctions and support accurate bnAb discovery from large, unselected datasets.

In Chapter 4, we tackle the complex problem of **heavy-to-light chain translation** and relationships in antibodies: by pre-training HeavyBERTa and LightGPT on millions of unpaired sequences and fine-tuning them on paired datasets, we achieved high accuracy in B cell developmental origin classification and generated plausible light chains from heavy-chain inputs. Our Heavy2Light

model recovered native light chains with 62% sequence identity, indicating that structurally critical interaction motifs can be preserved even with sequence divergence. Conditioning on the heavy chain markedly improved germline similarity, region completeness, and structural confidence (pTM, pLDDT), demonstrating that heavy-chain context guides biologically realistic light-chain folding. These findings highlight the promise of sequence-only, generative deep learning for antibody repertoire engineering and design.

Open challenges and limitations

Key limitations of our **protein-thermostability prediction** framework stem primarily from data biases and model interpretability. First, uneven taxonomic representation—particularly the under-sampling of true thermophiles and the temperature “gap” in the Meltome Atlas between 60–70 °C—skews the model toward organism-specific signals rather than intrinsic stability features. Second, reliance on growth-temperature proxies ignores the fact that many mesophilic proteomes harbor thermostable outliers, undermining label fidelity. Third, datasets with narrow sequence diversity (e.g., BacDive-derived) yield models that generalize poorly to novel or challenging test sets, highlighting the necessity of broad, balanced data curation. Finally, the impact of more sequence-identity thresholds during dataset splitting remains underexplored, leaving open the question of optimal partitioning strategies for robust, unbiased model evaluation.

In the context of **CDR-H3-based classification**, although H3BERTa-based classifier’s metrics are compelling, the observed ~18% false positive rate when applied to HIV-infected repertoires highlights limitations of narrow sequence windows. The omission of flanking framework regions and adjacent CDR loops may obscure critical allosteric or structural context; future iterations should explore multimodal inputs that integrate more features to enhance specificity and reduce false bnAb assignments.

Key limitations of our study regarding **heavy-to-light chain translation**, are including reliance on the OAS database, which under-represents naïve B cells and may bias both HeavyBERTa’s and LightGPT’s learned priors toward memory- or antigen-experienced repertoires. The moderate sequence recovery and pairing rate underscore that many generated light chains still diverge substantially from native sequences, risking loss of subtle specificity determinants. Trimodal identity distributions in kappa chains hint at repertoire complexity that our models do not fully disentangle. Finally, fine-tuning on paired data still leverages relatively small, potentially unbalanced cohorts; expanding to larger, more diverse, and experimentally validated datasets—and integrating structural constraints or alternative generative architectures—will be essential to improve generalizability and therapeutic utility.

Although protein language models have revolutionised therapeutic protein and antibody discovery, they still face three core limitations that we encountered in this dissertation: (i) pre-training corpora are biased toward germline-like, mesophilic sequences, leaving uncommon CDR loops and extreme physicochemical regimes under-represented; (ii) sequence-only objectives overlook key structural and biochemical constraints that are seldom annotated in large datasets; and (iii) model interpretability lags behind accuracy, making it difficult to translate embeddings into actionable design rules. Future progress should therefore depend on curating more diverse, property-rich corpora, fusing sequence embeddings with biophysical descriptors in multimodal architectures, and deploying high-throughput standardize validation to iteratively fine-tune models while illuminating the causal links between sequence, structure and function.

Supplementary materials for Chapter 2: "TemBERTure: advancing protein thermostability prediction with deep learning and attention mechanisms"

A.0.1 Ensemble evaluation for melting temperature prediction

To enhance a better melting temperature prediction of TemBERTure_{T_m} , we evaluated model ensembles on the validation set. These ensembles were constructed by selecting a subset of the initial 18 models, which covered all distinct initialization methods (random and transfer learning with TemBERTure_{CLS} weights) and their duplicates. We explored three ensemble approaches: greedy algorithm, weighted ensemble, and a method leveraging TemBERTure_{CLS} . Additionally, we experimented with various averaging techniques (standard deviation and interquartile range) to combine predictions and identify the optimal value for each data point. Overall, these ensemble strategies aimed to harness the strengths of multiple models and achieve effectiveness across a broad temperature range.

Averaging The predictions were averaged across all replicas, resulting in an average melting temperature from 18 models per observation.

IQR and standard deviation The predictions of all models were aggregated. We then identified and removed outliers using either the Interquartile Range (IQR) or a 3 standard deviation threshold. The remaining inliers are averaged for a final prediction.

Greedy search ensemble The greedy ensemble approach aimed to identify an optimal combination of models to minimize Mean Absolute Error (MAE) on the validation set. We began by initializing the ensemble with the model having achieved the lowest MAE. We then iteratively evaluated the performance (based on MAE) by adding one additional model to the ensemble. If the average prediction resulted in a lower overall MAE, we updated the ensemble to include that model. The process continued until no further improvement was obtained for a maximum of 3 iterations. We also carried out a similar approach, setting the maximum number of models to 5.

Classification-based ensemble This method leverages a two-stage ensemble approach for predicting melting temperature. Each sequence in the validation set is assigned a class label (thermophilic or non-thermophilic) using the TemBERTure_{CLS} model. For each class, a greedy search ensemble approach was employed to select the set of models that minimized the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) on the corresponding target melting temperature values.

TABLE A.1: Summary of the data-processing pipeline for TemBERTure_{DB}.

Step	Description	Input	Output	Source of Data
1	Sequence Acquisition – retrieve sequences for organisms in Meltome Atlas Ennagar et al., 2022	13 organisms	4 283 681 sequences (40 970 thermophilic; 4 242 711 non-thermophilic)	UniProtKB (Consortium, 2023)
2	Initial Centroid Generation – cluster sequences using MMseqs (>50 % identity)	Sequences from Step 1	574 600 non-thermophilic; 13 330 thermophilic centroids	Sequences from Step 1
3	Data Balancing (Thermophilic) – enrich thermophilic data	Organisms with growth temperature > 60 °C	467 thermophilic organisms (bacteria & archaea)	BacDive database (Reimer et al., 2022)
4	Protein Sequence Retrieval (Thermophilic) – retrieve protein sequences and filter out short sequences (<30 aa)	Thermophilic organisms (Step 3)	886 269 thermophilic protein sequences	NCBI database (Sayers et al., 2022)
5	Centroid Generation (Thermophilic) – cluster thermophilic sequences (MMseqs, >50 % identity)	Thermophilic sequences (Step 4)	272 658 thermophilic centroids	Thermophilic sequences from Step 4
6	Data Balancing (Non-thermophilic) – enrich non-thermophilic data	Organisms with growth temperature < 30 °C	11 028 non-thermophilic organisms (10 988 bacteria; 40 archaea)	BacDive database (Reimer et al., 2022)
7	Protein Sequence Retrieval (Non-thermophilic) – retrieve protein sequences and filter out short sequences (<30 aa)	Non-thermophilic organisms (Step 6)	35 247 992 protein sequences for non-thermophilic organisms	NCBI database (Sayers et al., 2022)
8	Centroid Generation (Non-thermophilic) – cluster non-thermophilic sequences (MMseqs, >80 % identity)	Non-thermophilic sequences (Step 7)	15 756 711 non-thermophilic centroids	Non-thermophilic sequences from Step 6
9	Challenging Pairs (Non-thermophilic) – derive only non-thermophilic sequences that are 80–95 % identical to thermophilic sequences	Thermophilic and non-thermophilic sequences (Steps 5 & 8)	37 203 challenging sequences	Thermophilic and non-thermophilic sequences from Steps 5 & 8
10	TemBERTure _{DB} – merge and balance data from Meltome Atlas, BacDive, and UniProt derived in previous steps	All previous data	241 472 thermophilic; 250 605 non-thermophilic sequences	All previous data

TABLE A.2: Summary of the data-processing pipeline for BacDive_{DB}.

Step	Description	Input	Output	Source of Data
1	Protein Sequence Retrieval (Thermophilic) – retrieve protein sequences for organisms with growth temperature > 60°C and filter out short sequences (< 30 aa)	Organisms with growth temperature > 60°C	900 859 thermophilic protein sequences	BacDive database (Reimer et al., 2022)
2	Centroid Generation (Thermophilic) – cluster thermophilic sequences (MMseqs, > 50% identity)	Thermophilic sequences (step 2)	278 894 thermophilic	NCBI database (Sayers et al., 2022)
3	Protein Sequence Retrieval (Non-thermophilic) – retrieve protein sequences for organisms with growth temperature < 30°C and filter out short sequences (< 30 aa)	Organisms with growth temperature < 30°C	40 032 534 protein sequences for non-thermophilic organisms	Thermophilic sequences from step 1 BacDive database (Reimer et al., 2022)
4	Reduce the Number of Non-thermophilic Sequences – cluster non-thermophilic sequences (MMseqs cascading clustering)	Non-thermophilic sequences (step 3)	3 985 266 non-thermophilic centroids; randomly select the same amount as the thermophilic dataset (900 859 non-thermophilic)	NCBI database (Sayers et al., 2022)
5	Centroid Generation (Non-thermophilic) – cluster non-thermophilic sequences (MMseqs, > 50% identity)	Non-thermophilic sequences (step 4)	861 960 non-thermophilic	Non-thermophilic sequences from step 3
6	BacDive _{DB} – merge and balance data from previous steps	All previous data	278 894 thermophilic; 278 894 non-thermophilic	Non-thermophilic sequences from step 4 All previous data

TABLE A.3: Summary of the data-processing pipeline for Meltome_{DB}.

Step	Description	Input	Output	Source of Data
1	Sequence Acquisition (Jarzab et al., 2020) – retrieve sequences for organisms in Meltome Atlas	13 organisms	4 283 681 sequences thermophilic; 4 242 711 non-thermophilic)	UniProtKB (Reimer et al., 2022)
2	Initial Centroid Generation – cluster sequences using MMseqs (> 50 % identity)	Sequences from Step 1	574 600 non-thermophilic; 13 330 thermophilic centroids	Sequences from Step 1
3	Data Balancing (Thermophilic) – retrieve protein sequences for organisms with growth temperature > 60°C and filter out short sequences (< 30 aa)	Organisms with growth temperature > 60°C	881 831 thermophilic protein sequences	BacDive database (Reimer et al., 2022)
4	Centroid Generation (Thermophilic) – cluster the thermophilic sequences (MMseqs, > 50 % identity)	Thermophilic sequences (step 4)	286 123 thermophilic	NCBI database (Sayers et al., 2022)
5	Meltome _{DB} – merge and balance data from Meltome Atlas, BacDive, and UniProt derived in previous steps	All previous data	286 123 thermophilic; non-thermophilic	Thermophilic sequences from Step 4 All previous data

TABLE A.4: TemBERTure_{CLS} model hyperparameter tuning for different datasets. The optimal setting is highlighted in bold.

Hyperparameter	BacDive	Meltome	TemBERTure _{DB} (3 replicas)
Learning rate	5e-3, 5e-4, 5e-5, 5e-6	5e-3, 5e-4, 5e-5, 5e-6	1e-3, 1e-4, 1e-5 , 1e-6
Head dropout probability	0 , 0.1	0 , 0.1	0, 0.1 , 0.2, 0.3, 0.4
Head activation function	tanh	tanh	tanh
Warmup ratio	0	0	0, 0.10
Weight decay	0	0	0, 0.10
Lowest validation loss	Epoch 9	Epoch 10	Epoch (4, 4, 5)
Training time	23 hours	32 hours	37 hours

TABLE A.5: TemBERTure_{*T_m*} hyperparameter tuning. Optimal parameters are shown in **bold**.

Hyperparameter	Values explored
Learning rate	1e-2, 1e-3 , 1e-4, 1e-5
Head layers	1, 2
Head dropout probability	0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 , 0.4
Head activation function	tanh, ReLU , LeakyReLU
Warmup ratio	0 , 0.10
Weight decay	0 , 0.10

TABLE A.6: Number of sequences in the TemBERTure_{*DB*} classifier and regression datasets.

	Classifier			Regression		
	Train	Validation	Test	Train	Validation	Test
Thermophilic	241 472	26 649	26 643	10 296	203	209
Non-thermophilic	250 605	22 404	22 380	19 780	319	322

TABLE A.7: Comparison between our TemBERTure_{CLS} model and other state-of-the-art models on the TemBERTure_{DB} test set.

Models	Thermo. Recall	Non-thermo. Recall	Avg. Accuracy	F1-Score	Non-thermo. Precision	Thermo. Precision	MCC
TemBERTure _{CLS}	0.889	0.897	0.893	0.900	0.872	0.911	0.784
iThermo(Ahmed et al., 2022)	0.633	0.812	0.723	0.707	0.650	0.800	0.448
SCMTPP (Charoenkwan et al., 2021)	0.477	0.847	0.662	0.594	0.577	0.788	0.344
ThermoPred (Lin and Chen, 2011)	0.636	0.798	0.717	0.704	0.648	0.789	0.435
BertThermo (Pei et al., 2023)	0.700	0.809	0.755	0.753	0.694	0.814	0.509
TemStaPro-major-30 (t60) (Pudžiuvėlytė et al., 2024)	0.847	0.922	0.877	0.892	0.805	0.941	0.757

TABLE A.8: TemBERTure_{CLS} generalization ability. Performance on external test sets after removing sequences with >50 % identity to any TemBERTure_{DB} train/validation sequence. Because the filtered sets are highly imbalanced, macro-averaged F1-score, recall, and precision are reported.

Dataset	Non-overlap		Non-overlap		F1-score	Recall	Precision
	Thermophilic Seq.	Non-thermophilic Seq.	Thermophilic Seq.	Non-thermophilic Seq.			
iThermo(Ahmed et al., 2022)	65	505	0.773	0.924	0.729		
TemStaPro _{minor-30} (t60) (Pudžiuvėlytė et al., 2024)	1495	10849	0.738	0.891	0.705		

TABLE A.9: Ensemble performance on the regression *validation* set. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) measures the discrepancy between predicted and observed melting temperatures; the coefficient of determination (R^2) assesses goodness of fit.

Ensemble / Oracle	Metric	All	Non-thermophilic	Thermophilic
Oracle	MAE	3.369	3.530	3.117
	R^2	0.910	0.715	0.595
Greedy algorithm (11 models)	MAE	7.004	6.981	7.041
	R^2	0.748	0.250	-0.274
Weighted ensemble (5 models)	MAE	7.065	7.028	7.124
	R^2	0.741	0.240	-0.343
Classification-based: non-thermophilic (5) / thermophilic (5)	MAE	6.769	6.834	6.668
	R^2	0.761	0.261	-0.135
Average after IQR outlier id.	MAE	7.042	7.010	7.092
	R^2	0.746	0.247	-0.297
Average after STD outlier id.	MAE	7.057	7.027	7.104
	R^2	0.746	0.248	-0.297
Average within best replicas	MAE	5.182	5.237	5.096
	R^2	0.837	0.505	0.205
Average within all replicas	MAE	7.056	7.023	7.107
	R^2	0.746	0.249	-0.297

FIGURE A.1: Effect of fine-tuning on amino acid High Attention Score (HAS) frequency. Scatterplot comparing the high attention frequency of amino acids as identified by the pretrained protBERT-BFD 10 model (x-axis) versus the fine-tuned TemBERTure_{CLS} model (y-axis) respectively for non-thermophilic sequences (A) and thermophilic sequences (B). Each point represents an amino acid, with its position reflecting the change in attention frequency after fine-tuning. Amino acids located above the diagonal have gained attention in the fine-tuned model and are colored in gray

FIGURE A.2: Amino acid frequency and HAS frequency. The bar chart presents a dual-layered comparison: the upper segment displays the frequency of individual amino acids within the TemBERTure_{DB} test set, while the lower segment focuses specifically on the frequency of HAS amino acids. Red bars represent the prevalence of amino acids in thermophilic proteins, and blue bars denote their occurrence in non-thermophilic proteins.

FIGURE A.3: Comparison of TemBERTure_{CLS} attention scores on pairs of protein homologs. Scatter plots illustrate the attention scores between thermophilic and non-thermophilic paired Protein Data Bank (PDB) structures. Each plot corresponds to a unique pair, denoted by their respective PDB IDs. Red and blue markers indicate HAS for thermophilic and non-thermophilic respectively, and diamonds and circles differentiate between conserved and non-conserved amino acids, and triangles represent insertions.

FIGURE A.4: Mapping of TemBERTure_{CLS} attention score on protein structures. Set of 16 pairs of homologous non-thermophilic (the left of each pair) and thermophilic (the right of each pair) protein structures extracted from the Protein Data Bank. Each pair of protein structures is depicted side by side for comparative analysis. Regions with a higher attention score are thickened and colored in red.

FIGURE A.5: Comparison of TemBERTure_{CLS} attention scores and entropy per residue on protein structures. Scatter plots comparing attention scores with entropy values for thermophilic (red IDs) and non-thermophilic (blue IDs) protein structures, distinguished by their respective PDB IDs. Each point represents a protein residue, with red markers specifically indicating High-Attention Scores (HAS).

References

- Ahmed, Z., H. Zulfiqar, and A. A. Khan (2022). “iThermo: a sequence-based model for identifying thermophilic proteins using a multi-feature fusion strategy”. In: *Frontiers in Microbiology* 13, p. 790063. DOI: [10.3389/fmicb.2022.790063](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.790063).
- Charoenkwan, P., W. Chotpatiwetchkul, and V. S. Lee (2021). “A novel sequence-based predictor for identifying and characterizing thermophilic proteins using estimated propensity scores of dipeptides”. In: *Scientific Reports* 11, p. 23782. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-021-03293-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-03293-w).
- Consortium, T. U. (2023). “UniProt: the universal protein knowledgebase in 2023”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 51, pp. D523–D531. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkac1052](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac1052).
- Elnaggar, A., M. Heinzinger, and C. Dallago (2022). “ProtTrans: toward understanding the language of life through self-supervised learning”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 44, pp. 7112–7127. DOI: [10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3095381](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3095381).
- Jarzab, A., N. Kurzawa, and T. Hopf (2020). “Meltome atlas—thermal proteome stability across the tree of life”. In: *Nature Methods* 17, pp. 495–503. DOI: [10.1038/s41592-020-0801-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-020-0801-4).
- Lin, H. and W. Chen (2011). “Prediction of thermophilic proteins using feature selection technique”. In: *Journal of Microbiological Methods* 84, pp. 67–70. DOI: [10.1016/j.mimet.2010.10.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mimet.2010.10.013).
- Pei, H., J. Li, and S. Ma (2023). “Identification of thermophilic proteins based on sequence-based bidirectional representations from transformer-embedding features”. In: *Applied Sciences* 13, p. 2858. DOI: [10.3390/app13052858](https://doi.org/10.3390/app13052858).
- Pudžiuvėlytė, I., K. Olechnovič, and E. Godliauskaite (2024). “TemStaPro: protein thermostability prediction using sequence representations from protein language models”. In: *Bioinformatics* 40, btae157. DOI: [10.1093/bioinformatics/btae157](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btae157).
- Reimer, L. C., J. Sardà Carbasse, and J. Koblitz (2022). “BacDive in 2022: the knowledge base for standardized bacterial and archaeal data”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 50, pp. D741–D746. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkab961](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab961).
- Sayers, E. W., E. E. Bolton, and J. R. Brister (2022). “Database resources of the National Center for Biotechnology Information”. In: *Nucleic Acids Research* 50, pp. D20–D26. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkab1112](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab1112).

Supplementary materials for Chapter 3: "Discriminating HIV-1 broadly neutralizing antibodies via CDR-H3 language model embeddings and perplexity"

FIGURE B.1: Comparison of perplexity values calculated with AntiBERTa (x-axis) and HB3ERTa (y-axis) on a healthy repertoire, specifically on the heavy chain and CDRH3 loop, respectively. Each point represents a sentence: shifts to the right indicate an increase in perplexity for AntiBERTa, and shifts upwards indicate an increase for HB3ERTa.

FIGURE B.2: UMAP visualization of H3BERTa-derived embeddings for CDRH3 loops from a bnAb donor (left) versus a healthy donor (right). In the top row, each point represents a single CDRH3 embedding colored by IGHJ gene-segment usage; in the bottom row, embeddings are colored by IGHV gene-segment usage. Marginal ridge plots alongside each UMAP axis depict the density of individual V- and J-gene families.

FIGURE B.3: Latent space representations of CDR-H3 sequences stratified by donor group and J gene usage. (A) CDR-H3 sequences from bnAb donors and (B) from healthy donors projected into two-dimensional latent spaces using PCA (top rows) and UMAP (bottom rows). Each point corresponds to a single CDR-H3 sequence and is colored according to its associated J gene. The marginal density plots display the distribution of each J gene projection along the first principal or UMAP component. Across both donor groups and projection methods, sequences cluster with varying degrees of separation by J gene, reflecting latent representations that partially preserve genetic origin. Notably, UMAP projections reveal more distinct gene-specific clustering, particularly among bnAb donors.

FIGURE B.4: Latent space representations of CDR-H3 sequences stratified by donor group and V gene usage. (A) CDR-H3 sequences from bnAb donors and (B) from healthy donors projected into two-dimensional latent spaces using PCA (top rows) and UMAP (bottom rows). Each point corresponds to a single CDR-H3 sequence and is colored according to its associated V gene. The marginal density plots display the distribution of each V gene projection along the first principal or UMAP component. Across both donor groups and projection methods, sequences cluster with varying degrees of separation by V gene, reflecting latent representations that partially preserve genetic origin. Notably, UMAP projections reveal more distinct gene-specific clustering, particularly among bnAb donors.

FIGURE B.5: (A) Box plots of pairwise Wasserstein distances between CDR-H3 perplexity distributions from H3BERTA. Distances are shown for comparisons within healthy donors (green), within bnAb donors (blue), and between the two cohorts (grey). Lower values indicate more similar repertoires. Healthy donors display the lowest median distance, whereas inter-cohort comparisons are shifted upward, signalling a partial separation of the two perplexity landscapes. (B) Heatmaps of the same pairwise distances. The left panel includes only healthy donors; the right panel includes only bnAb donors. Samples are ordered by hierarchical clustering to highlight similarity patterns. Colours progress from yellow (0; high similarity) through orange to black (= 2; high dissimilarity). The healthy cohort forms a largely homogeneous block, while the bnAb cohort shows several darker off-diagonal patches, pointing to greater intra-group heterogeneity.

FIGURE B.6: Perplexity distributions of CDR-H3 sequences from healthy and bnAb donors. Kernel density estimates show that both distributions are heavily right-skewed, with most sequences having low perplexity scores. An inset highlights the right tail of the distribution, where rare high-perplexity sequences are more visible.

FIGURE B.7: CDR-H3 length and amino acid composition across perplexity-defined groups in Healthy and bnAb repertoires. (A) Boxplots of CDR-H3 lengths stratified by perplexity group (Low, Central, High PPL) and immune status (Healthy: green; bnAb: blue). Across all perplexity ranges, bnAb-derived sequences tend to exhibit slightly shorter CDR-H3 regions than those from healthy repertoires. However, the overall length distributions remain broadly comparable, with similar ranges and outlier patterns across groups. (B) Amino acid frequency profiles within CDR-H3 sequences for each subgroup. The amino acid composition remains largely consistent between healthy and bnAb repertoires across all perplexity-defined groups, indicating conserved biochemical properties in the CDR-H3 regions despite immune status.

FIGURE B.8: Length distribution of CDR-H3 sequences across perplexity-defined groups. Kernel density estimates of CDR-H3 amino acid lengths for sequences categorized into Low PPL (orange), Central PPL (magenta), and High PPL (dark purple) groups. While all groups display a peak in the 12–18 amino acid range, Low PPL sequences tend to be longer, indicating a potential association between lower model perplexity and naive CDR-H3 regions. CDR-H3 sequences with lengths greater than 40 amino acids were removed from the plot as outliers to improve the clarity of the density distribution.

FIGURE B.9: Biochemical properties of CDR-H3 sequences across perplexity-defined groups. Boxplots of (A) net charge at physiological pH (7.0) and (B) hydrophobicity (GRAVY score) for CDR-H3 sequences stratified by model-derived perplexity into Low, Central, and High PPL groups. Sequences in the Low PPL group exhibit significantly lower net charge compared to Central and High PPL groups (all $p < 0.001$, Mann-Whitney U test), suggesting a possible association between low perplexity and reduced electrostatic diversity. In contrast, GRAVY scores are relatively stable across groups, with only minor shifts despite statistically significant differences, indicating that overall hydrophobicity is not strongly differentiated by perplexity. Color-coded legends indicate PPL groups.

FIGURE B.10: Length distribution of CDR-H3 loops in bnAb and nnAb repertoires. Histogram and kernel density estimates (KDE) of CDR-H3 amino acid lengths for broadly neutralizing antibodies (bnAbs, blue) and non-neutralizing antibodies (nnAbs, green). While both distributions peak in the 14–18 residue range, bnAbs tend to exhibit a broader and slightly right-shifted distribution, with a higher proportion of longer CDR-H3 loops compared to nnAbs.

FIGURE B.11: Distribution of V gene identity across antibody repertoires with varying neutralization capacity. Violin plots showing the distribution of V gene nucleotide identity (%) for antibody sequences derived from non-neutralizing (nnAb), neutralizing (nAb), and broadly neutralizing (bnAb) repertoires. Each point represents a unique sequence, with identity calculated relative to the closest germline V gene. Despite functional differences in neutralization breadth, the three groups exhibit highly similar identity profiles, with average values of 96.31% for nnAb, 96.24% for nAb, and 96.19% for bnAb repertoires. The number of sequences per group is indicated within the plot.

Supplementary materials for Chapter 4: "Bridging the Chains: A Deep Learning Framework for Heavy-to-Light Antibody Sequence Translation and B Cell Classification"

	LightGPT	HeavyBERTa	Heavy2Light
Total clusters (# centroids)	3'751'662	113'503'257	52'262
Total sequences	28'278'253	123'867'780	588'389
Train dataset (80%)	22'622'602	99'094'224	470'711
Validation dataset (10%)	2'827'825	12'386'778	58'838
Test dataset (10%)	2'827'826	12'386'778	58'840

TABLE C.1: Dataset composition and data split allocation. Number of sequences and centroids used for training, validation, and testing across all model datasets. HeavyBERTa and LightGPT datasets show unpaired sequence counts with corresponding centroids used for cluster-based allocation (50% identity clustering). The Heavy2Light dataset shows paired sequence counts from combined OAS and PLAbDab sources with centroids derived from 30% identity clustering for allocation across data splits.

Model	Configuration	Antibody chain type	Accuracy
RoBERTa	small	Heavy	0.8895
RoBERTa	large	Heavy	0.8912
GPT-2	–	Light	0.8635

TABLE C.2: Language modeling performance across model configurations. Accuracy values represent the fraction of correctly predicted amino acid residues for masked language modeling (HeavyBERTa models with 15% random masking) and autoregressive language modeling (LightGPT model with next-token prediction), evaluated on their respective heavy and light chain datasets.

FIGURE C.1: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of learned embeddings colored by gene family annotations. (A) HeavyBERTa embeddings projected onto the first two principal components, with sequences colored by heavy chain V gene families (IGHV1-7, top) and J gene families (IGHJ1-6, bottom). (B) Light-GPT embeddings projected onto the first two principal components, with sequences colored by light chain V gene families (top) and J gene families (bottom). Each point represents an individual sequence. Density plots along each axis show the distribution of sequences across principal components.

FIGURE C.2: Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) of learned embeddings colored by gene family annotations. (A) HeavyBERTa embeddings projected onto the first two linear discriminants, with sequences colored by heavy chain V gene families (IGHV1-7, top) and J gene families (IGHJ1-6, bottom). (B) Light-GPT embeddings projected onto the first two linear discriminants, with sequences colored by light chain V gene families (top) and J gene families (bottom). Each point represents an individual sequence. Density plots along each axis show the distribution of sequences across linear discriminants. The visualization reveals separation patterns of sequences with shared gene family annotations in the learned embedding space.

Metric	HeavyBERTa (heavy chain)			LightGPT (light chain)		
	Naive	Memory	Overall	Naive	Memory	Overall
Accuracy	0.9122	0.9367	0.9231	0.5818	0.9044	0.7917
Precision	0.9500	0.8900	0.9242	0.7700	0.8000	0.7887
Recall	0.9100	0.9400	0.9231	0.5800	0.9000	0.7917
F1 score	0.9300	0.9200	0.9232	0.6600	0.8500	0.7838

TABLE C.3: Classification performance for naive and memory B cell prediction. Performance metrics for HeavyBERTa and LightGPT models in classifying antibody sequences by B cell developmental state. Metrics are reported for individual classes (naive and memory) as well as overall performance across the entire test dataset.

Dataset	Memory B cells	Naïve B cells
OAS	0.55817	0.13834
Classified from unsorted B cells	0.80571	0.05595
All combined data	0.60634	0.11190

TABLE C.4: Coherence percentages of V gene usage in memory and naive B cells for the labeled OAS database data and the previously unlabeled data classified by our model.

Region	Germline similarity		Length [AA]	
	LightGPT	Heavy2Light	LightGPT	Heavy2Light
FWR1	0.9568	0.9349	0.2084	0.2561
CDR1	0.8790	0.8355	0.0687	0.0779
FWR2	0.9639	0.9623	0.1664	0.1702
CDR2	0.9000	0.9033	0.0302	0.0302
FWR3	0.9739	0.9623	0.3221	0.3600
CDR3	0.8934	0.9009	0.0710	0.0737
Full sequence	0.9586	0.9368	0.8059	0.9680

TABLE C.5: Germline similarity and recognized sequence length of generated light chain sequences. Comparison of germline identity percentages and amino acid lengths across antibody regions (FR1-3, CDR1-3, and total sequence) for light chains generated unconditionally by LightGPT versus conditionally by the Heavy2Light model. Values represent mean germline similarity scores and sequence lengths in amino acids [AA] as determined by IgBLAST alignment analysis.

Region	Mean similarity to true light sequence (%)	Length (aa)
FWR1	59.4296	25.81
CDR1	36.5724	8.45
FWR2	74.2764	17.04
CDR2	42.3734	3.06
FWR3	71.1027	36.02
CDR3	35.8133	7.70
Full sequence	62.0042	111.26

TABLE C.6: Similarity generated light chain sequences to their corresponding true light sequence. Comparison of identity percentages across antibody regions (FR1–3, CDR1–3, and total sequence) for light chains generated conditionally by Heavy2Light. Values represent mean germline similarity scores to its true light sequence after global alignment; Length indicates the average region length in amino acids.

Region	Training		Validation		Test	
	Seq. Id.	Length	Seq. Id.	Length	Seq. Id.	Length
FWR1	0.9565	25.59	0.9310	25.39	0.9348	25.39
CDR1	0.8595	7.48	0.7536	7.84	0.7510	7.22
FWR2	0.9593	17.01	0.9099	17.03	0.9123	17.02
CDR2	0.8944	3.05	0.7749	3.06	0.7958	3.03
FWR3	0.9652	36.03	0.9279	36.03	0.9278	36.01
CDR3	0.8902	7.26	0.7960	7.33	0.8049	7.04
Full sequence	0.9448	96.41	0.8967	96.66	0.9000	95.64

TABLE C.7: Germline identity across antibody regions (FR1–FR3, CDR1–CDR3, and full sequence) for light chains in the training, validation, and test sets. Sequence identity is expressed as the fraction of germline-matched residues; Length is the average region length in amino acids.

FIGURE C.3: Distribution of percent identity across light chain V gene families: Kernel density estimation plots showing the distribution of calculated similarity (percent identity) for immunoglobulin light chain sequences grouped by V gene family. (A) Kappa chain sequences showing V gene family-specific distributions of sequence similarity. (B) Lambda chain sequences showing V gene family-specific distributions of sequence similarity. Each colored line represents a different V gene family, with density curves indicating the frequency distribution of sequences at various similarity percentages.

FIGURE C.4: V gene family distribution across generated and reference antibody light chain sequences. V gene family usage in (A) overrepresented generated sequences (≥ 100 occurrences), (B) all generated sequences from the Heavy2Light model, (C) true light chain sequences from the test set, and (D) true light chain sequences from the training set. IGKV1 predominates across all datasets. Numbers above bars indicate absolute counts and percentages.

FIGURE C.5: Distribution of pairing compatibility scores for Heavy2Light generated sequences. Histogram showing the distribution of Immunomatch pairing probability scores for light chain sequences generated by the Heavy2Light model.

FIGURE C.6: Distribution of germline identity and region lengths for light chain sequences across dataset splits. For each dataset (A: Training set, B: Validation set, and C: Test set), violin plots show the distribution of mean percent identity to germline sequences (upper panel) and mean sequence lengths (lower panel) for framework regions (FR1-3) and complementarity-determining regions (CDR1-3). Black dashed lines indicate the mean values for each region.

Training Configuration	
Number of epochs	50
Batch size	64
Learning rate	$1e^{-5}$
Weight decay	0.1
Optimizer	AdamW
Learning-rate scheduler	Linear
Gradient clipping (max-norm)	1.0
Seed	42
Model Architecture	
Model type	Encoder–Decoder
Encoder	HeavyBERTa (RoBERTa-based)
Decoder	LightGPT (GPT-2-based)
Cross-attention	Enabled
Vocabulary size	25
<i>Encoder (HeavyBERTa)</i>	
Hidden size	512
Layers	4
Attention heads	4
Intermediate size	2048
Max sequence length	512
<i>Decoder (LightGPT)</i>	
Hidden size	768
Layers	12
Attention heads	12
Context length	1024
Generation Parameters	
Sampling method	Nucleus (top- p)
Top- p	0.85
Temperature	0.8
Top- k	0
Max new tokens	115
Adapter Configuration	
Adapter type	Bottleneck
Multi-head adapter	True
Output adapter	True
Reduction factor	16
Activation function	ReLU
Final Performance	
Final training loss	0.2078
Final evaluation loss	0.3828
Total training steps	367 750
Training runtime	~34.9 h

TABLE C.8: Hyper-parameters and performance of the Encoder–Decoder model (HeavyBERTa encoder, LightGPT decoder).

Hyper-parameter / Metric	Small config.	Large config.
<i>Training setup</i>		
Number of epochs	22	9.18
Batch size	16	16
Learning rate	5×10^{-5}	5×10^{-5}
Weight decay	0.1	0.1
Optimizer	AdamW	AdamW
LR scheduler	Linear	Linear
<i>Model architecture</i>		
Model type	RobertaForMaskedLM	
Vocabulary size	25	25
Max sequence length	512	512
Max position embeddings	514	514
Position embedding type	Absolute	Absolute
Hidden activation	GELU	GELU
Hidden size	512	768
Layers	4	12
Attention heads	4	12
Intermediate size	2048	3072
<i>Performance</i>		
Final training loss	0.4476	0.4379
Final evaluation loss	0.4376	0.4234
Evaluation accuracy	0.8895	0.8912
Total training steps	136 254 500	56 832 000
Training runtime	~244 h	~673 h

TABLE C.9: HeavyBERTa model training parameters and performances.

Training Configuration	
Number of epochs	83
Batch size / total batch size	16 / 32
Learning rate	5×10^{-5}
Weight decay	0.1
Optimizer	AdamW
LR scheduler	Linear
Model Architecture	
Model type	GPT2LMHeadModel
Vocabulary size	25
Context length / max positions	1024
Hidden activation	gelu_new
Hidden size	768
Layers	12
Attention heads	12
Inner dimension	3072
Embedding / attention / residual dropout	0.1 / 0.1 / 0.1
Layer-norm ϵ	1×10^{-5}
Initializer range	0.02
Performance	
Final training loss	0.3517
Final evaluation loss	0.5446
Evaluation accuracy	0.8635
Total training steps	12 265 000
Training runtime	~606 h

TABLE C.10: LightGPT language-model pre-training hyper-parameters and performance.

Parameter	HeavyBERTa classifier	LightGPT classifier
Max length	150	150
Batch size	64	64
Epochs	200	50
Learning rate	$3e^{-6}$	$3e^{-6}$
Weight decay	0.01	0.01
Dropout	0.1	0.3

TABLE C.11: Training parameters for naive/memory B cell classification models. Hyperparameters used for fine-tuning HeavyBERTa to classify heavy chain sequences and LightGPT to classify light chain sequences by B cell developmental state (naive vs. memory).

CHIARA RODELLA

BioMed Machine Learning Scientist

✉ rodella.chiara@gmail.com

📍 Switzerland, Permit B holder

🆔 0009-0002-2127-6594

🐙 Ch-rode

👤 chiara-rodella

🗣️ English (fluent), Italian (native)

Work Experience

08/2025

– 10/2021

Doctoral Researcher

University of Bern – Bern, CH

Main contributions:

- **Supervisor** of two Master's theses and one Master's project;
- Organized the NLP-in-Biotech Symposium, sponsored by the University of Bern and Roche, featuring three keynotes, PhD presentations, and a roundtable discussion;
- Responsible for the lab's **HPC administration**.

09/2021

–
11/2019

Data Scientist | Strategic Accounts

SAS Institute – Milan, Italy

- Main tasks: Advised major Finance and Telco clients on Advanced Analytics, AI, and Customer Intelligence solutions, actively contributing to the design and development of **data-driven transformation projects**. Designed and delivered business proposals, POCs, and presentations, showcasing the value of **SAS technologies**.
- Project highlights: Developed an **anomaly detection** system for VoLTE networks; built a data-driven employee attrition model to predict turnover and improve employee journey insights; integrated **open source tools** into SAS technologies.

Education

08/2025

– 10/2021

PhD in Computational Biology

University of Bern – Bern, CH – Professor Thomas Lemmin Lab

- Major: **Natural Language Processing** for Biological Application.
- Thesis Project: Exploring the architecture of **immune repertoires** with neural networks for the computational design of **therapeutic antibodies**
Supervisor: Prof. Thomas Lemmin.
- Key topics: **AI, NLP, Deep Learning, Graph Neural Network, Antibody, Molecular Dynamics, Docking, Protein language models**.

09/2020

–
09/2018

Master in Statistical Sciences and Data Analytics

Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore – Milan, Italy

- Two-year program. Grade: Summa cum laude.
- Thesis Title: **Personal data anonymization** using Natural Language Processing, Supervisor: Prof. Andrea Belli.
- Contribution: Building a **Flask API** to automatically extract personal named entities to provide a free data anonymization tool.
- Main subjects: **Computational Statistics, Inference, Bayesian Statistics**.

11/2018

–
09/2015

Bachelor in Economics and Management

Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore – Milan, Italy

- Three-year program. **Finance major**. Grade: Summa cum laude.
- Thesis Title: The blockchain as an innovation tool,
Supervisor: Prof. Andrea Mezzadri.
- Main subjects: **Economic Policy, Financial Accounting, Financial Markets**.

RESEARCH EXPERIENCE & PRESENTATIONS

- 14-16/07/2022 Poster, MMSML Workshop (**Method in molecular simulations and machine learning, Barcelona, Spain**), *TemBERTure: Discriminating between Thermophilic and Non-Thermophilic proteins using Natural Language Processing*
- 15-17/02/2023 **1* Best Poster Prize Bioinformatics - LS2 Annual Meeting (Zurich)**, *TemBERTure: Discriminating between Thermophilic and Non-Thermophilic proteins using Natural Language Processing*
- 27/04/2023 **Talk, BEFRI Genomics Day (Fribourg)**, *TemBERTure: Discriminating between Thermophilic and Non-Thermophilic proteins using Natural Language Processing*
- 29/06/2023 **Flash poster winner + poster, GCB Symposium (Bern)**, *TemBERTure: Discriminating between Thermophilic and Non-Thermophilic proteins using Natural Language Processing*
- 11-13/09/2023 **Talk, SIB Computational Biology Conference (Basel)**, *Identification of HIV-1 antibodies using a Deep Language Model*
- 4-6/10/2023 **Poster, Making the invisible protein life visible using integrative biophysical approaches, CECAM Workshop (Lugano)**, *TemBERTure: Discriminating between Thermophilic and Non-Thermophilic proteins using Natural Language Processing*
- 6-9/12/2023 **Talk, Computational structural biology Conference (EMBL Heidelberg, Germany)**, *Identification of HIV NAb/BnAbs using a Deep Language Model*
- 23/02/2024 **Research pitch, AI@UniBE – Research in Dialogue (Bern)**, *Identification of HIV-1 antibodies using a Deep Language Model*
- 27/06/2024 **Talk, GCB Symposium (Bern)**, *Identification of HIV-1 antibodies using a Deep Language Model*
- 01/07/2024 **SHCS AI meeting (ZOOM)**, *Identification of HIV-1 antibodies using a Deep Language Model*

List of publications

Rodella, C., Lazaridi, S., & Lemmin, T. (2024). TemBERTure: advancing protein thermostability prediction with deep learning and attention mechanisms. *Bioinformatics Advances*, 4(1), vbae103. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioadv/vbae103>

Declaration of Originality

Last name, first name: Rodella, Chiara

Matriculation number: 21-989-363

I hereby declare that this thesis represents my original work and that I have used no other sources except as noted by citations.

All data, tables, figures and text citations which have been reproduced from any other source, including the internet, have been explicitly acknowledged as such.

I am aware that in case of non-compliance, the Senate is entitled to withdraw the doctorate degree awarded to me on the basis of the present thesis, in accordance with the "Statut der Universität Bern (Universitätsstatut; UniSt)", Art. 69, of 7 June 2011.

Bern, June 11, 2025

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "Chiara Rodella". The signature is written in a cursive style with a large initial 'C' and 'R'.

Chiara Rodella